

UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY THESIS

**Edge-Accelerated Machine Learning-based Face
Verification using Open Autonomous UAV
Platforms**

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Many people have helped me along the way during these three years of my life. Here is a dedication to all of you.

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“It is the time you have wasted for your rose that makes your rose so important (Fue el tiempo que pasaste con tu rosa lo que la hizo tan importante).”

Antoine de Saint-Exupéry, *The Little Prince* (El principito)

This prospective portfolio-based PhD thesis is based on research publications. It has produced 10 outcomes composed by five scientific publications, two software programs, one physical device, one dataset and one algorithm.

Different international conferences, international journals and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) compose this research work. The main contributor of this work is the candidate who declares that has performed a major contribution to every work exposed. In the following list, several works are gathered, providing a list of the names of every publication accepted and published in international journals and conferences. In addition, other physical and logical outcomes developed to validate this research work are specified.

Outcome 1 (Conference):

Authors:	Julio Diez-Tomillo , Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero, Qi Wang
Title:	Empirical Comparison of Face Verification Algorithms from UAVs [1]
Conference:	2023 International Conference on Software, Telecommunications and Computer Networks (SoftCOM)
Publisher:	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE)
Pages:	6
Year:	2023
DOI:	10.23919/SoftCOM58365.2023.10271666

Outcome 2 (Conference):

Authors:	Julio Diez-Tomillo , Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero, Qi Wang
Title:	Edge-Accelerated UAV Operations: A Case Study of Open Source Solutions [2]
Conference:	20th International Wireless Communications & Mobile Computing Conference (IWCMC 2024)
Publisher:	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE)
Pages:	6
Year:	2024
DOI:	10.1109/IWCMC61514.2024.10592445

Outcome 3 (Journal):

Authors:	Julio Diez-Tomillo , Ignacio Martinez-Alpiste, Gelayol Gol-carenarenji, Qi Wang, Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero
Title:	Efficient CNN-based Low-Resolution Facial Detection from UAVs [3]
Journal:	Neural Computing and Applications
Publisher:	Springer
IF ¹ :	6.0
Volume:	36
Pages:	14
Year:	2024
DOI:	10.1007/s00521-023-09401-3

¹ Impact Factor.

Outcome 4 (Journal):

Authors:	Julio Diez-Tomillo , Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero, Qi Wang
Title:	Dynamic-Distance-Based Thresholding for UAV-Based Face Verification Algorithms [4]
Journal:	Sensors
Special issue:	Advances in Intelligent Sensors and IoT Solutions
Publisher:	MDPI
IF:	3.9
Volume:	23
Pages:	24
Year:	2023
DOI:	10.3390/s23249909

Outcome 5 (Journal):

Authors:	Julio Diez-Tomillo , Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero, Qi Wang
Title:	Face Verification Algorithms for UAV Applications: An Empirical Comparative Analysis [5]
Journal:	Journal of Communications Software and Systems
Publisher:	Croatian Communications and Information Society
IF:	0.7
Volume:	20
Pages:	12
Year:	2024
DOI:	10.24138/jcomss-2023-0165

Outcome 6 (Hardware):

Author:	Julio Diez-Tomillo
Title:	Open UAV architecture
Description:	Development and testing of an open-source UAV. Built with adaptable hardware and software, this UAV is compatible with various cameras and sensors. The research involved analysing the UAV's architecture, configuring its components, and fine-tuning its flight performance through flight tests.

Outcome 7 (Software):

Author:	Julio Diez-Tomillo
Title:	UAV face verification dynamic threshold calculation
Description:	Calculation of dynamic thresholds for UAV face verification algorithms, allowing to increase the accuracy just by modifying the thresholds depending on the distance from the UAV to the face.

Outcome 8 (Algorithm):

Author:	Julio Diez-Tomillo , Ignacio Martinez-Alpiste, Gelayol Golecarenarenji, Qi Wang, Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero
Title:	UWS-YOLO face detection algorithm
Description:	It is a novel breakthrough face detection algorithm. Based on the Tiny-YOLOv4 backbone, the modifications allow to maintain the low inference time, increasing the accuracy at long distances at the same time. It can detect faces from UAV video footage at up to 30 metres.

Outcome 9 (Software):

Author:	Julio Diez-Tomillo
Title:	Guardian Ground Control Station
Description:	Guardian, a modified version of the open-source QGroundControl software, serves as the ground control station for this research project. It enables configuration, mission planning, and telemetry display for unmanned vehicles, including UAVs and UGVs. Guardian extends its functionality to receive and display detection messages from these vehicles, allowing the mission commander to visualise detected locations on a map and send vehicles autonomously to those locations.

Abstract

This thesis presents a novel open-source Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) platform designed to be sensor-agnostic, enabling the integration of various cameras and sensors. The platform incorporates a companion computer, the BeagleBone AI-64, with onboard Artificial Intelligence (AI) capabilities, facilitating real-time data processing and analysis during flight. A key focus of this research is the evaluation of face verification algorithms for UAV applications. The study investigates the effectiveness of different face verification algorithms and introduces a novel dynamic distance-based thresholding technique to enhance their accuracy while varying distances, exhibiting that an improvement of 15% in accuracy can be achieved.

Moreover, a new face detection algorithm, UWS-YOLO, is proposed, demonstrating superior performance in detecting faces from UAV-captured images compared to existing methods, enabling effective face detection from UAV footage up to 30 metres with a low inference time of only 11 ms, 345% faster than RetinaFace and 373% than YOLOv7. Moreover, it achieves 59.29% of accuracy compared with 27.43% of RetinaFace and 46.59% of YOLOv7.

The integration of AI algorithms into the open UAV platform is explored, showcasing the potential for real-time face detection and verification during UAV operations. The research also addresses ethical considerations and privacy concerns related to facial verification technologies, emphasising the importance of compliance with regulations such as the European Union (EU) AI Act and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

The results demonstrate significant improvements in face verification accuracy and inference speed, validating the proposed methodologies and system architecture. This research has successfully achieved all its objectives, resulting in a novel, cost-effective, open

UAV platform with advanced AI capabilities. This work not only advances the field of UAV-based biometric verification but also opens new avenues for research and practical applications in security, surveillance, and beyond, offering a cost-effective and adaptable solution for face verification tasks. The open-source nature of the platform encourages further research and development in this field, promoting collaboration and innovation in UAV-based facial verification systems.

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Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific references that are made to the work of others, the contents of this dissertation are original and have not been submitted in whole for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This dissertation is my own work and contains nothing which is the outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and acknowledgements. This dissertation contains more than 10,000 and less than 25,000 words excluding appendices, bibliography, footnotes.

Julio Diez-Tomillo

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Glossary of terms

ACCST Advanced Continuous Channel Shifting Technology.

AFW Annotated Faces in the Wild.

AI Artificial Intelligence.

BBAI-64 BeagleBone AI-64.

BEC Battery Eliminator Circuit.

BGR Blue-Green-Red.

BVLOS Beyond Visual Line of Sight.

CAA Civil Aviation Authority.

CNN Convolutional Neural Network.

CPU Central Processing Unit.

CSP Cross-Stage Partial.

DGA Drone Guard Angel.

DL Deep Learning.

DSP Digital Signal Processor.

EFK Extended Kalman Filter.

ESC Electronic Speed Controllers.

EU European Union.

FC Flight Controller.

Fddb Face Detection Dataset and Benchmark.

FHSS Frequency Hopping Spread Spectrum.

FLOPS Floating Point Operations per second.

FN False Negatives.

FP False Positives.

FPS Frames per second.

FPV First-Person View.

FSPL Free-space path loss.

GCS Ground Control Station.

GDPR General Data Protection Regulation.

GigaMACS Giga Multiply-Accumulations.

GNSS Global Navigation Satellite System.

GPS Global Positioning System.

GPU Graphics processing unit.

IMES Indoor Messaging System.

IMU Inertial Movement Unit.

IoU Intersection over Union.

IPR Intellectual Property Rights.

KNN K Nearest Neighbour.

LBP Local Binary Pattern.

LBP_H LBP Histogram.

LFW Labeled Faces in the Wild.

LIDAR Light Detection and Ranging.

MAFA Masked Face Analysis.

mAP Mean average precision.

MMA Matrix Math Accelerator.

OPS Operations per second.

PAL Phase Alternating Line.

PAN Path Aggregation Network.

PDB Power Distribution Board.

PDD Power Distribution Drone.

PII Personally Identifiable Information.

PWM Power Width Modulation.

QZSS Quasi-Zenith Satellite System.

REST Representational State Transfer.

RGB Red-Green-Blue.

RTH Return to Home.

RTMP Real-Time Messaging Protocol.

RTSP Real Time Streaming Protocol.

SAR Search and Rescue.

SBAS Satellite Based Augmentation System.

SBC Single-board Computer.

SPP Spatial Pyramid Pooling.

SSL Secure Sockets Layer.

TI Texas Instruments.

TN True Negatives.

TP True Positives.

TRL Technology Readiness Level.

TVL Television Lines.

TX Transmitter.

UAS Unmanned Aerial Systems.

UAV Unmanned Aerial Vehicle.

UGV Unmanned Ground Vehicle.

UK United Kingdom.

VLOS Visual Line of Sight.

VTX Video Transmitter.

YTF Youtube Faces.

Part I

Summary

Chapter 1

Introduction

In recent years, Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV), commonly known as drones, have revolutionised various sectors due to their versatility. Applications range from aerial photography and crop monitoring to disaster management. Among these, integrating UAVs into security and surveillance operations has gained significant interest. Their ability to navigate diverse terrains, access remote areas, and offer increasing autonomy provides unique vantage points for security applications.

The need for robust security measures has become increasingly critical in the face of evolving threats and challenges. Traditional surveillance methods, while effective to some extent, often face limitations in coverage, efficiency and adaptability. Integrating face verification technologies with UAVs presents a promising solution to enhance the effectiveness and responsiveness of surveillance systems.

Biometrics serves as a pivotal component in a robust security mechanism, forming part of a multi-factor authentication system along with other factors such as passwords or authenticator apps. However, biometric authentication raises ethical concerns, as it involves storing identifiable personal traits such as faces, fingerprints, or iris scans. Addressing these concerns, the European Union (EU) released the Artificial Intelligence (AI) act on June 2023 [6], aiming to regulate the development and use of AI. The Act categorises AI practices into four different risk levels, each with specific regulations about biometrics:

1. **Unacceptable risk: Prohibited AI practices** - These practices are banned due to their potential threat to people's safety or rights. This category includes:
“‘Real-time’ remote biometric identification systems in publicly accessible spaces for law enforcement purposes, except in a limited number of cases.”[6]
2. **High risk: Regulated high-risk AI systems** - These systems can negatively impact people's safety or fundamental rights. This category includes: “Biometric identification and categorisation of natural persons.” [6]
3. **Limited risk: Transparency obligations** - This category includes: “biometric categorisation systems” [6].
4. **Low or minimal risk: No obligations** - Currently, biometrics are not mentioned in this category.

Furthermore, the EU AI act includes the following paragraph regarding facial recognition:

“Facial recognition: AI powers the use of biometric technologies, including facial recognition technologies (FRTs), which are used by private or public actors for verification, identification and categorisation purposes. In addition to the existing applicable legislation (e.g. data protection and non-discrimination), the draft AI act proposes to introduce new rules for FRTs and differentiate them according to their 'high-risk' or 'low-risk' usage characteristics. The use of real-time facial recognition systems in publicly accessible spaces for the purpose of law enforcement would be prohibited unless Member States choose to authorise them for important public security reasons, and the appropriate judicial or administrative authorisations are granted. A wide range of FRTs used for purposes other than law enforcement (e.g. border control, marketplaces, public transport and even schools) could be permitted, subject to a conformity assessment and compliance with safety requirements before entering the EU market [7].” [6]

First of all, it is essential to distinguish between facial verification and face recognition. While both technologies involve identifying individuals based on their facial features, they serve distinct purposes. Face recognition entails comparing a captured facial image against a

database of known faces to determine the person's identity in the image. Conversely, facial verification focuses on verifying whether a person is who they claim to be by comparing their face against a stored image of that individual's face. Unlike face recognition, which aims to identify a person from a pool of known individuals, facial verification involves a one-to-one comparison to authenticate an individual's identity. In summary, they differ in how the comparison is conducted: one-to-many for face recognition and one-to-one for facial verification. [8]

Figure 1.1 provides a schematic visualisation illustrating the difference between facial verification and face recognition. For facial verification, the system determines whether the faces belong to the compared user (ID-2 in the example) or not. Conversely, the face recognition system identifies the identities of all compared faces stored in the database.

This thesis will solely focus on facial verification mechanisms. While this choice helps address some ethical concerns outlined in the AI Act, such as minimising the risk of profiling or unauthorised mass identification, it does not entirely exempt the system from regulatory scrutiny. Facial verification still involves processing sensitive biometric data, which is subject to stringent requirements under both the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the AI Act. The system's design addresses these requirements by ensuring that verification is performed only on individuals who have explicitly granted permission and by avoiding the storage of comparison images. This reduces the risk of misuse or privacy violations.

Moreover, the compared images are not stored, ensuring compliance with the EU and United Kingdom (UK) GDPR. Furthermore, the face verification system developed in this project is intended for controlled, user-authorized security applications, explicitly excluding law enforcement or surveillance use cases. By adhering to these constraints, the system aligns with the key principles of the GDPR and AI Act. However, it is important to note that regulatory compliance is a complex, context-dependent process, and while this approach mitigates many ethical and legal concerns, it cannot be seen as universally compliant or free from controversy.

It should also be noted that under Article 2(6) of the AI Act, AI systems developed and used exclusively for research purposes are excluded from the regulation. This thesis,

Figure 1.1: Schematic showing the difference between face verification and face recognition.

being a research-focused project, benefits from this exclusion while still aiming to follow the principles and standards set by the regulation.

Facial verification offers an easy-to-use yet robust security mechanism that can complement other methods to create a multi-factor authentication system. This integration aligns with regulatory principles, as previously explained, by ensuring user permission and data protection. However, if the reader wishes to pursue further research based on the work presented in this thesis, consistent and ongoing monitoring of compliance with the applicable regulations at that time will be necessary.

However, face verification introduces another set of challenges for UAV applications. Existing face verification datasets serve as benchmarks for algorithm performance but are predominantly composed of high-resolution images captured at close distances. This makes them inadequate for evaluating face verification algorithms under the conditions typical of UAV footage, such as low resolution, significant variations in pose, and diverse environmental backgrounds. UAV-specific face verification datasets, though valuable, also fall short due to limited diversity in subjects and lack of real-world UAV imagery in some cases.

The literature on face verification algorithms demonstrates high performance on standard benchmarks but fails to address their suitability for UAV use cases. Most existing studies do not evaluate these algorithms on UAV footage, leaving a critical gap in understanding their practical viability for UAV-based face verification.

To bridge these gaps, this thesis focuses on developing and evaluating algorithms tailored for UAV-based face detection and verification. For face detection, a novel approach based on the YOLO architecture is proposed, aiming to achieve both high accuracy and real-time inference. For face verification, the thesis conducts an empirical evaluation of existing algorithms using UAV footage and introduces a dynamic-thresholding technique to enhance their accuracy under UAV-specific conditions.

One potential use case for face verification from UAVs, serving as a crucial component within a multi-factor authentication system, is the Drone Guard Angel (DGA) developed by the EU Horizon2020 project Arcadian-IoT [9]. This system enables UAVs to track and follow individuals in urban areas. For instance, consider someone returning home. Beforehand, they

must register with the DGA service, providing a photo of themselves stored in the biometric system and registering their smartphone. When they want to go back home, they can request a drone guard by authenticating themselves in the dedicated app installed on the smartphone.

Upon receiving the service request and relevant user data, a drone stationed in the vicinity takes off and approaches the individual. The drone initiates validation by communicating with the user's smartphone and performing facial verification. After successful validation, the drone notifies the individual, and the DGA service begins escorting them home. If any abnormal activity is detected, such as rapid movements or approaching vehicles, the drone can take appropriate measures to alert authorities while ensuring the individual's safety.

The collaboration between UAV technology and facial verification significantly enhances security by incorporating a robust verification mechanism. This approach aligns with the AI Act and GDPR, as user permission is required for identification, and the system strictly performs facial verification, not the more intrusive face recognition.

Furthermore, the current UAV market is dominated by established brands like Parrot, Yuneec, or DJI, which utilise proprietary software. This limits the ability to modify or conduct thorough security checks on these systems. Developing an open-source UAV system would address this issue by enabling modifications tailored to specific use cases, resulting in a versatile and cost-effective platform that can accommodate various sensors.

Academic studies highlight the importance of open-source UAV systems in advancing research and practical applications. Autopilot software solutions like PX4 and ArduPilot have been widely adopted for their modularity and robust feature sets, with applications in research ranging from swarm robotics [10] to obstacle detection [11] and underground exploration [12]. However, many existing solutions are either not fully open-source or lack integrated AI capabilities for advanced tasks like real-time data processing and object detection. Without fully open-source accessibility, the UAV platforms limit opportunities for in-depth research, modification, and customisation, limiting their adaptability for diverse and specialised use cases.

Moreover, the limited computational resources of companion computers on many platforms hinder their ability to perform tasks requiring hardware acceleration or GPU support

for efficient AI algorithm execution. Furthermore, some platforms cannot support the payload capacities needed to incorporate diverse sensor types, such as optical, thermal, or multispectral cameras, which are crucial for specialised applications like Search and Rescue (SAR) operations.

Therefore, this project aims to develop a novel open UAV using open-source software and hardware. This approach ensures complete modifiability, allowing for the integration of any sensor or camera available, thus creating a truly sensor-agnostic system.

By merging academic insights with industry needs, this project seeks to address a critical gap in the current UAV platforms. The outcomes are expected to contribute to both academic research and practical applications, ensuring a robust and open UAV solution.

In addition, this open UAV will be equipped with an open-source companion computer capable of executing AI algorithms onboard. This innovative AI-powered open UAV will perform real-time face detection during flight, significantly enhancing the capabilities and performance of any ground-based facial verification pipeline.

In summary, this thesis aims to develop an open-source system capable of performing facial verification from UAVs. This system would be fully compliant with new AI regulations such as the EU AI act and privacy regulations such as EU and UK GDPR. Moreover, as the UAV would be open-source, it would facilitate the attachment of any camera or sensor and UAV facial verification would enable non-intrusive identification from a distance.

This prospective portfolio-based PhD thesis is divided into two parts. The first part explains the argument and storyline of the thesis and extends the results that have already been peer-reviewed, accepted, and published in international journals and conferences. It is organised into nine chapters, including this introductory chapter.

Firstly, Chapter 2 conducts a literature review on the concepts to be developed in the thesis, such as custom UAVs and face verification and detection algorithms. Chapter 3 defines the overall aim of the project and outlines its objectives along with the main innovations. Chapter 4 elaborates on the methodology employed for the completion of the project. Chapter 5 delves into the analysis, design, and implementation of each of the components that form the entire UAV face verification system. Chapter 6 presents and analyses the extended results

obtained from the experiments conducted exclusively for this thesis. Chapter 7 outlines the limitations inherent in the system presented in this thesis. Chapter 8 draws conclusions based on the findings of the project, and Chapter 9 discusses potential avenues for future research and development beyond this research.

The second part of this prospective portfolio-based thesis comprises the five publications that have been peer-reviewed, accepted, and published in international journals and conferences. It includes Appendix A to E, with each appendix representing one of the publications.

Chapter 2

Background and Literature Review

This chapter investigates the state-of-the-art research and technologies relevant to the concepts and developments presented in this thesis. This includes custom and open UAV platforms, face detection algorithms and datasets, as well as face verification algorithms and datasets. This chapter directly contributes to achieving Objective 1.

2.1 Custom UAVs

Table 2.1 offers a comprehensive overview of various open UAV platforms documented in the research literature. Seven different parameters of each platform are analysed: the application or purpose of the UAV platform, the type of camera used (if any), the flight controller, the autopilot system, the companion computer, the weight of the platform, and whether it is completely open-source.

In terms of applications, the platforms are utilised in a wide range of use cases, from swarm robotics, where multiple UAVs collaborate on tasks [10], to obstacle detection for safe navigation [11]. Other notable applications include visual inertial odometry for precise positioning [13], autonomous flight for exploration and data collection [14], underground exploration in challenging environments [12], SAR operations, and even agricultural tasks like crop monitoring [15]. The choice of camera varies depending on the specific needs of the project. While some platforms utilise multiple cameras for comprehensive coverage

[10, 11], others focus on specific types like RGB cameras [12] or grayscale cameras for computationally efficient tasks [16]. Some platforms do not use any camera, relying on other sensors like radar for remote sensing [17].

Table 2.1: Comparison of custom UAVs solutions

Ref	Application	Camera	Flight Controller	Autopilot	Companion Computer	Weight	Open-source
[10]	Swarm robotics	Multiple	Pixhawk4	PX4	UP Core 01/16	2.5kg	Yes
[11]	Obstacle detection	Multiple	Pixhawk4	PX4	Intel NUC i7	3kg	No
[13]	Visual inertial odometry	Not included	NG	NG	Intel NUC i7	2.4kg	No
[14]	Autonomous flight	Tracking	Radix	Betaflight	NVIDIA Jetson TX2	0.75kg	Yes, on request
[12]	Underground exploration	RGB	Pixhawk4	PX4	Intel NUC i7	4.8kg	Software
[16]	Multi-UAV navigation	Grayscale	STM32 H7 MCU	PX4	Nvidia Xavier NX	0.3kg	Yes
[18]	Research	RGB	Pixhawk4	PX4	Odroid U3	1kg	Yes
[19]	SAR operations	FPV	APM 2.8	APM 2.8	None	NG	Yes
[20]	Research	None	Ardupilot Mega 2.5	Ardupilot	None	NG	Yes
[17]	Radar remote sensing	None	ARM Cortex F7	Custom Pixhawk	None	4.5 kg	No
[15]	Agriculture	None	Hobbyking KK2	Hobbyking KK2	None	1kg	No

NG = Not Given

Flight controllers are essential for stable and controlled flight. The Pixhawk4, a popular open-source flight controller, is a common choice in many of these platforms [10–12, 18]. However, some projects chose custom-built controllers based on microcontrollers like STM32 for greater flexibility [16]. Autopilot software, such as PX4 and ArduPilot, are responsible for autonomous flight capabilities. PX4 is a frequent choice due to its modularity and extensive feature set [10–12, 18, 16]. ArduPilot, another popular open-source autopilot, is also utilised in some platforms, particularly those focused on research and development [20].

Companion computers are often used to enhance the computational capabilities of the UAV. They can handle tasks like image processing, machine learning, and data analysis. The choice of companion computer varies significantly, with options ranging from powerful Intel NUCs for demanding applications [11, 13, 12] to more compact and efficient solutions like the NVIDIA Jetson TX2 [14] and Nvidia Xavier NX [16]. The weight of the platforms spans a broad range, reflecting the diverse nature of the applications and the trade-offs between payload capacity and agility. Lighter platforms [16] are designed for agile manoeuvring, while heavier platforms [12] prioritise computational power and sensor capabilities for specific tasks.

The table also highlights the importance of open-source development in this thesis and research community. Many of the platforms utilise open-source software and hardware

components. However, some platforms went for closed-source solutions, potentially due to proprietary technology or commercial interests.

As highlighted, there is a notable gap in the literature regarding open-source UAV platforms with integrated AI capabilities. Many existing platforms listed in the Table 2.1 are either not open-source or lack a companion computer equipped with hardware acceleration or GPU support for efficient execution of AI algorithms. Moreover, some platforms are unable to carry the heavy payloads required to mount diverse camera types, such as optical, thermal, or multispectral cameras. To address these limitations, this thesis introduces a novel UAV platform focused on fully open-source UAV technology, specifically designed for research and applications in object and face detection and verification (Objectives 2 and 7).

This platform uses the Durandal flight controller from Holybro, running ArduPilot as the autopilot system and the BeagleBone AI-64 as the companion computer. Additionally, the UAV weighs around 4 kg, making it relatively heavy but capable of carrying a substantial payload if needed. This capacity allows for the addition of sensors, cameras, gimbals, or even medical supplies for SAR operations. This open UAV platform will be further explained in Chapter 5.

2.2 Face detection

The task of face detection involves detecting the region of an image containing the face through image coordinates [21]. It serves as the initial stage in a face verification pipeline as it locates the face of the person to be verified in the image. This section examines the most commonly used datasets for face detection and reviews the techniques employed in the literature for performing face detection.

2.2.1 Face detection datasets

Table 2.2 offers a comparative analysis of several prominent face detection datasets available in the literature. Various characteristics of each of them are shown, including the number of

images, the number of faces in the dataset, if it is publicly available and the challenges the dataset entails to the face detection algorithms.

Table 2.2: Comparison of face detection datasets

Dataset	Number of Images	Number of Faces	Subjects	Publicly available	Challenges
FDDDB [22]	2,845	5,171	-	Yes	Unconstrained faces, Occlusions
WIDER FACE [23]	32,203	393,703	-	Yes	Large variability, Occlusions, Illumination
AFW [24]	205	473	-	Yes	Large pose variations, Complex backgrounds
CelebA [25]	202,599	202,599	10,177	Yes	Large-scale, Rich annotations
Pascal Face [26]	851	1,341	-	Yes	Large pose variations, different backgrounds and illumination
IJB-C [27]	24,327	49,759	3,531	No	Unconstrained faces, Occlusions, Diverse conditions
MAFA [28]	30,811	35,806	-	Yes	Masked faces
UAV-LAMS [29]	43,531	4001	-	No	Large angles, motion blur
DroneSURF [30]	411,451	786,813	58	Yes, on request	Different poses, varying distance, illumination

CelebA [25] is the dataset with the largest number of images, but all are taken at close distances with only one face per image, posing minimal challenges for face detection algorithms. In contrast, WIDER Face [23] holds the greatest number of faces, totalling nearly 400,000 across approximately 32,000 images, averaging about 12 faces per image. This dataset features faces captured from varying distances, under diverse lighting conditions, and includes occlusions, providing comprehensive challenges for training robust face detection models.

The Annotated Faces in the Wild (AFW) [24] dataset contains very few images, making it unsuitable for training face detection algorithms effectively. Masked Face Analysis (MAFA) [28] dataset focuses exclusively on masked faces, thus it is not suitable for general face detection tasks, though it holds potential for future research and scenarios like the COVID-19 pandemic when face masks were mandatory. IJB-C [27] is a valued dataset with a large collection of faces in diverse conditions, however, it is no longer publicly available since March 2023. Face Detection Dataset and Benchmark (FDDDB) [22] and Pascal Face [26] are publicly accessible datasets with diverse content, yet they contain fewer images and faces compared to other datasets.

Focusing on UAV-obtained face detection datasets, there are only two available in the literature. UAV-LAMS [29] comprises around 43,000 images but only 4,000 faces, featuring images with wide angles and motion blur typical in UAV video footage; however, this dataset is not publicly accessible. On the other side, DroneSURF [30] offers a large number of

images and faces but lacks diversity in subjects' ethnicities and ages, limiting its overall diversity.

As discussed, there is a notable lack of open datasets for face detection that include UAV-acquired images. While many publicly available datasets are large and diverse, they lack images captured from UAVs, which present unique characteristics such as camera movement, large distances, and varied angles. UAV-specific datasets, such as UAV-LAMS and DroneSURF, address some of these gaps but have limitations. DroneSURF, for instance, lacks diversity in age and ethnicity, while UAV-LAMS is not publicly accessible.

Therefore, to address these issues, this thesis utilises two main datasets for face detection algorithms: the comprehensive WIDER Face dataset and a UAV-obtained dataset known as the Arcadian-IoT Faces dataset, which will be further explained in Chapter 5, that contributes to fulfilling Objective 3.

2.2.2 Face detection techniques

The methods commonly used to detect faces from images or videos are divided into two main categories: feature-based and image-based approaches. Feature-based approaches such as Viola-Jones[31] and Gabor features-based methods [32] focus on extracting main facial features that result in sub-optical facial detection [33]. These methods are fast, but fail when the detections are made from different angles and lighting conditions [34]. Image-based approaches including deep convolutional neural networks have inspired face detection in recent years. There are two categories for CNN-based face detectors, region-based (two-stage) and single-stage methods. Fast RCNN [35], Faster RCNN [36], and R-FCN [37] are common region-based methods. They have achieved high accuracy at the cost of speed. The single-stage methods including YOLO series [38–40], and SSD (Single-Shot Detector) [41] have achieved high inference time but lower accuracy compared to two-stage approaches. RetinaFace [42] using Resnet-152 as backbone achieves great accuracy but has a high inference time while processing HD (1920×1080) or 4k (4096×2160) images.

Table 2.3 shows a comparative analysis of different face detection techniques used in the literature. The results shown in the table have been obtained from the papers of each algorithm.

Table 2.3: Comparison of face detection solutions

Ref	Algorithm	Execution Environment	Platform	Accuracy	Speed (FPS)	Model Size	Distance
[43]	Haar cascade	RPi	OpenCV	98.00%	NG	NG	Up to 5 m
[44]	Enhanced YOLOv3	PC	Darknet	51.90%	NG	NG	WF distance
[34]	Customised CNN	PC	Caffe	77.40%*	31.0	NG	WF distance
[45]	LSTM	PC	NG	99.20%	00.7	NG	3 m - 6 m
[46]	SVM	PC	OpenCV	97.50%	13.0	NG	2 m - 10 m
[47]	YOLOv3	RPi	NG	NG	06.7	NG	3.8 m
[48]	Mobilenet-SSD	PC	Tensorflow	91.92%	39.0	NG	NG
[49]	LBPH	RPi	NG	89.10%	NG	NG	NG
[50]	IRNet	PC	PyTorch	76.60%	31.3	1.68MB	WF distance
[51]	Enhanced YOLOX	PC	PyTorch	87.38%	NG	NG	WF distance
[52]	Enhanced RetinaNet	PC	PyTorch	41.00%	11.8	NG	WF distance
[53]	EfficientFace	PC	PyTorch	90.10%	NG	NG	WF distance

NG = Not Given; RPi = Raspberry Pi; WF = WIDER FACE; *=Recall

In one study, [43] proposed a face detection technique implemented on a Raspberry Pi. Haar cascade classifier algorithm was implemented using OpenCV [54]. The Droneface dataset [55] was used as the facial image dataset. Although high accuracy was obtained (98%, 93%, 86% and 80%) for distances of 1.5, 3, 4 and 5 metres respectively, the detections were not tested from an altitude of more than 5m. In addition, the speed of the model has not been reported. In another study, [44] proposed an enhanced YOLOv3 algorithm for face detection being comparable with YOLOv3 and YOLOv4. The mAP of 51.9% was achieved using WIDER FACE dataset [23]. The speed of the model has not also been reported.

In[34], a fast customised CNN was implemented suitable for UAV use cases. In [45] and [46], although high performance has been achieved for face detection and identification, they are not fast enough for our use case and they have been tested up to a distance of 10 m. In [48], a Mobilenet-SSD was implemented in TensorFlow for facial detection. Although very high accuracy was obtained (91.92%), the algorithm was not tested on the drone. In another study [47], YOLOv3 was implemented on Raspberry Pi for facial detection. This study is

slow for our use case (6.7 frames per second) and has been tested at a distance of 3.8m. In [49], Local Binary Pattern Histogram (LBPH) was used as a face recogniser for anti-theft and surveillance applications. Although it has obtained a high accuracy of 89.1%, the speed and the distance have not been reported.

In [50] a high accuracy is achieved in the WIDER FACE dataset but without specifying what input size was used to obtain this accuracy. Moreover, it achieves almost real-time inference speed being close to 30 frames per second (FPS). In [51] and [53] a high accuracy is achieved in the WIDER FACE dataset but the inference time has not been reported. In [52] a modification of RetinaNet to improve accuracy and speed is presented.

As highlighted, there is a gap in the literature regarding face detection algorithms for UAV footage that achieve both high accuracy and low inference time. Algorithms with high accuracy often fail to operate in real-time, rendering them unsuitable for our use case, which requires a fast face verification pipeline. Conversely, algorithms with low inference time typically lack the accuracy needed to detect faces at the long distances characteristic of UAV recordings. Furthermore, some algorithms tested on UAV footage have not been evaluated for long-distance scenarios. These algorithms are generally limited to deployment on small and lightweight UAVs due to safety constraints.

Therefore, to address these limitations, this thesis develops a novel face detection algorithm based on the YOLO architecture. The proposed algorithm achieves both high accuracy and real-time inference, making it suitable for UAV applications and contributing to Objective 6.

2.3 Face verification

As discussed in the previous chapter (Chapter 1), face verification involves determining whether a particular face image belongs to a particular individual [56]. This section elaborates on the most widely used datasets for face verification and reviews the techniques employed in the literature for conducting face verification.

2.3.1 Face verification datasets

Table 2.4 presents a comparative analysis of the most recognised datasets for face verification applications. Each dataset is evaluated based on the number of images, the number of identities it includes, its public availability and the specific challenges it presents to the face verification algorithms.

Table 2.4: Comparison of face verification/recognition datasets

Dataset	Number of Images	Number of Identities	Publicly available	Challenges
Labeled Faces in the Wild (LFW) [57]	13,233	5,749	Yes	Unconstrained faces, Different poses
Youtube Faces (YTF) [58]	3,425 videos	1,595	Yes	Video frames, pose variations, low resolution
VGGFace2 [59]	3.31 million	9,131	Yes	Large variations in pose, age, ethnicity
CASIA-WebFace [60]	494,414	10,575	Yes, on request	Unconstrained faces, occlusions
MS-Celeb-1M [61]	10 million	~100,000	No	Large-scale, variability in images per identity
MegaFace [62]	4.7 million	672,057	No	Scale, large size
IJB-C [27]	31,334	3,531	No	Large variations in pose, age, and occlusion
DroneFace [55]	2057	11	Yes	Varying altitudes, angles
DroneSURF [30]	411,451	58	Yes, on request	Different poses, varying distance, illumination

The most commonly used datasets to test the accuracy of face verification algorithms are the LFW [57] and YTF [58] datasets. These datasets serve as benchmarks for every new face verification algorithm released and published in the literature. However, most images in these datasets are captured at close distances, resulting in relatively high resolution, which is not representative of the low-resolution images typically expected in UAV applications.

In the table, three datasets are not publicly available: IJB-C [27], which was discontinued in March 2023 as explained in the previous section; MegaFace [62], which included more than 4 million images; and MS-Celeb-1M [61]. The MS-Celeb-1M dataset was created by Microsoft but it stopped being publicly available after a Financial Times investigation revealed it was being used to build surveillance systems [63].

The largest publicly available datasets are VGGFace2 [59] and CASIA-WebFace [60], with over 3 million and approximately half a million images respectively. However, only two datasets were recorded using UAVs: DroneFace [55] and DroneSURF [30]. The DroneFace dataset contains around 2,000 images from 11 subjects. These images were not recorded directly from a UAV but with a camera attached to a stick, simulating the images obtained by a drone. This dataset provides a comprehensive set of images varying in distances and heights from the camera to the subject. On the other hand, as explained in the previous section, DroneSURF has a large number of images but includes only 58 subjects. This limited

number of subjects restricts its utility for training face verification algorithms. Additionally, it lacks variety in ages and ethnicities, making it a less diverse dataset.

As discussed in this subsection, there is a notable lack of publicly available datasets tailored to face verification from UAVs. While many existing datasets contain a significant number of images of people, they do not include footage recorded from UAVs, rendering them unsuitable for UAV-based face verification use cases. For example, the DroneFace dataset claims to be UAV-recorded but was not actually captured using UAVs. Similarly, DroneSURF, though recorded with UAVs, lacks diversity in age and ethnicity, resulting in a highly biased dataset.

Therefore, to address this gap, this thesis utilises the Arcadian-IoT Faces dataset, a UAV-captured dataset, to evaluate face verification algorithms. The details of this dataset and its role in achieving Objectives 3 and 4 will be elaborated in Chapter 5.

2.3.2 Face verification techniques

Numerous studies have investigated the use of drones for face verification, often utilising simple yet efficient algorithms like LBPH [64] that are well-suited for the limited computational resources of UAV companion computers.

Previous research has also examined how factors like distance and altitude affect the accuracy of UAV-based face recognition [65]. [46] combined face recognition and distance estimation using UAV-captured data and a Siamese network. Additionally, [66] compared the performance of different architectures, such as ResNet-50 and SENet, for face recognition in UAV applications.

Table 2.5 provides a comprehensive comparison of various face verification algorithms found in the literature. The table presents verification performance metrics and various algorithm parameters, such as input/output size, training image count, and weight file size – a crucial factor for potential embedding in UAV companion computers. Performance is assessed using the previously explained datasets LFW [57] and YTF [58], with 6000 and 5000 face pairs respectively.

Table 2.5: Comparison of state-of-the-art face verification techniques.

Ref	Algorithm	Input Size	Output Size	Verification Accuracy		Weights size	Training Images
				on LFW dataset [57]	on YTF dataset [58]		
[67]	Human-beings	N/A	N/A	97.53%	NG	N/A	N/A
[68]	Deep-Face	152x152x3	4096	97.35%	91.40%	551 MB	4.4M
[69]	OpenFace	96x96x3	128	92.92%	NG	14 MB	0.5M
[70]	VGG-Face	224x224x3	2622	98.95%	97.30%	554 MB	2.6M
[71]	CosFace	112x96x3	NG	99.73%	97.60%	214 MB	5M
[72]	DeepID2	55x47x3	160	99.53%	93.20%	1.6 MB	0.2M
[73]	ArcFace	112x112x3	512	99.83%	98.02%	131 MB	5.8M
[74]	FaceNet	160x160x3	128	98.87%	95.12%	88 MB	200M
[75]	FaceNet512	160x160x3	512	99.60%	NG	91 MB	200M
[76]	Dlib	150x150x3	128	99.38%	NG	22 MB	3M
[77]	SphereFace	112x96x3	512	99.42%	95.00%	69 MB	0.5M
[78]	AdaFace	112x112x3	NG	99.82%	NG	668 MB	15.1M
[79]	DAM-R	112x112x3	NG	99.03%	95.23%	NG	1.5M
[80]	CurricularFace	112x112x3	NG	99.80%	NG	249 MB	6.3M

NG = Not Given; N/A = Not applicable

Human performance on LFW (97.53%) serves as a benchmark [67]. Notably, only DeepFace [68] and OpenFace [69] fall short of this accuracy. The top performers on LFW are ArcFace [73], AdaFace [78], and CurricularFace [80], while ArcFace also leads on YTF (although not all algorithms report YTF results).

DeepFace has the largest feature vector (4096), contrasting with FaceNet [74] and OpenFace’s smaller 128-length vectors. AdaFace, VGG-Face [70], and DeepFace stand out with large model sizes, potentially hindering UAV embedding, whereas DeepID2 [72], OpenFace, and Dlib [76] are more lightweight.

SphereFace [77], despite limited training data, achieves high LFW accuracy (99.42%). While CosFace [71] performs well on both datasets, it lacks sufficient published information for inclusion. The novel DAM-R [79] excels on LFW but underperforms on YTF compared to others.

Finally, FaceNet and its extension FaceNet512 [75] benefit from the largest training datasets (200 million images), followed by AdaFace with 15.1 million. The primary difference between the two FaceNet variants is the output vector size (128 vs. 512), resulting in improved performance for FaceNet512.

All of these algorithms have not been compared and evaluated using UAV footage, so it is unclear if they are suitable for UAV face verification use cases. Therefore, this thesis proposes an empirical comparison of face verification algorithms for UAV use cases and

develops a novel dynamic-thresholding technique to improve their accuracy for these use cases. These contribute to achieving Objectives 4 and 5.

Chapter 3

Aim and Objectives

Since it commenced, the main objectives of this research have been the following:

- **Objective 1:** Conduct an in-depth study and analysis of existing literature and related work focusing on key areas including face detection algorithms, face verification algorithms, biometric pipelines, custom and open-source UAVs, and AI processing in embedded systems. Furthermore, perform an analysis of the compatibility of these technologies with the EU [81] and the UK [82] GDPR and the European AI act [6].
- **Objective 2:** Define, design, implement, and test a novel architecture for a cost-effective open UAV, leveraging an open-source flight controller and autopilot system to enhance accessibility and affordability in UAV technology, targeting the creation of a sensor-agnostic UAV.
- **Objective 3:** Obtain a comprehensive dataset suitable for the training and evaluation of face verification and face detection algorithms in UAV imaging scenarios.
- **Objective 4:** Conduct a rigorous empirical evaluation of various face verification algorithms to determine their efficacy and suitability for deployment in UAV imaging applications. This evaluation will utilise the dataset acquired in Objective 3 to compare algorithm performance and effectiveness.

- **Objective 5:** Design, implement, and empirically evaluate a novel distance-based dynamic thresholding technique for face verification on UAV imaging applications using the dataset obtained in Objective 3. This involves dynamically modifying the threshold used for the different face verification algorithms, compared in Objective 4, depending on the distance from the UAV to the person, notably enhancing their accuracy.
- **Objective 6:** Design, train, implement and empirically evaluate a novel face detection algorithm for UAV imaging applications, optimising the pipeline, enhancing its inference speed and accuracy.
- **Objective 7:** Integration and evaluation of AI face detection algorithms in the open UAV (Objective 2) using an embedded GPU-capable board.

3.1 Innovations

This research project presents five main innovations that contribute significantly to the research community, providing new insights and advancements in the field of UAV-based face detection and verification and open UAV platforms. The five innovations are described as follows:

- **Open UAV platform (Outcome 6, Outcome 9):** The creation of an open UAV platform is a fundamental step in this research. An open UAV refers to a customisable, modifiable drone platform that leverages open-source hardware and software. The development of such a UAV involves selecting appropriate components like the frame, motors, flight controller, and sensors, and integrating them with open-source flight control software, such as ArduPilot. This open UAV serves as the primary platform for conducting various experiments related to face detection and verification. Its modular nature allows for easy upgrades and modifications, creating a sensor and camera-agnostic drone.

- **Face verification algorithms comparison (Outcome 1, Outcome 5):** This study comprehensively compares various state-of-the-art face verification algorithms. By evaluating their performance on the Arcadian-IoT Faces dataset, the strengths and weaknesses of these algorithms are assessed for UAV use cases. This comparative analysis provides valuable guidance for selecting the most suitable algorithm for specific operational requirements and constraints.
- **Dynamic distance-based thresholding (Outcome 4, Outcome 7):** To enhance the accuracy and reliability of face verification in UAV use cases, this research proposes a novel dynamic distance-based thresholding technique. This method adapts the verification threshold based on the estimated distance between the UAV and the subject. By considering the varying image quality and scale associated with different distances, the dynamic thresholding approach improves the overall face verification performance, especially in scenarios where the UAV operates at varying altitudes.
- **UWS-YOLO face detection algorithm (Outcome 3, Outcome 8):** A key innovation in this work is the development of the UWS-YOLO face detection algorithm. This algorithm is specifically designed for UAV video footage. The UWS-YOLO algorithm incorporates optimisations to handle the unique challenges of face detection from UAVs, such as small object sizes and varying scales. Through extensive training and fine-tuning on the Arcadian-IoT Faces dataset, the UWS-YOLO algorithm demonstrates superior performance compared to existing face detection methods in UAV scenarios.
- **Comparison of face detection algorithms in a high-spec computer and the companion computer (Outcome 2):** This research compares the performance of various face detection algorithms on both a high-specification computer and the companion computer onboard the UAV. This comparison reveals the trade-offs between computational resources and detection accuracy, providing valuable insights for deploying face detection algorithms in real-world UAV applications. By evaluating the feasibility of running computationally demanding algorithms on resource-constrained platforms, this

study contributes to the development of efficient and effective face-detection solutions for UAVs.

Chapter 4

Methodology

The methodology employed in this thesis is shown in two tables. First, the objectives (Chapter 3) are mapped with the outcomes. Second, each objective is linked to a specific time in the last three years. Table 4.1 provides a visual schema that associates objectives with outcomes. Different objectives may have a relation with several outcomes and the opposite, various outcomes associated with the same objective. When a relation exists, the correlation between objective and outcome is coloured in green.

Table 4.1: Mapping Objectives-Outcomes

	Outcome 1	Outcome 2	Outcome 3	Outcome 4	Outcome 5	Outcome 6	Outcome 7	Outcome 8	Outcome 9
Objective 1	Green								
Objective 2		Green				Green			Green
Objective 3	Green		Green	Green	Green				
Objective 4	Green		Green	Green	Green		Green		
Objective 5				Green			Green		
Objective 6					Green			Green	
Objective 7		Green				Green	Green	Green	Green

Figure 4.1 illustrates the research methodology and key contributions of this PhD project. It outlines the sequential steps undertaken, from the initial literature review to the final comparison of face detection algorithms on different computing platforms. Each stage

is linked to specific objectives (Ob), explained in Chapter 3, and corresponding research outcomes. The star symbol highlights the significant and novel innovations resulting from this research, as explained in Chapter 3.

Figure 4.1: Schematic figure with tasks performed in this research project and its corresponding objectives and innovations.

The figure also includes references to relevant sections within the thesis, directing the reader to more detailed explanations of the methodologies and extended results for each step. Overall, this diagram serves as a roadmap for this research project, highlighting its innovative contributions to the field of Open UAV platforms and UAV-based face detection and verification.

To illustrate a deeper understanding of the methodology of this research work and its achievements, Table 4.2 enumerates each objective over the last three years. Each coloured cell corresponds to a quartile where an objective has been addressed. Some objectives should be accomplished before starting the following one, nevertheless, other situations require an overlapping of objectives where the results of one objective feed the other and vice versa. Each coloured square is indexed by at least one enumerated step, as defined further in this chapter.

Table 4.2: Objectives Gantt timetable

	Q2 2021	Q3 2021	Q4 2021	Q1 2022	Q2 2022	Q3 2022	Q4 2022	Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023	Q4 2023	Q1 2024
Objective 1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Objective 2		2	2	2	2	2	2, 3	2, 3	3	3	3	
Objective 3		4	4	4								
Objective 4					5	5	5	5				
Objective 5							6	6	6			
Objective 6								7	7	7	7	
Objective 7											8, 9	8, 9

The numbers in the table refer to the description of steps described as follows:

1. The first step involves conducting an extensive literature review on topics relevant to this research project. This includes studying existing works on self-designed UAVs, with a particular focus on those utilising open-source software. Additionally, the literature review covers face verification and face detection algorithms, as well as UAV-recorded datasets for face verification, and potential examples of pipelines.
2. The next step entails the design of the architecture for the open UAV. Subsequently, the platform was built and configured meticulously, following the guidelines of the autopilot documentation.
3. To ensure the successful performance and validate the operational capabilities of the open UAV, comprehensive testing flights were conducted.
4. A crucial element of the project involved the acquisition of a dataset specifically designed for UAV-based face detection and verification. This dataset, referred to as the "Arcadian-IoT Faces dataset", captured the faces of volunteers at various distances for the Arcadian-IoT European project. The captured data would then be used to evaluate the face detection and verification algorithms.
5. Six carefully chosen face verification algorithms were subjected to an empirical comparison. This evaluation aimed to assess their suitability and effectiveness for UAV-based face verification tasks.

6. To enhance the accuracy of face verification from UAVs, a novel approach involving distance-based dynamic thresholding was developed. This technique dynamically adjusts the verification threshold based on the distance between the UAV and the subject.
7. A key objective of the project was the creation of a novel face detection algorithm. This algorithm referred to as "UWS-YOLO", prioritises both speed and accuracy at far distances, making it well-suited for UAV applications.
8. Once developed, the newly created face detection algorithm was compared with other face detection algorithms integrated into the UAV's companion computer. This integration enables real-time face detection onboard the UAV platform.
9. The final stage involved the critical task of validating the entire system. This validation process employed drone-captured images to comprehensively evaluate the performance and effectiveness of the integrated face detection and verification system.

Figure 4.2: Schematic figure mapping the objectives with the outcomes of the thesis showing the overall aim of the project.

Finally, Figure 4.2 provides a visual representation of the project's overall aim. This figure visually illustrates how the project's objectives - explained in Chapter 3 - map to the outcomes, from the initial literature review (Objective 1), ultimately leading to the successful integration of AI face detection models within the open UAV platform (Objective 7).

Chapter 5

Analysis, design and implementation

This chapter focuses on the analysis, design, and implementation of the work. Each section addresses a different contribution and covers various aspects of the final solution. These sections explain the content of the publications that form this thesis and also expand upon the information presented in those publications. The first section describes the open UAV, including its architecture, configuration, and implementation. Section 5.2 details the datasets used in the experiments, including the obtained Arcadian-IoT Faces dataset. Section 5.3 explains the designed dynamic distance-based thresholding technique used to increase the accuracy of face verification algorithms at long distances. Section 5.4 describes the UWS-YOLO face detection algorithm that achieves high inference speed without sacrificing accuracy. Finally, Section 5.5 explains the integration of AI algorithms into the open UAV using the BBAI-64 board.

5.1 Open UAV

The initial phase of this research project involved the design, implementation, and testing of a novel open UAV. This UAV utilises open-source hardware and software, making it a sensor-agnostic platform. This versatility allows the attachment of any camera or sensor, promoting cost-effectiveness. This section is divided into six subsections. The first subsection analyses the designed UAV architecture and its components. Following this, the configuration of the

architecture is explained. The third subsection details the UAV's fail-safe mechanisms, which are critical for safe operation. Next, the BeagleBone AI-64, chosen as the UAV's companion computer, is analysed. The UAV's implementation is then briefly explained, followed by a discussion of Guardian, the ground control station used for connecting and monitoring the UAVs.

The open UAV was briefly explained and reported in a peer-reviewed conference paper (**Outcome 2**) which can be found in Appendix B [2]. Due to a limitation on the number of pages, the architecture was not fully explained in that publication. In this chapter, the architecture and every aspect of the open UAV are explained and developed (**Outcome 6**).

5.1.1 Architecture

The frame utilised in the UAV is the Tarot X6 [83], which is a hexacopter configuration. The Tarot X6 was selected for its robust and versatile design, making it well-suited for various UAV use cases. Its hexacopter configuration provides enhanced stability and payload capacity compared to quadcopters, which is critical for carrying additional equipment such as sensors, cameras or other equipment, like a companion computer. Its modular design allows for easy maintenance and upgrades, further supporting the long-term adaptability of the UAV platform. Additionally, the high availability of spare parts makes it easy to repair in case of any accident or crash. Constructed entirely from carbon fibre, the frame weighs only 2kg. Based on this frame, an architecture for the UAV has been established. Figure 5.1 illustrates the complete schematic of the open UAV architecture. Each component and system is explained in detail below.

1. **UAV Control:** It is the central processing unit of the UAV. It receives data from various sensors and user input through different interfaces, processes this information, and controls the UAV's motors and other actuators accordingly. Additionally, it transmits telemetry data about the UAV's state to the Ground Control Station (GCS). It is composed of four components:

Figure 5.1: Schematic of the architecture of the designed open UAV platform. It is divided into two main parts: the components inside the UAV and the external connections on the ground

- Flight Controller (FC) [84]: The flight controller employed is the Durandal, manufactured by Holybro. Featuring a 32-bit STM32H743 processor with 1MB of RAM and 2MB of flash memory, this controller serves as a robust computational hub for UAV operations. Equipped with an array of sensors including accelerometers, gyroscopes, barometers, and magnetometers, the Durandal ensures precise navigation and stability during flight. Its design includes multiple interfaces that facilitate integration with various sensors and UAV components, enabling efficient communication and coordination within the system. It was chosen because it surpasses the specifications required for this research project compared with other flight controllers on the market. Compared to the Pixhawk 4 [85], it offers superior processing capabilities. Moreover, while the Cube Orange

[86] provides exceptional reliability with its triple-redundant Inertial Movement Unit (IMU), Durandal's advanced processor and sensors make it a robust choice for most UAV applications. Unlike the DJI N3 [87], Durandal's open-source nature and compatibility with various components offer greater flexibility and adaptability.

- **Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) module:** The one used is the M8N from Holybro [88]. It supports four GNSS constellations: GPS [89], Galileo [90], BeiDou [91], and GLONASS [92], and three GNSS augmentation systems: Satellite Based Augmentation System (SBAS) [93], Indoor Messaging System (IMES) [94] and Quasi-Zenith Satellite System (QZSS) [95]. It can utilise up to two constellations simultaneously, enhancing positioning accuracy, especially in areas with limited satellite visibility. Additionally, the flight controller offers the capability of adding a second GNSS receiver for further redundancy.
- **Telemetry transmission [96]:** This system enables bidirectional communication between the UAV to the GCS, facilitating the exchange of telemetry data, waypoints and configuration updates. It utilises two identical SiK Telemetry radios from Holybro, operating at 433MHz with a transmit power of 100 mW. These radios use the open-source SiK firmware [97]. One radio is connected to the UAV and the other to the device running the GCS.
- **X8R receiver [98]:** The receiver is from the FrSky brand and operates at 2.4GHz using D16 mode, which provides 16 channels for separate control functions. It receives the pilot's control commands from the joystick and transmits crucial telemetry and UAV information to the pilot during the flight, supporting basic short-range operations.

2. **Power:** The power subsystem is crucial for the effective operation of the UAV, ensuring consistent power delivery to all components, thus preventing power shortages or surges. It is composed of the following components:

- **Power Distribution Board (PDB) [99]:** The PDB utilised in this system is the PM07 manufactured by Holybro. This board accepts batteries up to 14S LiPo configuration with a continuous current rating of 90A and a burst capability of 140A. It connects directly to the battery and provides a regulated 5V output to the FC. Moreover, the PM07 features several connectors for external components requiring the same voltage as the battery. Notably, it measures the total current drawn from the UAV, allowing the estimation of the remaining battery capacity.
 - **Power Distribution Drone (PDD):** The Tarot X6 frame, utilised in this UAV [83], integrates a power distribution board to supply power to the motors and Electronic Speed Controllers (ESC). Connected with the PM07 PDB, this board ensures the power distribution throughout the system. Additionally, it includes three XT-60 connectors for connecting other essential components such as the landing gear controller.
 - **Battery [100]:** The UAV utilises a 13Ah, 6S LiPo battery with a 20C discharge rate (capable of delivering up to 160A) from Lumenier. The system allows for two such batteries to be connected simultaneously for extended flight times. Each battery weighs approximately 1,410 grams. The 20C discharge rate allows the battery to deliver high current output when needed, ensuring that the UAV can handle power-intensive tasks and sudden surges in demand, such as during takeoff or when carrying heavy payloads. The 6S configuration ensures a higher voltage supply, which contributes to greater power efficiency and improved performance of the onboard systems. Additionally, this battery was selected due to its optimal balance between weight and capacity. A battery with a higher capacity would have a higher weight, leading to reduced flight time despite the increased capacity.
3. **Landing gear:** The UAV is equipped with retractable landing gear, offering dynamic adaptability throughout flight operations. After take-off, the landing gear can be retracted to enhance aerodynamic efficiency, minimise antenna interference, and optimise camera visibility. Before landing, the landing gear can be deployed to ensure a

safe touchdown. The control mechanism for the landing gear is facilitated through a dedicated button on the pilot's joystick.

- **Controller [101]:** It is connected to the X8R radio receiver to receive the command from the pilot to retract or deploy. It instructs the servos to retract or deploy the landing gear legs by providing the necessary power.
- **Servos [102]:** They are responsible for moving the landing gear legs based on the power received by the landing gear controller.

4. **Motors:** The propulsion system plays a critical role in enabling the UAV's flight capability. It comprises two key components:

- **ESC [103]:** The UAV utilises one ESC Hobbywing 40A ESC per motor. It receives a Power Width Modulation (PWM) signal from the FC and interprets it into precise adjustments of power delivery to the motor, controlling its speed. This ESC was chosen based on the maximum current that the motors are expected to draw. It's crucial for the ESC's current rating to exceed the maximum current requirement of the motors to ensure reliable operation and prevent overheating or failure. Hobbywing was selected due to its reputation as a reliable brand widely trusted within the UAV community and the availability of spare parts, which ensures ease of maintenance and quick repairs if needed.
- **Motor [104]:** As a hexacopter, the UAV employs six brushless DC motors. The chosen model is the U7 KV420 from T-Motor. Each motor weighs 300g. Each motor weighs approximately 300 grams and is coupled with an 18x5.5-inch propeller (diameter x pitch). The motors were chosen because they have sufficient power to lift the UAV, including additional payload, without drawing too much current. This selection strikes a balance between power output and energy consumption, ensuring efficient operation of the UAV during flight.

5. **First-Person View (FPV) Transmitter (TX):** The FPV system plays a vital role in allowing the pilot to control the UAV effectively. It transmits a real-time video feed

from the onboard camera to the pilot's display, providing a first-person perspective for navigation and obstacle avoidance.

- **Battery Eliminator Circuit (BEC):** This voltage regulator steps down the high voltage from the battery (6S LiPo, around 22.2V) to the lower voltage required by the Video Transmitter (VTX) (12V).
 - **FPV camera:** The UAV utilises an FPV camera with a 4:3 aspect ratio and a resolution of 1200 Television Lines (TVL). TVL is the unit used to quantify analogue video resolution, representing the number of vertical lines visible in each frame. Higher TVL values indicate better image detail.
 - **VTX TX801 [105]:** This transmitter operates in the 5.8 GHz frequency band using the PAL colour encoding and offers nine selectable channels within each band (A, B, E, F, R, U, O, L, H), resulting in a total of 72 transmission channels. It also provides adjustable power levels, ranging from a low-power setting of 0.01mW to a high-power option of 600mW, allowing for adaptation to different flight environments and regulations. The FPV camera and the VTX TX801 were chosen primarily for their balance between affordability and quality. They provide high-quality video transmission for piloting the UAV at a relatively low cost compared to other alternatives.
6. **Video TX AI processing:** This subsystem is responsible for acquiring, processing, and transmitting video feed captured by the UAV's primary camera along with the processing results to the Ground Control Station (GCS). It consists of three components:
- **Camera:** The current configuration utilises an HD USB camera from Logitech. This camera provides high-definition video but lacks a motorised gimbal for stabilisation. However, the system can be adapted to integrate one if needed. Additionally, alternative cameras from various brands, including DJI, are compatible with the system for potential upgrades.

- BeagleBone AI-64 (BBAI-64) [106]: The chosen platform for onboard AI processing is the BeagleBone AI-64 board. A detailed explanation of this board and its functionalities is provided in Section 5.1.4.
 - BEC: As the BBAI-64 board operates on 5V voltage, a BEC is necessary to step down the higher voltage from the 6S battery (around 22.2V) to the required level. A BEC with a minimum output current rating of 5A was selected to ensure stable power delivery to accommodate the board's potential current spikes reaching 4A.
7. **Joystick:** The model utilised is the Taranis X9D [107]. It is powered by a 2S battery (7.4V) and operates on the 2.4GHz frequency using the Advanced Continuous Channel Shifting Technology (ACCST) private protocol, offering 16 available channels. The Taranis X9D is a highly customisable transmitter, featuring 32 programmable logic switches. These switches can be assigned different functions specific to the UAV, such as deploying or retracting the landing gear, changing flight modes, or arming/disarming the motors.

5.1.2 Configuration

After building the UAV according to the previously defined architecture, it must undergo proper configuration. The autopilot chosen for the FC is ArduPilot [108]. This open-source software is widely used for multicopter UAVs and offers a comprehensive set of configurable parameters for optimal UAV setup. ArduPilot supports various flight modes, including loiter, position hold, and stabilise. It also enables autonomous missions based on pre-defined GPS waypoints and incorporates failsafe mechanisms to counter potential failures. ArduPilot was chosen over other autopilots, such as PX4 [109], due to several key advantages. It is compatible with a wider range of platforms and it benefits from extensive documentation and a large, active community that provides valuable support and resources, making it easier to learn, troubleshoot, and customise the software [110].

Configuration of the UAV was conducted following the guidelines provided by ArduPilot. Since our UAV is a hexacopter with an "X" configuration, motor rotation direction was set

Figure 5.2: Rotation direction for each motor and propeller of the hexacopter UAV.

as shown in Figure 5.2, alternating between clockwise and counter-clockwise. Propellers were then attached to the motors based on their designated rotation. Subsequently, several parameters had to be adjusted based on our specific architecture, including frame type, propeller size, and battery type. A list of the most significant modified parameters can be found in Table 5.1. These parameters are exclusively for this UAV architecture and components. If any modification is done to the UAV, a new calibration will be needed to update the corresponding parameters in order to have a stable flight.

If a drone is built following this architecture and incorporating the specified parameters, it will be fully functional. The UAV is entirely open-source, allowing it to be built and operated based on the guidelines provided in this document. This thesis provides comprehensive documentation and instructions, enabling others to replicate and build upon this design.

Following these parameter modifications, the UAV was prepared for flight testing. During these initial tests, additional parameters were fine-tuned to enhance flight stability and facilitate smoother flight manoeuvres, minimising abrupt movements.

Table 5.1: Most important UAV parameters modified for its calibration.

Parameter	Description	Value	Range
FRAME_TYPE	Controls motor mixing for multicopters	1 (X)	N/a
FRAME_CLASS	Controls frame class for multicopter	2 (Hexa)	N/a
FENCE_ENABLE	Enables the virtual Geofence	1	N/a
MOT_THST_EXPO	Motor thrust curve exponent	0.7	-1 to 1
MOT_SPIN_MAX	Point at which the thrust saturates	0.95	0 to 1
MOT_SPIN_MIN	Point at which the thrust starts	0.09	0 to 1
MOT_THST_HOVER	Motor thrust needed to hover	0.5012	0.2 to 0.8
INS_ACCEL_FILTER	Filter cutoff frequency for accelerometers	20 Hz	0 to 256
INS_GYRO_FILTER	Filter cutoff frequency for gyroscopes	26 Hz	0 to 256
ATC_ACCEL_P_MAX	Maximum acceleration in pitch axis	60300	0 to 180000
ATC_ACCEL_R_MAX	Maximum acceleration in roll axis	60300	0 to 180000
ATC_ACCEL_Y_MAX	Maximum acceleration in yaw axis	19800	0 to 72000
ATC_RAT_PIT_FLTD	Pitch axis rate controller derivative frequency	13 Hz	0 to 50
ATC_RAT_PIT_FLTT	Pitch axis rate controller target frequency	13 Hz	5 to 50
ATC_RAT_RLL_FLTD	Roll axis rate controller derivative frequency	13 Hz	5 to 100
ATC_RAT_RLL_FLTT	Roll axis rate controller target frequency	13 Hz	5 to 100
ATC_RAT_YAW_FLTE	Yaw axis rate controller error frequency	2 Hz	0 to 20
ATC_RAT_YAW_FLTT	Yaw axis rate controller target frequency	13 Hz	1 to 50
PSC_ACCZ_I	Acceleration (vertical) controller I gain	0.374	0 to 3
PSC_ACCZ_P	Acceleration (vertical) controller P gain	0.2	0.2 to 1.5
ATC_INPUT_TC	Attitude control input time constant	0.2	0 to 1
GPS_GNSS_MODE	What GNSS system to use on the GPS	5	N/a

N/a = Not applicable

5.1.3 Failsafes

The UAV incorporates various failsafe mechanisms designed to handle potential in-flight failures or attacks and ensure safe operation. These systems automatically trigger pre-defined countermeasures upon encountering specific issues. The most important failsafes are outlined as follows:

- **Radio Failsafe:** This failsafe is activated when the connection between the joystick and the radio receiver or the telemetry radios is lost. In such an event, the UAV enters a Return to Home (RTH) mode, autonomously navigating back to its takeoff location at a predefined altitude and speed. If the connection is re-established during the RTH process, the pilot will regain control over the UAV.

- **Geofence:** A virtual geofence can be established around the takeoff point. This geofence defines a circular area limiting the UAV's travel distance and maximum altitude. If the UAV reaches the geofence perimeter, it automatically stops, preventing it from straying outside the defined boundaries. This failsafe proves valuable in scenarios where the UAV experiences unexpected drift due to failures or jamming.
- **Battery Failsafe:** The pilot receives real-time battery level information throughout the flight. However, a low battery failsafe is implemented as a safety precaution. When a pre-defined battery percentage threshold is reached, the failsafe is triggered, and the UAV enters the RTH mode. A critical battery threshold is also defined for scenarios where a safe return to the takeoff point is not feasible due to distance limitations. If the critical threshold is reached, an immediate automated landing at the UAV's current position is triggered.
- **Extended Kalman Filter (EFK) failsafe:** The EFK is the system responsible for estimating the position and attitude of the UAV. The EFK failsafe monitors the system's health to detect any errors in the estimation of the vehicle's position, such as GPS glitches or compass errors, thereby preventing potential flyaways. Upon triggering, notifications will appear on both the GCS and the pilot's joystick. Moreover, the UAV will enter a controlled landing mode, granting the pilot control over the roll and pitch angles while descending at the land speed defined on the UAV configuration before the flight.

5.1.4 AI enabler companion board

Table 5.2 provides a detailed comparison of five popular Single-board Computer (SBC) that are candidates to be the companion computers in the open UAV platform. "These five boards share the fact that they are commonly used for AI applications. Each specification highlights key components and features critical for AI performance, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation of each board's capabilities. After careful consideration of these specifications, the BeagleBone AI-64 was selected as the optimal choice for this project.

Table 5.2: Comparison of AI single-board computer to use as a companion computer.

Specification	Jetson Nano	Jetson AGX Xavier	BeagleBone AI-64	Coral Dev Board	Raspberry Pi 5
RAM	4 GB	16 GB	4 GB	4 GB	8 GB
CPU	Quad-core ARM A57	64-bit octa-core ARM V8.2	Dual 64-bit Arm Cortex-A72	Quad Cortex-A53, Cortex-M4F	Quad Arm Cortex-A76
GPU	128-core NVIDIA Maxwell	512-core Volta GPU with Tensor Cores	3D GPU PowerVR Rogue 8XE GE8430	Integrated GC7000 Lite Graphics Google Edge TPU coprocessor	Broadcom VideoCore VII
Clock Speed	1.43 GHz	2.265 GHz	2.0 GHz	1.5 GHz	2.4 GHz
GPIO	40	40	2x46	40	40
WiFi	No	No	Yes (M.2 E-key)	Yes	Yes
Bluetooth	No	No	No	4	5
Ethernet	Gigabit	Gigabit	Gigabit	Gigabit	Gigabit
Power	5V (2A - 10W)	9-20V (10/15/30W)	5V (3A - 15W)	5V (2-3A - 15W)	5V (5A - 25W)
Weight	77 g	274 g	192 g	25.5 g	50 g
Other	-	7-way VLIW Vision Processor 2 NVDLA Engines	C7x floating point Deep-learning MMA Two C66x floating point DSP	Supports TensorFlow Lite	-
Open-source	No	No	Yes	No	No
Price	£107.00	£1,992.00	£167.00	£168.00	£76.80

Regarding the GPU capabilities, the Jetson AGX Xavier, with its 512-core Volta GPU and Tensor Cores, is exceptionally powerful for AI inference and training tasks. However, it is overpowered and too costly for the project's needs. While the BeagleBone AI-64 is not as specialised as the Coral Dev Board's Edge TPU coprocessor or as powerful as the Jetson AGX Xavier, it provides a balanced performance suitable for the intended applications.

The BeagleBone AI-64's dual ARM Cortex-A72 processors, coupled with the dedicated C7x DSP and deep learning MMA accelerator, provide ample processing power for real-time face detection tasks. The onboard 3D GPU also enables potential expansion into other computer vision applications in the future. Furthermore, the BeagleBone AI-64's 4 GB of RAM and 16 GB eMMC storage are sufficient for the research project's needs. Additionally, it is the only board among those compared that is open-source, making it the most appropriate for this open UAV platform.

To sum up, the BeagleBone AI-64 was selected as the companion computer for the open UAV due to its high computing power with low power consumption—a critical factor for UAVs—and its open-source characteristic. Table 5.3 summarises the board's key components. Notably, the Texas Instruments (TI) TDA4VM processor [111] integrates two C66x Digital Signal Processor (DSP) capable of up to 40 Giga Floating Point Operations per second (FLOPS), a C71x vector DSP reaching 80 Giga FLOPS, and a dedicated Deep Learning Matrix Math Accelerator (MMA) offering up to 8 Tera Operations per second (OPS).

The BeagleBone AI-64 serves several critical functions. First, it acquires the video feed from the onboard camera. This video is then processed using a chosen AI algorithm, which

Table 5.3: Main BeagleBone AI-64 features

Processor	TI TDA4VM
Arm CPU	2 Cortex-A72
RAM	4GB
Graphics Engine	PowerVR® Series8XE GE8430
Connectivity	WiFi (M.2 E-key) 4G/5G (USB Modem)
Power source	5V @ >3A
Weight	192g

Figure 5.3: Picture of the BeagleBone AI-64 board used as companion computer of the open UAV.

can perform various tasks like object detection, face detection, or semantic segmentation. The AI results are then transmitted to the GCS along with the video feed. Furthermore, the board serves as a MAVLink router [112, 113], forwarding messages such as telemetry from the FC to the GCS.

5.1.5 Contributions

It is also important to highlight which aspects of the Open UAV are off-the-shelf components and which represent innovations. Each component of the Open UAV — such as the companion computer, flight controller, and others — consists of commercially available

off-the-shelf products. The primary innovation lies in how these components are interconnected, forming the overall UAV architecture. This architecture enables the creation of a low-cost, sensor-agnostic platform specifically designed for UAV research, distinguishing it from commercially manufactured drones. Additionally, certain component housings were custom-designed and 3D-printed specifically for this UAV. Another significant contribution is the assembly and integration of the entire architecture into a fully functional UAV, along with its successful testing in field conditions.

Regarding the software, the ArduPilot framework is an open-source product that is readily available online. The primary software contribution of this research is the fine-tuning of parameters, as detailed in Section 5.1.2. These parameter modifications enable ArduPilot to ensure stable flight performance while accommodating the addition of various payloads as needed.

5.1.6 Implementation

After designing the whole open UAV, configuring it and adding any failsafe, the UAV has to be implemented and tested. Many flights were required to calibrate the drone correctly. The result of the implementation can be seen in Figure 5.4, Figure 5.5 and Figure 5.6. The first one shows the whole UAV deployed indoors with the canopy attached while performing some calibrations. The second one shows a close image of the main components of the UAV where it can be seen the BBAI-64, the GNSS receiver or the FC. Lastly, the third one shows the open UAV flying in an open field while performing a test flight outdoors. To sum up, Table 5.4 shows the specifications and main features of the designed and implemented open-UAV.

In this study, all UAV operations were conducted in compliance with the regulations established by the UK Civil Aviation Authority (CAA). The drones were operated under the Open category (A1 and A3) and adhered at all times to standard guidelines, including maintaining Visual Line of Sight (VLOS) and avoiding flights over uninvolved people or congested areas. Pilots were required to hold appropriate certifications and were registered as operators with a specific Operator ID or Flyer ID to ensure safe and compliant operations.

Figure 5.4: Picture of the open UAV deployed indoors.

Additionally, each drone was registered with the CAA and equipped with its Operator ID, as mandated by UK legislation.

Flight Controller	Holybro Durandal
AutoPilot	ArduPilot
Battery	6S 13Ah
Battery weight	1410g
Total weight	6.5kg
Propeller size	18x5.5 inches
Drone diameter	1112mm
Main frame diameter	328mm
Arms length	392mm
Motor to motor spacing	960mm
Average current consumption	47A
Companion board	BeagleBone AI-64

Table 5.4: Specifications of the open UAV.

5.1.7 Guardian Ground control station

An open-source GCS called QGroundControl [114] has been modified for this project. This software allows easy connection to UAVs using the popular ArduPilot [108] or PX4 [109] autopilots, which communicate via MAVLink messages [115]. For UAVs that use other

Figure 5.5: Close picture of the main components in the open UAV.

autopilots, like DJI models, MAVLink wrappers such as RosettaDrone [116] can be used to enable connection.

QGroundControl was selected as the GCS for this project over alternatives like Mission-Planner [117], MAVProxy [113] or APM Planner [118] due to its cross-platform compatibility and comprehensive feature set. QGroundControl is compatible with Windows, OS X, Linux, iOS, and Android. Furthermore, like the other GCS options, it is fully open-source (GPLv3), aligning with the project's commitment to open-source development. Lastly, it is a very comprehensive platform that allows you to configure each of the drones connected to the platform, calibrate them, and it offers versatile features for the commander.

Guardian, the modified version of QGroundControl, provides full configuration of UAVs, mission planning for autonomous flights, and displays all UAV telemetry, including its position on a map. Moreover, video streaming from the UAV can be visualised within the software.

Figure 5.6: Picture of the UAV on a test flight outdoors.

Guardian expands functionality to receive detection messages from various unmanned vehicles, including both UAV and Unmanned Ground Vehicle (UGV). These detected locations are displayed on a map for the mission commander, who can then choose to send a vehicle autonomously to that location by creating a mission. Detection messages from UxVs are routed to all connected GCS clients through a dedicated detection server.

Figure 5.7 illustrates a modification implemented within QGroundControl to accommodate the requirements of Guardian. This includes a configurable section within the software enabling users to specify the connection details for the detection server, including its port and IP address.

Figure 5.7: Configuration of the Guardian GCS to connect to the detection server that routes the detection messages.

Figure 5.8 shows the Guardian GCS interface on the left. The map displays the location of the computer running the Guardian software and a person detection. On the right, the

detection server logs show a connected Guardian GCS and UAV. A message with a person detection is received from the UAV and routed to the Guardian for visualisation by the mission commander.

Figure 5.8: Figure displaying the Guardian GCS interface on the left, indicating the location of the PC running the software and a single detection. On the right, logs from the detection server are visible, illustrating the connection of a UAV, a GCS, and the transmission of a person detection message.

5.2 Datasets

Two datasets have been used for this research. The first one is a novel dataset recorded from a UAV called the Arcadian-IoT Faces dataset. The second one is a public dataset for face detection algorithms named WIDER Face. Both datasets are explained in the next subsections.

5.2.1 Arcadian-IoT Faces dataset

A dataset from the Arcadian-IoT project was used for this research. It is composed of human faces recorded from a UAV at different distances. Our research required a dataset with particular characteristics, but no suitable public dataset existed. Therefore, the one obtained for the Arcadian-IoT project was used.

Figure 5.9: Dataset recording distances with the vertical and horizontal distances from the UAV to the face of the volunteer.

This dataset is composed of videos recorded from a DJI Mini 2 UAV at different distances. This drone has a video resolution of 4K (3840x2160 pixels) with a frame rate of 30 fps. The DJI Mini 2 camera does not have autofocus, and the focus is fixed from 1 metre to infinity. Moreover, the videos are stored in the MicroSD inside the drone in MP4 format. 20 people were recorded for the dataset in an open field with no other subject in the videos, thus there is only one face per video, making it easier to label. Each recorded video last 30 seconds, during which the volunteers were asked to execute different head movements to obtain the face from different angles, and then they were asked to stare at the camera for a few seconds. Eight videos were recorded per volunteer at different distances: 2, 5, 7, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 metres. In order to create the dataset, only one image per half-second was captured from the videos, having a total of 60 images per person per each of the distances recorded.

Figure 5.9 shows the distances arranged for the recordings. The distances are measured from the face of the subject to the UAV camera and in all cases the UAV has 30 degrees of elevation above the face of the person. The dataset has been divided arbitrarily into two subsets of the same size. One is going to be used for the calculation of the proposed

Figure 5.10: Cropped face image examples from the Arcadian-IoT Faces dataset at the 8 recorded distances.

thresholds in Section 4 and the other for the comparison between the accuracy using the proposed and the original thresholds in Section 6.

Furthermore, Figure 5.10 shows the cropped faces from the eight different distances of the dataset. In Figure 5.10a all features of the face can be seen without any problem. The person can easily be verified. On the other hand, in Figure 5.10h it is challenging to verify the person in the image due to the low resolution and its small size.

Figure 5.11 shows example images of our dataset at each of the recorded distances: 2, 5, 7, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 metres.

More information about this dataset can be obtained from the Public Deliverables of the Arcadian-IoT project, such as D4.2 (ARCADIAN-IoT Vertical Planes – 2nd version) and D4.3 (ARCADIAN-IoT Vertical Planes – Final version), and also in Appendix G.

Figure 5.11: Example images of the Arcadian-IoT Faces dataset at the 8 recorded distances.

Finally, table 5.5 shows a summary of the specifications of the Arcadian-IoT Faces dataset. Moreover, table 5.6 shows a summary of the metadata of the dataset such as age group, ethnicity and gender of the participants.

Table 5.5: Specifications of the created Arcadian-IoT Faces dataset.

Number of people	20 volunteers
Distances recorded	2, 5, 7, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 metres
Video resolution	4K (3840x2160 px)
Video frame rate	30 FPS
Recording device	DJI Mini 2 UAV
Duration per video	30 seconds
Total number of images	9620
Age range	18-60 years
Other characteristics	Various ethnicities Different genders Different head poses
Dataset Division	50% Testing /50% Validation

Table 5.6: Summary of Metadata for the Arcadian-IoT Faces Dataset

Category	Demographic Group	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)
Age Group	18–25 years	6	30%
	26–35 years	9	45%
	36–50 years	3	15%
	51+ years	2	10%
Ethnicity	Caucasian	15	75%
	Asian	2	10%
	African/Caribbean	2	10%
	Other	1	5%
Gender	Male	15	75%
	Female	5	25%

This dataset has been used for the comparison of face verification algorithms (**Outcome 1, Outcome 5**) that were reported and published in two peer-reviewed publications [1, 5] that can be found in Appendix A and Appendix E.

5.2.2 WiderFace

One of the largest publicly available datasets for face detection is the WIDER Face dataset [23]. It contains over 32,00 images and nearly 394,000 labelled faces. The images are divided into 61 different event classes, such as demonstrations, people marching, interviews, football, etc. The strength of this dataset not only lies in the great amount of faces but also in the variety it offers. Faces come in all shapes, sizes, and orientations, and can be partially obscured. This makes it a valuable tool for training and testing algorithms to ensure they can handle real-world scenarios where faces are not always perfectly clear. The WIDER Face dataset is also pre-divided into training, validation, and testing sets in the following percentages respectively, 40%/10%/50%.

Figure 5.12: Example images of the WIDER Face dataset.

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Figure 5.12 shows four examples of images obtained from the WIDER Face dataset with the following event classes: cheering (Figure 5.12a), shoppers (Figure 5.12b), celebration or party (Figure 5.12c) and meeting (Figure 5.12d).

5.3 Dynamic distance-based thresholding

The technique explained in this section, the algorithm used to obtain the thresholds and the experimental results have been reported and published in a peer-reviewed journal [4] which can be found in Appendix D.

Figure 5.13 shows the modified face verification pipeline used for the created dynamic distance-based thresholding. The pipeline is divided into five different stages.

- **Face detection:** The images are processed using a face detection algorithm in order to detect all the faces present in each image. Different algorithms can be used such as RetinaFace [119], MTCNN [120], Viola-Jones [31] or the custom UWS-YOLO. The outputs of this stage are the bounding boxes with the location of detected faces, the detection confidence and the original image.
- **Preprocessing:** It is divided into two different components. Firstly, each detected face is cropped from the original image using the coordinates of the bounding boxes. Secondly, each face is resized to the input size of the algorithms in the Siamese network. The original size of the detected face is stored for future use in the next step by the dynamic thresholding technique.
- **Siamese network:** It is composed of two Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) that have the same architecture and the same weights, thus, with the same input they will have the same embeddings as output. They process both cropped faces, and the outputs are the embeddings of each of them.
- **Distance calculation:** In this stage, the distance between the embedding of both faces is calculated. Different metrics can be used to calculate the distance, such as Manhattan

distance, Euclidean distance or cosine distance. This pipeline only uses the former two, as they are the main ones used in the literature and the ones with the best performance.

- **Decision making:** This stage determines if both faces belong to the same person based on the distance previously calculated compared to a threshold. If the calculated distance is below the threshold, both faces belong to the same person, otherwise, they belong to different people. The key contribution is a dynamic threshold that adapts to face size. This dynamic approach improves accuracy by using a tailored threshold based on face size, obtained from the second stage, leading to more true positives (correctly identified matches) and fewer false negatives. The chosen threshold also considers the specific algorithm, metric, and distance between the face and the UAV.

Figure 5.13: UAV face verification pipeline adding the novel size adaptive dynamic thresholding technique.

To calculate the new dynamic thresholds, establishing a scale is essential. Two approaches can be considered for defining this scale. The first approach utilises distances from the face to the UAV's camera, applying different thresholds based on the person's distance. However, this method presents challenges, such as accurately determining face distance, especially when UAVs lack rangefinders. Additionally, variations in camera resolution can affect face size detection, making this approach less efficient. Alternatively, the most advantageous approach directly employs face size for the scale. By applying one threshold based on face pixel count, greater flexibility can be offered and, if necessary, approximate distance calculation based on camera resolution.

Figure 5.14: Scale used for the dynamic thresholding techniques depending on the width of the cropped face and its association with the distances of the recorded dataset.

Once this approach is selected, the scale must be established. The thresholds are primarily determined by face width, as significant changes are observed in width rather than height in the images. The scale comprises four ranges based on empirical experimentation, each corresponding to different pixel widths of detected faces. These ranges are depicted in Figure 5.14, illustrating the covered distances in our dataset.

Utilising this scale and adjusting thresholds based on detected face width is expected to enhance the accuracy of face verification algorithms across all distances. Moreover, this approach establishes the system independent of camera resolution, relying solely on face size in pixels rather than face-to-person distance.

The methodology for empirically calculating thresholds is outlined in the algorithm described in the published journal paper [4]. The verification set comprises close-up images of each person's face in the dataset, termed face identity. Positive pairs consist of frames associated with the same face identity, while negative pairs include frames with different face identities. A similarity index is defined as the distance between two faces, and a hyperparameter iterates through threshold candidates in a loop.

The algorithm calculates ratios for both positive and negative pairs to ensure equal importance. A loop iterates through threshold candidate values, calculating True Positives (TP) and True Negatives (TN) based on these thresholds. Using TP, TN, and the previously calculated ratios, accuracy is then computed. The chosen threshold is the one that obtains the highest accuracy upon loop completion.

5.4 UWS-YOLO: Face detection algorithm

A new face detection algorithm has been developed to be used on UAV videos or images, named UWS-YOLO. The architecture of UWS-YOLO can be seen in Figure 5.15.

Figure 5.15: The architecture of UWS-YOLO face detector.

The backbone's starting point is Tiny-YOLOv4 [121], which has a low inference time (4 ms). Enhancements were implemented on the backbone to develop UWS-YOLO, boosting its accuracy while maintaining its fast inference speed capability. Three specific modifications were applied to transform Tiny-YOLOv4 into UWS-YOLO.

- **Cross-Stage Partial (CSP) Blocks modules** [122] have been introduced as replacements for the ResBlock module within residual networks. They improve the flow of gradient information within the network, leading to better learning capabilities. The CSP block works by splitting the feature maps into two branches, applying different transformations to each branch, and then merging them back together.
- An **enhanced Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP)** [123] layer is added at the end of the network's backbone (marked "b" in the diagram). This layer allows the network to handle images of varying sizes effectively. SPP captures information from different spatial resolutions within the image, which is crucial for detecting small faces in large images captured from high altitudes. This makes the network more robust to changes in image size caused by the UAV's flight altitude.
- The network also incorporates a **modified Path Aggregation Network (PAN)** [124] module (marked "c" in the diagram) with three up-sampling stages (compared to the standard YOLOv4 implementation). This module helps preserve fine-grained details extracted from low-resolution faces during the network's processing. This is important because losing these details can significantly impact face detection accuracy.

In summary, the main modifications made to the Tiny-YOLOv4 architecture, as illustrated in Figure 5.15, are numbered for clarity. First, the CSP module filters were adjusted from 128/256/512 to 64/128/256 (1), with experiments conducted on various filter configurations to identify the optimal number. Second, a SPP module, absent in the original Tiny-YOLOv4, was incorporated to enhance multi-scale feature extraction (2). Third, the simple upsampling strategy of the original design was replaced with a more complex PAN module featuring three upsampling operations, which significantly improved feature fusion across the network (3). Fourth, the number of output layers was expanded from two, optimised for detecting large and medium-sized objects, to three, enabling more accurate detection of small objects such as distant faces (4). Finally, the input resolution was increased from 416×416 to 608×608 (5), providing more detailed information to the model and enhancing overall detection accuracy. These enhancements collectively improve the model's suitability for UAV-based

face detection tasks. Appendix F shows a more extended visualisation of the UWS-YOLO architecture, detailing each of its layers.

This architecture and the results obtained with this algorithm have been reported and explained in a peer-reviewed journal paper [3] which can be found in Appendix C. Furthermore, those results are expanded in Chapter 6 in this thesis.

5.5 AI UAV integration

The AI UAV integration was reported and explained in a peer-reviewed conference paper (**Outcome 2**) which can be found in Appendix B [2], but using object detection algorithms. This subsection expands that publication by integrating face detection algorithms, aligning with the main aim of this thesis.

Therefore, the next step in this research was to integrate the two developed technologies: the open UAV and the face verification pipeline. However, due to the limited capabilities of the BeagleBone AI-64, the entire pipeline cannot be embedded, as the board cannot simultaneously execute two models. Therefore, the goal was to incorporate the face detection algorithm into the open UAV system, enabling offloading of computational tasks and facilitating edge computing.

Three models were executed on the BBAI-64, as detailed in Table 5.7. It is worth noting that UWS-YOLO could not be onboarded on the board due to compatibility issues. The BBAI-64 can only execute compatible backbones [125], such as the modified version of the YoloX backbone used in these experiments. The three models used are different versions of the YoloX backbone varying their sizes. Their size is directly related to the Giga Multiply-Accumulations (GigaMACS) that shows the complexity of each model, the lower the better, as the model will be less complex.

These models are referred to as Lite because they are modifications of the original backbones to be quantisation- and embedding-friendly. These Lite models use the ReLU activation function instead of more complex ones such as Swish, HSwish, SeLU, etc., to facilitate quantisation and embedding on the board. All models were trained using the

WIDER Face dataset, as explained in previous sections. The models were trained and implemented using the MMDetection framework [126].

The accuracy in Table 5.7 is shown using the Mean average precision (mAP) metric computed at 0.5 Intersection over Union (IoU). For comparison, UWS-YOLO achieves an accuracy of 72.26% mAP50% on the WiderFace dataset, besting the accuracy of the other 3 models.

Table 5.7: Summary of the face detection models executed inside the BeagleBone AI-64.

Model	mAP 50%	Input Size	GigaMACS	Model size
YoloX-Tiny (Lite)	49.1%	416x416	3.19	21MB
YoloX-S (Lite)	64.4%	640x640	13.29	38MB
YoloX-M (Lite)	67.5%	640x640	36.67	104MB

In Chapter 6 two scenarios are evaluated: one where the face detection algorithm is executed on a ground computer, receiving video from the BBAI-64 and another where the face detection algorithm is executed inside the BBAI-64, sending the video with the detections to the GCS. The advantage of the second method is that the video resolution can be lowered, resulting in less transmission delay and reduced bandwidth usage since the algorithm has already been executed, making high resolution unnecessary.

Chapter 6

Results

This chapter presents the results obtained from the extensive experiments conducted throughout this research. The findings are exhibited to highlight the performance and efficacy of the developed UAV platform, the implemented face detection and verification algorithms, and the novel dynamic distance-based thresholding technique. Key metrics such as inference time, accuracy, and processing efficiency are analysed to provide a comprehensive assessment of each component's contribution to the overall system. Through detailed analysis and comparison, this chapter aims to demonstrate the effectiveness of the integrated UAV-based facial verification system. The results presented in this chapter are extended from the ones shown in the publications that form this thesis.

It is important to note, as explained in previous chapters, that the EU AI Act introduces a risk-based framework for AI systems, categorising real-time biometric identification in public spaces as high-risk and subject to stringent requirements. However, as outlined in Article 2(6), the AI Act exempts AI systems developed exclusively for research purposes, such as the one created for the experiments described in this chapter.

To ensure compliance with applicable regulations, the experiments presented in this chapter incorporated the following measures:

- **Data minimisation:** Only the data strictly necessary to train and execute the models was used. The data was limited to the specific purposes of the thesis and its defined use cases.

- **Purpose limitation:** It was ensured that the AI models in this thesis were developed and used solely for research purposes. Moreover, the use cases were restricted to those explicitly defined in the thesis, excluding any defence or law enforcement applications.
- **Storage limitation:** All data and models were stored only for the duration of the thesis. Upon completion, the data will be deleted, ensuring that storage is limited to the project's scope.
- **Integrity and confidentiality (Security):** The computers where the models and data were stored were secured with password protection to limit external access. Additionally, the database containing the datasets was encrypted and secured, preventing any unauthorized external access that could lead to a security breach.

6.1 Dynamic distance-based thresholding technique

In this section, the results of the novel thresholding technique are shown. This dynamic size-adaptive thresholding technique has been explained in the previous section. It was already reported and published in a peer-reviewed journal paper [4], which can be found in Appendix D. Therefore, the results shown in this section are obtained using two different algorithms from the ones used for the journal paper. This will show the effectiveness of this technique as similar results are obtained using different algorithms. The ones used for this report are FaceNet512 [75] and OpenFace [127], whereas in the journal paper, the ones compared were ArcFace [73], SFace [128], Dlib [76] and VGG-Face [70].

6.1.1 Testbed

The experiments have been carried out on a computer with an Intel(R) Xeon(R) E5-2630 v4 at 2.20 GHz with 20 cores and 32 GB of RAM. In addition, an NVIDIA GeForce GTX TITAN X with 12 GB of onboard memory with CUDA compatibility [129] was used. The Operative System (OS) used is Focal Ubuntu 20.04.3 with a Kernel version of 5.11.00.

6.1.2 Application of the Proposed Methodology for Close (5 m) and Far (15 m) Distances

The proposed methodology explained in Section 5.3 is applied to the FaceNet512 and OpenFace algorithms using the Arcadian-IoT Faces dataset. The thresholds are calculated to maximise the accuracy of the algorithms at each of the distance ranges using the testing part of the dataset.

Figure 6.1a shows how the proposed thresholds are obtained. This figure shows an example of how the threshold is obtained for each algorithm at a close range, showing how the accuracy changes for a distance of 5 metres. The figure shows two graphs for each algorithm, the upper ones are the distribution of the similarity indexes of each algorithm. Each graph includes two plots, one for the positive pairs and the other for the negative pairs. The positive pairs are obtained by executing the pipeline with the videos of one individual, comparing it with the picture of its own face and obtaining the similarity indexes. On the other side, the negative pairs are obtained oppositely. The videos of one individual are compared with the pictures of all the people in the dataset besides that individual. The similarity indexes of the positive pairs should have lower values as two faces of the same person are being compared, whereas the negative pairs will have higher values as the faces belong to two different people.

The further apart both plots are from each other, the higher accuracy will be obtained. If both graphs are not overlapped there will be no false negatives or false positives, thus the threshold will be easy to define, maximising the accuracy. On the other side, if both plots are closer to each other, they will overlap and there will be a high number of false positives and negatives and it will be more difficult to define an appropriate threshold, thus the accuracy will be low.

Let us see the example of Figure 6.1a. The original thresholds are obtained from the Deepface project [130, 131]. Looking at Figure 6.1c both similarity index plots can be seen for FaceNet512 at 5 metres using cosine distance as metric. Both plots are not highly overlapped, thus it will be easy to obtain high accuracy by defining an adequate threshold.

(a) Distribution of Similarity indexes of FaceNet512 (b) Distribution of Similarity indexes of OpenFace

(c) Accuracy by threshold of FaceNet512

(d) Accuracy by threshold of OpenFace

Figure 6.1: Distribution of distances and accuracy by threshold at **5 metres** of the two algorithms using **cosine distance** as metric

Figure 6.1c shows how the accuracy varies depending on the defined threshold. It can be seen that by using the original threshold the accuracy will be low (60%), whereas if the optimal threshold is defined an accuracy of 96% could be obtained. The threshold could be modified depending on the use case, for instance, if it was crucial to minimise the false positives, the threshold could be moved to the left to be further from the negative pairs plot, but the accuracy will be lower.

Figures 6.1b and 6.1d show the same but for the OpenFace algorithm using the cosine distance metric at 5 metres. In this case, both similarity index plots are more overlapped, thus the accuracy obtained is lower, only reaching 72% by maximising the possible accuracy.

(a) Distribution of Similarity indexes of FaceNet512 (b) Distribution of Similarity indexes of OpenFace

(c) Accuracy by threshold of FaceNet512

(d) Accuracy by threshold of OpenFace

Figure 6.2: Distribution of distances and accuracy by threshold at **15 metres** of the two algorithms using **cosine distance** as metric

Figure 6.2 shows the same graphs but at 15 metres and using again cosine distance as metric. As can be seen, in both upper graphs, the plots are more overlapped. This occurs as the face is further from the camera, thus the resolution is lower and two different faces are going to look more similar. FaceNet512 plots (Figure 6.2a) can still be easily differentiated as they are not completely overlapped, whereas OpenFace plots (Figure 6.2b) are almost completely overlapped, thus the accuracy will be low.

This can be seen in the other two graphs. As FaceNet512 plots are not highly overlapped, it is easier to establish an optimal threshold with a high accuracy as shown in Figure 6.2c. On the other side, as OpenFace plots are overlapped, a low accuracy is obtained as there are going to be many false positives or negatives, as shown in Figure 6.2d.

It is important to notice that the thresholds selected at this distance do not coincide with the point of highest accuracy in the graphs. This occurs because the optimal threshold is calculated based on four specific ranges as explained in previous sections. Each range includes two distances of the created dataset. The far distance range includes 15 and 20 metres, thus the optimal threshold is going to be the one that maximises both distances, not only the one of 15 metres. Hence, the threshold at 15 metres is not the maximum of the graph.

The same experiments were executed but using Euclidean distance as metric instead of cosine distance. Figure 6.3 shows the same graphs as cosine distance at 5 metres but using Euclidean distance as metric. The main difference between both metrics is that cosine distance has a range of values between 0 and 2, whereas Euclidean distance goes from 0 to infinite.

As can be seen in the upper figures, FaceNet512 plots (Figure 6.3a) are not highly overlapped, whereas OpenFace ones are (Figure 6.3b). Both graphs are similar to the ones of cosine distance at the same distance. FaceNet512 is easily obtained with a high accuracy (96%) improving the original one. On the other side, OpenFace does not achieve such high accuracy but the results are improved from the original one, achieving 72% of accuracy.

Finally, the same experiments are executed but using Euclidean distance as metric at 15 metres of distance. The plots of both algorithms are highly overlapped, thus not great

Figure 6.3: Distribution of distances and accuracy by threshold at **5 metres** of the two algorithms using **Euclidean distance** as metric

accuracy is achieved. Nevertheless, FaceNet512 obtains better results than OpenFace as its plots are less overlapped. As in the cosine distance graphs, the optimal thresholds do not coincide with the maximum point of accuracy. As previously explained, this occurs as the optimal threshold is calculated for a range of distances and not exclusively for 15 metres.

Table 6.1 shows the calculated dynamic thresholds using the proposed technique using cosine distance as metric. As can be seen, the closer to the face the threshold is less restrictive (lower), whereas at further distances the threshold will be more restrictive (higher). One exception is OpenFace with far and very far distances. Both thresholds are similar, with the threshold for very far distances lower. This can be explained as the OpenFace algorithm

(a) Distribution of Similarity indexes of FaceNet512 (b) Distribution of Similarity indexes of OpenFace

(c) Accuracy by threshold of FaceNet512

(d) Accuracy by threshold of OpenFace

Figure 6.4: Distribution of distances and accuracy by threshold at **15 metres** of the two algorithms using **Euclidean distance** as metric

does not have high accuracy and at far distances is not able to verify, therefore there are discrepancies due to the low accuracy.

Table 6.1: Our dynamic thresholds calculated for cosine distance as metric

Algorithm	Very Far	Far	Medium	Close
FaceNet512	0.905	0.807	0.632	0.611
OpenFace	0.436	0.44	0.345	0.325

On the other side, Table 6.2 shows the dynamic thresholds but uses Euclidean distance as metric. As in the previous table, the furthest the face, the threshold will be more restrictive. However, the same exception as before is shown, that at the furthest distance, the threshold

lowers again. As with OpenFace with cosine distance, this occurs as the algorithms have very low accuracy at this distance, thus there will be many false verifications. Therefore, these algorithms are not recommended to be used at these distances using Euclidean distance as metric.

Table 6.2: Our dynamic thresholds calculated for Euclidean distance as metric

Algorithm	Very Far	Far	Medium	Close
FaceNet512	27.5	28.1	26.4	25.6
OpenFace	0.806	0.938	0.83	0.806

6.1.3 Accuracy

After executing the experiments for both algorithms at every distance included in the dataset and obtaining the thresholds for each distance, the accuracy has been calculated. These calculations have been executed using the other half of the created dataset, the one used for validation.

Figure 6.5: Accuracy of the algorithms at fixed distances using the old and the proposed thresholds and cosine distance as metric

Figure 6.5 shows the accuracy of both algorithms at every distance of the dataset using the original and the proposed thresholds using cosine distance as metric. As it can be seen,

for FaceNet512 (6.5a) the maximum improvement is at middle distances, like 7, 10 and 15 metres. OpenFace (Figure 6.5b) improves the most at close distances like 2, 5 and 7 metres.

Table 6.3: Accuracy of the algorithms at different distances using our dynamic thresholds - Cosine Distance

Algorithm	2m	5m	7m	10m	15m	20m	25m	30m
FaceNet512	96.95	96.6	94.89	89.89	82.42	74.78	67.16	63.48
OpenFace	75.85	72.44	73.00	71.00	67.12	60.71	59.35	60.77

Table 6.3 shows the accuracy values for both algorithms at each distance. As can be seen, FaceNet512 has far better accuracy than OpenFace, being most noticeable at close distances. The further the distance, the lower the accuracy, as the face resolution will be as well lower. The only exception is OpenFace at 30 metres which is a bit better than at 20 metres. This can occur due to how the threshold is selected to optimise that range, as the values are very close.

Figure 6.6: Accuracy of the algorithms at fixed distances using the old and the proposed thresholds and Euclidean distance as metric

Figure 6.6 shows the accuracy of both algorithms at every distance using Euclidean distance as metric.

Table 6.4 shows the accuracy value of each algorithm at every distance of the dataset using Euclidean distance as metric. For FaceNet512, using cosine distance the accuracy obtained is better than by using Euclidean distance. Therefore, if this algorithm is used it is recommended to use cosine distance as metric.

Table 6.4: Accuracy of the algorithms at different distances using our dynamic thresholds - Euclidean Distance

Algorithm	2m	5m	7m	10m	15m	20m	25m	30m
FaceNet512	96.8	96.22	94.08	89.28	79.7	70.37	65.1	62.8
OpenFace	75.84	72.42	73	71	67.13	60.7	59.36	60.76

On the other hand, OpenFace achieves almost the same accuracy values by using both metrics, thus any can be used. However, the accuracy obtained is far lower than FaceNet512, so this algorithm is preferable to be used for face verification from UAVs.

6.1.4 Inference time

The inference time is defined as the time it takes to process each frame, in other words, the time elapsed since a face enters the model until the embeddings are obtained. The obtained cumulative average inference time can be seen in Figure 6.7. All the models compared during this research project are shown, including the ones previously published in the publications. Therefore, six different models are compared: VGG-Face, FaceNet512, ArcFace, OpenFace, SFace and Dlib.

As can be seen in the figure, VGG-Face is the slowest algorithm, taking around 112 ms to process one face. In second place FaceNet512 takes 76 ms. Then, with similar times we have ArcFace, OpenFace and SFace with an inference time of 63 ms, 58 ms and 53 ms respectively. Finally, the fastest model is Dlib which takes 26 ms to obtain the embeddings of one single face.

6.2 UWS-YOLO

All results related to UWS-YOLO were initially reported in the following paper [3], which can be found in Appendix C. However, since that publication, a new version of YOLO, YOLOv9 [132], has been released by the authors of YOLOv7 [133]. Given its relevance, a comparison between our UWS-YOLO algorithm and YOLOv9 is needed.

Figure 6.7: Cumulative average inference time in milliseconds for each of the compared face verification algorithms.

Following the methodology of our prior work, YOLOv9 was trained on the WIDER Face dataset [134]. This model achieved an accuracy of 62.9% on the WIDER Face dataset using an IoU threshold of 50%. Notably, the other models evaluated in our previous journal paper demonstrated superior accuracy, as summarised in Table 6.5.

Model	mAP50 WIDER Face	Number of faces detected (Figure 6.8)
RetinaFace	81.96%	69 faces
YOLOv7	65.43%	164 faces
YOLOv9	62.90%	178 faces
UWS-YOLO	72.26%	409 faces

Table 6.5: Comparison of different face detection models on the WIDER Face dataset and executed on the world's largest selfie.

For qualitative comparison, the "world's largest selfie" was utilised, a standard benchmark image containing over 1100 faces of varying sizes. Figure 6.8 visually demonstrates the performance of each model on this challenging image. UWS-YOLO clearly outperforms the other three models, detecting a significantly larger number of faces. Conversely, RetinaFace

exhibits the weakest performance. Table 6.5 provides a quantitative comparison of the number of faces detected by each model.

Figure 6.8: Example of face detection algorithms on the world's largest selfie using the same input size.

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6.3 AI open-UAV integration

This section expands on the results obtained in an accepted peer-reviewed publication (Appendix B, **Outcome 2**) [2]. In this publication, the AI open-UAV integration was performed using object detection models to establish a proof of concept. In this section, the integration and comparison are conducted using face detection models, aligning with the scope and aim of this thesis.

6.3.1 Testbed

The following results were obtained from a system capable of operating in a real-world environment. The designed and built open UAV was used for the experiments. A Logitech C920 HD Pro webcam was attached to the UAV to record the video. The recorded video is in Full-HD (1920x1080 px) with a frame rate of 30 fps. The camera includes an autofocus feature and has a diagonal field of view (FOV) of 78 degrees. It is connected to the BeagleBone AI-64 via a USB cable. Internet connectivity for the board is provided through a Huawei E8372 4G modem, equipped with a GiffGaff SIM card.

When the video is sent directly from the camera to the RTSP server via the BeagleBone AI-64, a GStreamer command is used to transmit the video without compression. In this scenario, the raw video stream is transmitted directly. The GStreamer command used to transmit the video is as follows:

```
gst-launch-1.0 v4l2src device=/dev/video2 io-mode=2 !  
rstpsink location=rtsp://<IP>:<Port>/live.stream
```

In the alternative scenario, the BeagleBone AI-64 processes the video. The video is captured from the camera, and each frame is individually processed using the jpegdec component from GStreamer. The processed frames are then analysed by the AI algorithm, reassembled into a video stream, and transmitted through RTSP with H.264 compression. More information on the processing of the video can be found in the official Edge AI for BeagleBone AI-64 documentation [135].

The computer used to execute the face verification pipeline, as described in the previous sections, is equipped with an Intel(R) Xeon(R) E5-2630 v4 processor running at 2.20 GHz with 20 cores and 32 GB of RAM. Additionally, an NVIDIA GeForce GTX TITAN X with 12 GB of onboard memory and CUDA compatibility [129] was used. The operating system (OS) is Ubuntu 20.04.3 Focal Fossa with a kernel version of 5.11.00.

Figure 6.9 shows the schematic of the network implemented for these experiments. As described, the BeagleBone AI-64 uses a 4G modem for Internet access and connects to

the computer executing the face verification pipeline. The computer is located on a private network and connected to a router with a public IP address. Network Address Translation (NAT) [136] is used to forward the necessary ports from the router to the computer. This configuration allows the BeagleBone AI-64 to connect to the computer to send the video stream or face images.

Figure 6.9: Testbed network system.

Table 6.6 shows two metrics evaluated for the network. Using the Iperf command, it was determined that the bandwidth of the connection averaged 4.41 Mb/s. Additionally, using the Hping3 command, the round-trip time (RTT) was calculated to average 57.8 ms.

Command	Metric	Value
Iperf	Bandwidth	4.41 Mb/s
Hping3	RTT	57.8 ms

Table 6.6: Metrics of the network used for the testbed.

6.3.2 Embedded face detection algorithm inference time

Once the network and the system were fully set up, experiments were conducted to measure the inference time of the models and their total processing time. The YoloX face detection algorithms were embedded inside the BBAI-64, and the pipelines were executed to capture video from the USB camera.

The calculated inference time represents the duration it takes for the Deep Learning (DL) network to produce results from the preprocessed frame. In contrast, the total processing time

encompasses the duration from when a frame enters the pipeline until the result is obtained, including preprocessing and postprocessing times.

Figure 6.10 illustrates the cumulative average inference time for the three compared versions of the YoloX algorithm. As depicted, the Tiny model exhibits the fastest inference time at approximately 5 ms, followed by the S version at around 15 ms, and the M version at around 25 ms. This is closely related to the size of each model; larger models tend to have higher inference times but offer better accuracy. Therefore, the choice of model depends on the specific use case.

Figure 6.10: Inference time of the models executed in the BeagleBone AI-64

Additionally, Figure 6.11 showcases the total processing time of each model. Both the Tiny and S versions have a total time of 33 ms, while the M version is around 35 ms. The Tiny and S versions share the same total time because they match the frame rate of the video being processed, which is 30 fps (33 ms). Consequently, their pipelines are faster than the rate at which they receive new frames, requiring them to wait until completion before the arrival of a new frame.

Figure 6.11: Total time to process a frame of the models executed in the BeagleBone AI-64.

Based on these findings, using the Tiny model in this use case may not be worthwhile, as it results in the same total time as the S version due to the limitation imposed by the video frame rate. Moreover, the S version offers better accuracy. On the other hand, the M version processes video slightly slower than real-time, with a processing time that closely aligns with a frame rate of around 28.6 fps. Therefore, for this use case, the logical choices would be the S version if speed is the primary concern or the M version if greater accuracy is required.

Table 6.7: Time results obtained by the different models executed in the BeagleBone AI-64 and the computer.

Model	Device	Input Size	Inference time	Total frame rate
YoloX-Tiny	BBAI-64	416x416	7.31 ms	30.0 fps
YoloX-S	BBAI-64	640x640	13.85 ms	30.0 fps
YoloX-M	BBAI-64	640x640	24.99 ms	28.6 fps
UWS-YOLO	PC	608x608	10.98 ms	30.0 fps

Table 6.7 summarises the obtained results. As explained, YoloX-M is the only model that is not able to process the video in real-time, achieving a lower frame rate than the video. Thus, if real-time processing is needed, the main choice would be between YoloX-S

Figure 6.12: Inference time versus accuracy of the compared algorithms in the WIDER Face dataset.

and UWS-YOLO executed on the computer. At first glance, the obvious choice would be UWS-YOLO as it achieves better accuracy on the WIDER Face dataset while maintaining the same processing speed of 30 fps. However, if only face detection is being executed, the video sent from the BBAI-64 would have a reduced resolution as the algorithm has already been executed. Therefore, the total execution time would be lower as the video would have less delay due to its lower resolution.

On the other hand, if the whole face verification process is to be executed, performing the face detection algorithm on the BBAI-64 means only the detected faces need to be sent through the network, not the entire video. This will reduce the delay of the whole pipeline if the number of detected faces is not high. If many faces are detected, the delay will be higher than sending the video, as many images would need to be transmitted through the network.

Figure 6.12 shows a comparison of inference time and accuracy for each algorithm on the WIDER Face dataset using an IoU threshold of 0.5. The fastest algorithm is YoloX-Tiny, but it also has the lowest accuracy. UWS-YOLO achieves the second-fastest time with the

highest accuracy when executed on the ground computer. YoloX-S is slightly slower and has slightly lower accuracy than UWS-YOLO. Finally, YoloX-M is significantly slower and does not substantially improve its accuracy compared to YoloX-S.

Chapter 7

Limitations

Despite the promising results and advancements achieved in this research, several limitations need to be acknowledged. These limitations pertain to various aspects of the project, including the hardware constraints of the UAV platform, the performance trade-offs of the implemented algorithms, and the ethical and regulatory challenges associated with facial verification technology. This chapter critically evaluates these constraints, providing a comprehensive overview of the areas that require special attention or improvement.

7.1 Open-source UAV

This section will analyse the limitations of the open-source UAV. It will first focus on the limitations of the different interfaces between the UAV and other devices, such as the FPV video and telemetry. Then, it will analyse the hardware limitations of the UAV, such as battery duration and flight range.

7.1.1 FPV Video

The FPV video is transmitted from the UAV using the TX801 Eachine transmitter [105] employing the Phase Alternating Line (PAL) colour encoding at 5.8GHz. The transmitted video is analogue. The transmitter offers the flexibility of selecting from 8 channels and 9 frequency bands, providing a total of 72 possibilities for video transmission. Additionally, it

features 8 different power levels ranging from 0.01mW to 600mW, allowing adjustment of transmission power based on specific use cases. There are two main threats that the UAV might encounter in FPV video transmission:

1. **Video signal jamming:** This involves the transmission of radio signals on the same frequency as the channel of our video transmission to disrupt communication between our transmitter and receiver.
 - Solution: Our transmitter offers the capability to adjust the power transmission level across 8 levels. If interference is detected, the power level can be increased to mitigate the issue.
2. **Video interception:** This occurs when the video transmitted by the UAV is intercepted and viewed by a third party.
 - Solution: There is no available solution as the transmitted analogue video lacks a security protocol. Consequently, the video could be viewed by anyone with a receiver tuned to that channel and frequency band. To address privacy concerns, it may be advisable to refrain from using FPV video for sensitive use cases and instead rely solely on direct visual observation of the UAV.

7.1.2 Joystick and receiver

As explained in Section 5, the joystick used is Taranis X9D [107] and the receiver is FRSky X8R [98]. The communication between them is made using a private communication protocol: ACCST D16 [137]. This protocol, operating at a frequency of 2.4GHz with 16 available channels [138], is not encrypted, making it susceptible to potential hacking [139] [140].

1. **Signal jamming:** Similar to previous examples, signal jamming involves emitting a radio signal that interferes with ACCST communication, preventing message reception [141].

- **Solution:** In the event of lost connection between the transmitter and receiver, a failsafe will activate so the UAV triggers the RTH mode, returning to the take-off point. Moreover, ACCST uses Frequency Hopping Spread Spectrum (FHSS) that makes the communication more robust to interference and jamming.
2. **UAV takeover:** It consists of a malicious third party seizing control of the drone, by bypassing the communication between the transmitter and the receiver [140]. Thus, the attacker gains full control of the UAV for any purpose.
 - **Solution:** As ACCST is not encrypted the takeover cannot be avoided as explained in [140]. A possible solution could include not using this communication and controlling the UAV using the Ground Control Station. Another option could be encrypting the communication protocol.

7.1.3 Telemetry receiver

The telemetry is transmitted between two Holybro telemetry radios [96], with one connected to the flight controller in the UAV and the other to the computer running the GCS at 433MHz. These radios utilise an open-source firmware known as SiK [97]. Additionally, the telemetry radios employ FHSS, which, as discussed in the previous subsection, enhances communication resilience to interference. Moreover, as explained in Section 5, the telemetry messages use the MAVLink protocol.

1. **Telemetry signal jamming:** It involves introducing interference at 433MHz, the operational frequency of the telemetry radios, thereby impeding the accurate reception of telemetry messages.
 - **Solution:** The telemetry radios use FHSS that can help mitigate jamming to some extent. Additionally, utilising a ground path antenna could enhance telemetry signal reception.

2. **Telemetry signal interception:** Since MAVLink messages [115] lack encryption, they are susceptible to interception and analysis by malicious entities, enabling access to all UAV telemetry data.
 - Solution: To prevent telemetry message interception, the MAVLink could be encrypted. One approach involves incorporating ChaCha20 encryption [142] into MAVLink messages [143], as proposed in the study on MAVSec [144].

7.1.4 BeagleBone AI-64

The BBAI-64 [106] is vulnerable to attacks since it must exchange messages with the GCS. As a preventive measure, no ports are left open on the board.

1. **Video interception:** UAV video feeds are transmitted to a video proxy using either Real Time Streaming Protocol (RTSP) or Real-Time Messaging Protocol (RTMP), both of which can be intercepted.
 - Solution: To mitigate such attacks, two options exist. Firstly, employing encrypted versions of these protocols, such as RTSPS or RTMPE, though this may introduce delays in video transmission. Secondly, implementing authentication mechanisms to control access to the video feeds.
2. **Detection messages interception:** Messages with the detections, transmitted via Representational State Transfer (REST), are also susceptible to interception.
 - Solution: Encrypting detection messages or utilising Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) to establish secure connections for message transmission can enhance security.
3. **Telemetry interception:** Telemetry messages, transmitted using the unencrypted MAVLink protocol, are vulnerable to interception.
 - Solution: As explained in the previous subsection, MAVLink could be encrypted by adding ChaCha20 encryption into the messages, enhancing the transmission's security.

4. **WIFI or 4G/5G jamming:** The UAV communicates with other devices via WIFI or 4G/5G, both of which could be subject to jamming or may have insufficient coverage.
 - Solution: In the event of jamming in one communication channel, switching to the alternative channel is an option. If both channels are jammed, the UAV can still be operated using alternative control methods such as telemetry receivers or joysticks, although detection data will not be received.

7.1.5 GNSS receiver

The UAV utilises a standard GPS module M8N from the brand Holybro [88]. It can use up to two GNSS constellations concurrently between the four available: Global Positioning System (GPS), Galileo, GLONASS, BeiDou.

1. **GNSS spoofing:** This occurs when a counterfeit GNSS signal is transmitted to a receiver antenna, overriding legitimate GPS satellite signals and providing false UAV position data, which can lead to unauthorised control or potential crashes.
 - Solution: To mitigate GNSS spoofing, our UAV employs the capability to switch between different constellations. This solution would be effective if all four constellations were not under attack simultaneously. Additionally, specific countermeasures can be integrated into the UAV system to prevent such attacks.
2. **GNSS jamming:** This involves intentional interference with GNSS signals, disrupting reception and compromising the accuracy of the UAV's position data, which could potentially lead to crashes or drifting.
 - Solution: Similar to the previous attack, the UAV can use several GNSS constellations, including GLONASS, GPS, Galileo, Beidou. Furthermore, redundancy measures can be implemented by integrating a secondary GNSS receiver onboard. In the event of interference affecting one receiver, the other can be utilised, potentially with different constellations, ensuring continued operation. Additionally,

Figure 7.1: Open UAV battery consumption on a normal flight with low wind and a temperature of 10 degrees.

the UAV can rely on its onboard IMU for navigation, albeit with reduced accuracy and stability compared to GNSS. The IMU could also help to improve the navigation and stability in situations with limited GNSS reception.

7.1.6 Hardware limitations

The UAV also has some hardware and physical limitations. These limitations, like the maximum weight or the duration of the battery, restrict its ability to perform certain activities.

- **Weight lifting:** The UAV weighs around 8kg with one battery onboard and is capable of lifting a payload of up to 10 kg. This payload may include an additional battery or other accessories required for specific use cases.
- **Battery duration:** As explained in Chapter 5, the UAV is powered using a 13Ah 6S 40C LiPo battery. As depicted in Figure 7.1, the UAV average battery consumption during a normal flight is approximately 47Ah, with a peak of 90A during take-off. Therefore, the flight time is limited to around 17 minutes without any payload. Adding more payload further reduces the flight time. The UAV's capacity has been enhanced by allowing the connection of two batteries in parallel, doubling the capacity to 26Ah. However, this doesn't double the flight time because the added weight of the extra battery reduces it to around 25 minutes.
- **Range:** Each interface connecting to the ground has a different connection range depending on the technology and hardware employed. The telemetry connection

typically has a range of 300m but can be extended to several kilometres using a patch antenna on the ground [96]. The maximum distance between the joystick and the X8R receiver is approximately 1.5km [145]. The range of the FPV video transmission depends on the transmitting power level. The maximum theoretical range can be approximated using the Friis transmission formula [146]:

$$P_{Rx} = P_{Tx} + G_{Tx} + G_{Rx} + FSPL - Attenuation_{Atmosphere}$$

where:

- P_{Rx} (dBm): Power received by the receiver. In our case, it is the receiving sensitivity of our receiver R600, which is -95 dBm.
- P_{Tx} (dBm): Power transmitted by the transmitter, has 8 different power level options.
- G_{Rx} (dBi): Gains of the receiver antenna.
- G_{Tx} (dBi): Gains of the transmitter antenna.
- Free-space path loss (FSPL) (dB): It is the loss in signal strength of a signal as it travels through free space. It depends on the distance between the antennas and the signal frequency. It is defined as follows:

$$FSPL(dB) = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{4\pi d f}{c} \right)$$

Ideal conditions are assumed for this calculation, with no loss in transmission, reception or propagation aside from the FSPL. Ambient conditions are also ideal as rain would also attenuate the signal propagation. Table 7.1 presents the maximum calculated ranges under ideal conditions.

Finally, concerning the BBAI-64, if it is connected via WIFI, the range would be limited to less than 100 metres. However, if 4G/5G is used, the range will be virtually unlimited wherever there is coverage. It's important to note that since the UAV can be

Power level (mW)	0.01	5	25	50	100	200	400	600
Power level (dBm)	-20	7	14	17	20	23	26	27.78
Range (km)	0.05	1.03	2.31	3.27	4.62	6.52	9.21	11.3

Table 7.1: Maximum theoretical range of the FPV video depending on the power transmission level used.

remotely controlled using the BBAI-64, with a 4G/5G connection, the UAV's range becomes unrestricted, allowing control from anywhere with an internet connection. Nevertheless, due to CAA regulations in the UK, the UAV is not permitted to conduct Beyond Visual Line of Sight (BVLOS) flights and must remain within VLOS at all times [147].

- **Weather conditions:** The UAV is not waterproof, so flying in rain is not recommended. While it can withstand light rain due to waterproof motors and ESCs, and the canopy covering main components, flying in such conditions is still not advised. This setup allows for a safe UAV landing if it unexpectedly encounters rain. Moreover, flying in temperatures below 0 degrees Celsius is not recommended, primarily because the battery capacity is significantly reduced in cold temperatures, reducing notably the flying time, and condensation on propellers can freeze, potentially leading to a UAV crash. Additionally, flying in strong winds is also discouraged as it can cause loss of control and potential crashes.
- **Companion computer:** Another limitation is that the BeagleBone AI-64 companion computer must operate alongside the existing flight controller, leading to increased power consumption and potential communication delays. Integrating the flight controller directly into the companion computer, running ArduPilot on it, is a potential improvement. However, this approach could limit the capability of executing AI algorithms in parallel, potentially impacting overall system performance. While this integration has been demonstrated successfully with the BeagleBone Blue [148] and BeagleBone Black [149], it has not yet been tested with concurrent AI algorithm execution.

- **Guardian Ground Control Station:** The current system works by connecting the GCS to a detection server that routes messages from the UxVs to every GCS connected to the server. This setup has limited scalability, as the message delay will increase with more GCS and UxVs. This issue can be resolved by integrating other messaging technologies into Guardian, such as RabbitMQ [150] or Kafka [151], which are more suitable for scalability.

7.2 Face detection

There are some limitations regarding the face detection algorithm developed in the context of this research project, UWS-YOLO.

- **Distance:** The algorithm has been tested with faces at a maximum distance of 30 metres. The algorithm could be used at greater distances with proper training or by using an optical zoom on the camera.
- **Inference time:** The algorithm has an inference time of 11 ms. This inference time could be reduced by further enhancing the algorithm or by using a GPU with higher performance capabilities than the one used for testing.
- **Accuracy:** The accuracy of the algorithm could also be improved with further training or by enhancing the images for detection using image enhancement algorithms or optical zoom on the camera.

7.3 Face verification

There are also some limitations in our research developed on face verification. The limitations found in this research are exposed as follows:

- **Accuracy:** The accuracy of the face verification pipeline is limited by the resolution of the images and the performance of the algorithms used. Enhancing the image

resolution of the faces could improve the accuracy. This can be achieved by using higher-quality cameras, employing optimal zoom, or applying image enhancement algorithms. Additionally, improving the algorithms themselves could further increase the accuracy of the pipeline.

- **Inference time:** The inference time of the face verification pipeline could be optimised by reducing the time of each stage. Potential improvements include refining the algorithms, leveraging hardware acceleration like TensorRT on the GPU, or utilising more powerful GPUs with increased processing capabilities.
- **Partial Face Verification:** Our system needs the visibility of the entire face for accurate verification. It exhibits lower accuracy when only half-face is visible, such as when a person is looking sideways.
- **Low-Light Conditions:** While our face verification system performs well under low-lighting conditions, it struggles to achieve optimal accuracy during nighttime settings, where lighting conditions are extremely poor.
- **Distance Limitation:** The effectiveness of our face verification and detection algorithms diminishes significantly beyond a distance of 30 metres. It could be explored to go beyond this distance by enhancing the algorithms used, using image enhancement algorithms or using optical zoom.
- **Drone Stability:** The stability of the drone platform influences the performance of our face verification system. In situations where the drone encounters turbulence or instability during flight, the accuracy of face verification may be compromised.
- **Dynamic Thresholding:** Although the distance-based dynamic threshold technique significantly enhances the accuracy of the compared face verification algorithms, in scenarios where the face verification algorithm exhibits low accuracy, this technique alone would not notably increase it.

7.4 Arcadian-IoT Faces dataset

While the dataset used in this research provides a valuable foundation for face detection and verification in an open-source UAV environment, it is important to acknowledge its limitations regarding bias and generalisability. The dataset was not explicitly designed to ensure diversity across key demographic variables, such as age, ethnicity, gender, or socio-economic background, thus, the dataset's composition reflects inherent biases in its collection process. For instance, the majority of volunteers belonged to specific demographic groups, leading to the under-representation of others.

This lack of systematic effort to mitigate potential biases may lead to skewed representation. Consequently, the face detection and verification algorithms evaluated in this study could exhibit performance disparities when applied to under-represented demographic groups, potentially affecting their generalisability, but performing well on over-represented groups.

Moreover, the algorithms tested in this thesis were evaluated primarily on standard performance metrics, without incorporating techniques aimed explicitly at bias mitigation. Methods such as adversarial debiasing, re-weighting of training samples, or balanced sampling could have been explored to enhance fairness. However, these approaches were not within the scope of this study, leaving potential disparities across demographic groups unaddressed.

Another notable limitation is the dataset's size and variability. Despite efforts to expand its scope, the dataset remains limited in its coverage of diverse conditions and environments. This constraint restricts the algorithms' ability to generalise effectively in real-world scenarios, particularly in settings that deviate significantly from those represented in the dataset.

In summary, while this research provides valuable insights into UAV-based face detection and verification, it highlights key areas for future improvement. Addressing these limitations through the development of a more diverse and representative dataset, combined with the integration of bias-mitigating techniques in both data collection and algorithm design, would enhance the fairness, reliability, and applicability of such systems in practical applications.

7.5 Ethics, GDPR and AI Act

The integration of facial verification technology with UAVs presents a range of ethical and regulatory challenges, especially concerning privacy and data protection. This section examines these issues in greater depth and evaluates how the system developed in this research ensures compliance with the GDPR and the EU AI Act. Additionally, it highlights areas where the platform has successfully addressed these challenges and identifies aspects requiring further refinement.

7.5.1 Compliance with the GDPR

The principles of data protection as outlined in Article 5 of the GDPR serve as a framework for ensuring the responsible handling of personal data. These principles also align with the ethical standards emphasised in the EU AI Act. The face verification system developed in this thesis adheres to these principles to ensure data is processed lawfully, securely, and transparently while safeguarding users' rights. Below, each principle is addressed with respect to the system's design and implementation:

1. **Lawfulness, fairness and transparency:** All data was processed in strict accordance with relevant regulations, including the GDPR and the EU AI Act. Users were informed at all times about how their data was handled, including the purpose and scope of its use. Furthermore, explicit, informed consent was required from all individuals prior to their data being processed for face verification purposes. This consent process was designed to ensure users had full knowledge of their rights and the intended use of their data.
2. **Purpose limitation:** The images obtained for face verification were exclusively used for this specific purpose and were deleted immediately after processing. This prevents their use for any secondary or unintended purposes. Similarly, the dataset images, collected under the European project framework, were used solely for project objectives, including dissemination activities and the research documented in this thesis.

3. **Data minimisation:** Only the minimal amount of data necessary for performing face verification was collected. This included the user's facial image and a unique identifier for verification purposes. No additional personal data was requested or retained, ensuring compliance with the principle of minimising data collection to the essentials.
4. **Accuracy:** By limiting the data collected to what was strictly necessary (facial image and identifier), the risk of inaccuracies or errors in data collection was minimised. The system ensured the accuracy of the captured data to maintain reliability in face verification operations.
5. **Storage limitation:** Data retention policies were designed to limit the storage duration of biometric data. The data of registered users and the dataset were stored only until the completion of the project and its dissemination activities. Following these phases, the database will be securely deleted using industry-standard secure deletion protocols, ensuring no residual data remains accessible.
6. **Integrity and Confidentiality (Security):** All user data was stored securely with advanced encryption methods, ensuring that unauthorized access was prevented. In addition, the facial data was processed through a feature extraction algorithm, and only the resulting feature vectors were stored in the database. This approach ensures that even in the event of a data breach, it would not be possible to reconstruct the original facial images from the stored data.
7. **Accountability:** The system incorporates mechanisms to ensure accountability throughout the data lifecycle. Regular audits were conducted during development to verify compliance with GDPR and the AI Act. Furthermore, roles and responsibilities for data handling were clearly assigned to project team members to prevent unauthorised processing.

7.5.2 Privacy Concerns

Facial verification involves processing biometric data, classified as highly sensitive under Article 9 of the GDPR. The ethical risks include unauthorised surveillance, potential misuse of biometric information, and loss of trust among users. To address these concerns, this research strictly adheres to the principle of data minimisation. The UAV platform ensures facial verification is conducted exclusively on individuals who have provided explicit, informed consent, verified through a robust consent management framework.

Unlike facial recognition systems that compare images against large-scale databases, the platform employs one-to-one facial verification, focusing on verifying the identity of a specific individual. This distinction minimises the risk of profiling or mass surveillance, as emphasised in Chapter 1. Moreover, the UAV's operational scope avoids public spaces, further reducing the potential for misuse.

7.5.3 Data Storage and Processing

The handling of biometric data is guided by the GDPR principles of lawfulness, fairness, and transparency (Article 5). In compliance, the system was designed to avoid permanent storage of biometric data. Facial images are processed transiently and securely, and they are deleted immediately after verification. This approach eliminates risks associated with data breaches or misuse of stored biometric data.

Additionally, the system incorporates technical safeguards to prevent unauthorised access during processing, such as encryption of data in transit and secure deletion protocols. These measures ensure that biometric data is used solely for its intended purpose, aligning with the principles of purpose limitation and storage limitation under GDPR.

7.5.4 Compliance with Regulations

The EU AI Act introduces a risk-based framework for AI systems, categorising real-time biometric identification in public spaces as high-risk and subject to stringent requirements. The UAV platform developed in this thesis avoids high-risk practices by ensuring that:

- **Restricted Operational Environment:** Facial verification is conducted only in controlled environments, never in public spaces. Therefore, no individual who had not explicitly provided informed consent was recorded or verified using the system.
- **Explicit Consent:** All biometric data processing is contingent on the user's informed and explicit consent, ensuring compliance with GDPR Article 7.
- **Transparency Measures:** Users are informed about how their data is processed and the purpose of its collection, with detailed disclosures provided during the consent process.

These design choices demonstrate alignment with the EU AI Act's principles of risk mitigation. Moreover, the EU AI Act exempts systems developed exclusively for research like the one developed in this thesis, as outlined in Article 2 (6):

“This Regulation does not apply to AI systems or AI models, including their output, specifically developed and put into service for the sole purpose of scientific research and development.”

Beyond technical and legal compliance, ethical considerations play a pivotal role in the deployment of facial verification technology. The system emphasises fairness, accountability, and transparency as foundational principles. The system is explicitly designed for safety and security use cases and is not intended for law enforcement or surveillance applications. This restriction prevents ethical misuse associated with profiling or unwarranted surveillance.

7.5.5 Conclusion

The face verification system developed in this research exemplifies a rigorous commitment to ethical and regulatory compliance. By prioritising privacy protection, minimising data retention, processing the data only for the purpose it was obtained and adhering to the GDPR and the EU AI Act, the system sets a benchmark for responsible innovation in biometric and face verification technology. The overall design aligns strongly with existing and emerging

legal frameworks. This commitment to compliance not only safeguards user privacy but also promotes trust and acceptance of facial verification technology in UAV applications among users.

Chapter 8

Conclusions

This thesis is based on five peer-reviewed publications in international journals and conferences where the PhD candidate is the main author. These publications have been submitted, peer-reviewed, accepted and published with exhaustive anonymous peer-reviewed processes. Each publication is presented as a chapter in the second part of this document. Additionally, the candidate has significantly contributed to this thesis by designing two software projects, developing one algorithm, and completing a hardware project. During this thesis, the candidate has also been actively involved and participated in the release of several technical deliverables of the Horizon 2020 European projects Arcadian-IoT [9] and 5G-INDUCE [152] and the Horizon Europe project INCODE [153].

All the objectives outlined in Chapter 3 were achieved, with this research project aiming for a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 5 system, validated through extensive field testing.

This thesis introduces a novel open UAV architecture designed to achieve a sensor and camera-agnostic system (**Objective 2**). The architecture was implemented on a tangible UAV, with extensive testing and experimentation conducted on the ground. This research addresses a significant challenge faced by researchers employing UAVs—the constraint of closed software and hardware. By establishing an open-source platform, researchers gain the flexibility to incorporate any necessary sensors or cameras for their experiments without the limitations imposed by proprietary hardware or the need for intricate reverse engineering processes to integrate hardware with closed-software systems.

The developed open UAV underwent successful testing, exhibiting promising results with a flight duration of 17 minutes on a fully charged battery. Additionally, a customised version of the ground control station QGroundControl, named Guardian, was developed to suit our specific use case. Guardian provides real-time visualisation of algorithmic detections on a map, facilitating enhanced situational awareness for commanders.

A comprehensive literature review was conducted on face verification, encompassing pipelines, face detection and feature extraction algorithms, and publicly available datasets (**Objective 1**). Moreover, an empirical comparison of face verification algorithms was conducted, evaluating distinguished algorithms across different metrics such as inference speed, accuracy, and similarity index distribution (**Objective 4**). This comparison helps identify which algorithms are more suitable for UAV applications and allows for selecting one tailored to a specific use case. The comparison was performed using a dataset obtained from a European project named the Arcadian-IoT Faces Dataset (**Objective 3**). This dataset was utilised for various comparisons and algorithm testing within the project.

Moreover, based on the comparison findings, a novel dynamic distance-based thresholding technique was developed to increase the accuracy of these algorithms based on the UAV camera's distance from the individual's face (**Objective 5**). The thresholds of the face verification pipeline change depending on the distance of the user, leading to a higher accuracy while verifying people from long distances, such as UAV applications. This technique led to accuracy improvements of up to 15%.

Furthermore, A new face detection algorithm based on the Tiny-YOLOv4 backbone was developed to further optimise the face verification pipeline's capabilities (**Objective 6**). This algorithm was tailored to maintain accuracy while enhancing inference speed when detecting faces from distant distances using UAV-recorded images. The novel-designed algorithm outperformed other face detection algorithms on UAV footage, achieving an accuracy of 59.29% on the Arcadian-IoT Faces dataset compared with 27.43% with RetinaFace and 46.59% with YOLOv7. This accuracy is achieved with an inference speed of only 11 ms, which is 345% faster than RetinaFace and 373% than YOLOv7.

Finally, a companion computer with AI capabilities was integrated into the open UAV to augment its capabilities and enable real-time algorithm execution (**Objective 7**). The system underwent testing with various face detection algorithms, compared with the novel UWS-YOLO algorithm executed on a high-spec ground computer. The choice between these models, or running the UWS-YOLO model on a PC, depends on the specific application requirements, balancing accuracy, speed, and network transmission overhead when considering the entire face verification pipeline.

This research has successfully achieved all objectives, resulting in the development of a novel, cost-effective open UAV with high-spec AI capabilities, and advancing research in face verification from UAV footage by enhancing accuracy and inference speed within these pipelines.

Chapter 9

Future work

The present study also reveals that the proposed systems have the potential for further improvements aiming to achieve a TRL level 6 or 7. The open UAV system, for instance, can be enhanced by incorporating new sensors or exploring alternative camera types. The integration of Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) technology could prove particularly beneficial for surveying applications, while other sensors like rangefinders, radars, or multi-spectral cameras could be tested and added to broaden the UAV's capabilities.

Additionally, the open UAV's robustness could be enhanced by addressing some of the vulnerabilities outlined in Chapter 7. In particular, mitigating risks such as UAV takeover or signal jamming attacks would be crucial, especially in light of recent conflicts like the war in Ukraine, which have highlighted the susceptibility of UAVs to such threats. Researching and implementing countermeasures to these attacks could significantly improve the security and reliability of the open UAV system in real-world scenarios.

Another significant improvement for the open UAV system is the integration of the flight controller into the companion computer (BBAI-64), akin to the integration achieved with the BeagleBone Blue [148] and the BeagleBone Black [149]. This integration would streamline the UAV by reducing the number of components, thereby decreasing power consumption and consolidating control systems. Future research could investigate the BBAI-64's ability to execute ArduPilot alongside the AI algorithms outlined in this study, potentially exploring alternative boards if simultaneous operation proves challenging.

Guardian, the enhanced version of the QGroundControl ground control station, could be customised to accommodate messaging from additional technologies such as RabbitMQ or Kafka. Moreover, refining additional features tailored to specific use cases would augment its versatility and effectiveness. For example, expanding the mapping functionality to include the locations of additional assets like devices, vehicles, or personnel beyond just UGVs and UAVs would enhance situational awareness during operations. This expansion would provide operators with a more comprehensive overview of the operational environment, enabling more informed decision-making.

This research could also be improved by using enhanced datasets. For example, the Arcadian-IoT Faces dataset could increase the number of volunteers with diverse backgrounds, including different ethnicities, genders, and ages. This would ensure a balanced dataset and mitigate bias. Moreover, capturing data under various conditions such as different lighting (dawn or dusk), distances exceeding the recorded 30 metres, and different environmental settings would enhance the dataset's robustness.

Another key avenue for future work would be designing and obtaining a dataset for face detection and verification from scratch, instead of obtaining one already available and making it openly accessible for the research community. To achieve this, several steps must be taken to ensure that the dataset complies with ethical and legal standards, particularly those concerning privacy and data protection. Firstly, authorisation from the appropriate ethical committee should be obtained to begin the process of obtaining the images for the dataset. Then, explicit consent forms would need to be obtained from all participants, clearly outlining their understanding of how the data will be used, shared, stored and what purposes it can be used for. These consent forms should meet the requirements of relevant data protection regulations, such as the EU and UK GDPR, to ensure the dataset is ethically and legally compliant.

Before releasing the dataset, it would also be necessary to anonymise or obscure Personally Identifiable Information (PII) within the images to safeguard individual privacy. Techniques such as blurring background elements, cropping to focus only on faces, or using advanced privacy-preserving tools could be applied. Additionally, metadata associated with

each image, such as timestamps or locations, must be carefully reviewed to ensure it does not inadvertently reveal sensitive information.

Moreover, further steps can be taken to enhance its utility and address potential biases. For example, efforts should be made to ensure balanced representation across demographic categories, including age, gender, ethnicity, and other relevant factors, to improve the generalisability and fairness of models trained on the dataset. Synthetic augmentation techniques could be employed to increase the diversity of samples in under-represented groups without compromising privacy. Moreover, robust protocols should be established for data collection, including detailed documentation of the data acquisition process, camera specifications, environmental conditions, and participant demographics.

Finally, comprehensive labels, such as facial expressions, occlusions, or pose variations, could support a broader range of research applications. By taking these steps, the dataset could not only become a valuable open resource but also set a benchmark for ethical and high-quality dataset design in the field of UAV-based face detection and verification.

In addition, the face verification pipeline can also be refined. Incorporating intermediate algorithms, such as image enhancement for low resolution or visibility conditions (low-visibility), could potentially boost accuracy, albeit at the cost of processing speed. Furthermore, efforts to optimise the feature extractor algorithm, as exemplified by the UWS-YOLO face detection model, could yield faster inference times without sacrificing accuracy.

While the research has primarily focused on face detection algorithms, investigating object detection and semantic segmentation algorithms for execution within the BBAI-64 would broaden its applicability. Moreover, if feasible within budget constraints, comparative analysis of alternative boards such as the Coral Dev Board [154], Jetson Orin [155], or Raspberry Pi 5 [156] could provide valuable insights into their suitability for the proposed applications.

As discussed in the thesis, the BeagleBone AI-64 was unable to execute the UWS-YOLO algorithm because the architectural modifications made to the algorithm were not compatible with the hardware acceleration on the board. This limitation highlights the importance of thoroughly evaluating the compatibility of hardware accelerators with the intended AI models

during the selection process for companion computers. In future work, the selection criteria for an AI board should include not only compatibility with a wide range of AI architectures, including non-standard and modified algorithms like UWS-YOLO but also adherence to the project's open-source objective.

Boards such as the NVIDIA Jetson Nano, which incorporates an embedded NVIDIA GPU, or the Coral Dev Board, equipped with a TPU coprocessor, offer broader compatibility with AI models. However, their lack of open-source hardware conflicts with the main thesis objective of developing an entirely open-source UAV platform. This limitation suggests that future comparisons should prioritise hardware that balances compatibility, performance, and open-source availability.

Lessons learned from this experience emphasise the need to test hardware compatibility with the intended algorithms early in the research and development process. Furthermore, conducting a comprehensive review of the hardware's technical documentation, community support, and available software libraries can help mitigate such issues. As future work, a new systematic comparison of companion computers can be undertaken to identify a board that aligns with the project's open-source aim while being capable of executing advanced and modified AI models like UWS-YOLO. This will ensure that future experiments, including comparisons between companion computers and high-spec GPU systems, can be conducted as originally planned.

With all considered, while this work demonstrates considerable potential for further refinement, the research conducted has culminated in an innovative, open UAV architecture. Each component has been meticulously designed, implemented, and validated, resulting in a system that is both sensor- and camera-agnostic, capable of performing effectively across diverse use cases, from intruder detection and search-and-rescue operations to aerial inspections. Moreover, the implemented algorithms and software have advanced the state of the art in UAV-based face verification systems, delivering improved accuracy and speed compared to existing solutions.

Part II

Accepted Publications

Appendix A

Empirical Comparison of Face Verification Algorithms from UAVs

Please note that this chapter contains a copy of content present in the research paper [1], and that, therefore, it has already been peer-reviewed and accepted.

Abstract

Face verification use cases have recently gained momentum in the increasingly digitalised society, and thus the need arises significantly to integrate this technology in wireless/mobile networked systems such as 5G and applications such as Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) based public safety services. However, there is no benchmarking result for the evaluation of the various existing face verification algorithms for such UAV applications. This paper is concerned with such new use cases (e.g., the Drone Guard Angel in the EU H2020 project ARCADIAN-IoT and the surveillance network applications in the EU H2020 project 5G-INDUCE), and provides an empirical comparison among three popular state-of-the-art face verification algorithms for this use case. To this end, a face verification pipeline is presented. These algorithms are then compared in terms of their inference time, and the distribution of the similarity indexes for different distances in UAV-based use cases. Their strengths

and weaknesses are analysed, leading to an insightful recommendation on their applicability scenarios for UAVs.

A.1 Introduction

Nowadays, new technologies are emerging due to the digitisation of society. Two of them are face recognition and face verification. The difference between them is that face recognition needs a database because it relies on telling which person a face belongs to. On the other hand, face verification just compares two faces and decides whether the face belongs to the same person or to a different one.

In recent years face verification has become crucial in various applications, including security and surveillance systems or biometric identification. Traditional face verification systems are based on static cameras in fixed locations. But they have several limitations like restricted coverage or the inability to track a person. In contrast, the use of UAVs for face verification can solve those limitations by being able to cover large areas and follow a person in real-time. One main new use case using this technique is the Drone Guard Angel for public safety escort services, as being developed in the EU H2020 project ARCADIAN-IoT [9]. The UAV will go to the position of the user requesting the service, it will verify the face of the person and will accompany the person home ensuring that it arrives safely. Another example can be observed in the surveillance network applications in the EU H2020 project 5G-INDUCE [152], where the pilot of the UAV can be verified before the authorised operation of the UAV through this method.

These use cases arose the need for face verification algorithms that can perform accurately with video feeds from UAVs. This means at far distances from the person and therefore low-pixel faces. Moreover, the UAVs would have to verify in environmental challenges conditions such as poor lighting for outdoor and late evenings operations and also fast-changing poses and positions to the target. Unfortunately, there is a serious gap in the literature on face verification at far distances from UAVs. Thus, this paper analyses different state-of-the-art

face verification algorithms and compares the three best ones. For this purpose, their accuracy and inference time is going to be compared using a dataset with UAV-recorded videos.

The main contribution of this research is an empirical comparison of three state-of-the-art face verification algorithms for a UAV-based use case. A dataset containing videos recorded from a UAV has been created for this comparison. The videos have been recorded from four different distances to analyse how these algorithms behave as the person to be verified is further away. The inference time of the face verification algorithm is also analysed to be able to do a precise accuracy/inference time comparison. This will allow us to analyse whether the face verification algorithms are optimal for UAV-based use cases. In summary, the main contributions of this study are as follows:

- Design and implementation of a face verification pipeline to conduct the experiments in similar conditions.
- Creation of a UAV recorded dataset for comparison of three state-of-the-art face verification algorithms.
- An empirical analysis of the inference time and similarity indexes obtained for four different distances using three state-of-the-art face verification algorithms.
- A comparison of the inference time in a face verification pipeline using three state-of-the-art algorithms.
- An empirical comparison among three state-of-the-art face verification algorithms, leading to practical recommendations of their applicability in UAV-based use cases.

The remainder of this paper is as follows: section II reviews the state-of-the-art face verification algorithms and explains why those three have been selected. Section III shows the experimental setup to carry out the experiments. Experiments and results are shown and discussed in section IV. Concluding remarks are given in section V.

Table A.1: Comparative between different Face Verification State-of-the-Art algorithms

Ref	Algorithm	Input Size	Output Size	Verification	Accuracy	Training Images
				on LFW dataset [57]	on YTF dataset [58]	
[67]	<i>Human-beings</i>	NA	NA	97.53%	Not given	NA
[68]	Deep-Face	152x152x3	4096	97.35%	91.40%	4.4M
[69]	OpenFace	96x96x3	128	92.92%	Not given	0.5M
[70]	VGG-Face	224x224x3	2622	98.95%	97.30%	2.6M
[71]	CosFace	112x96x3	Not given	99.73%	97.60%	5M
[72]	DeepID2	55x47x3	160	99.53%	93.20%	0.2M
[73]	ArcFace	112x112x3	512	99.83%	98.02%	5.8M
[74]	FaceNet	160x160x3	128	98.87%	95.12%	200M
[75]	FaceNet512	160x160x3	512	99.60%	Not given	200M
[76]	Dlib	150x150x3	128	99.38%	Not given	3M
[77]	SphereFace	112x96x3	512	99.42%	95.00%	0.5M

A.2 Related work

UAVs are a technology whose use is increasing exponentially. They are making it easier to perform previously difficult tasks. For instance, now UAVs can detect lost people in the forest from the sky whereas before it had to be done by helicopter with the cost that this entailed [157] [158].

Some papers explore the use of UAVs to perform face verification tasks. They usually use simple algorithms that do not have great accuracy but they are fast, such as LBPH (Local binary patterns histograms) [64] which was developed in 1996. Most of these algorithms are used because of their small capabilities needed to execute them as the system is embedded in the UAV. However, suppose a high-speed connection is made between a Ground Control Station (GCS) and the UAV. In that case, high-performance algorithms can be used as they will be executed in the GCS and the UAV will only transmit the video. The UAV can be connected to the GCS, for instance, via a 5G connection [159] which also allows controlling the UAV with Beyond Visual Line of Sight (BVLOS) flights.

Moreover, previous studies have explored the impact of distance and height on the accuracy of face recognition algorithms using an UAV [65]. Another line of research has performed face recognition and distance estimation from UAVs using a siamese network with a ResNet v1 architecture [46]. Furthermore, the architectures ResNet-50 and SENet have been compared for face recognition on UAVs [66].

Table A.1 shows a comparison between different state-of-the-art face verification algorithms. Different parameters are compared such as the input and output size of the neural network, and the number of images used for training. Also, the verification performance is going to be compared using two different datasets: Labeled Faces in the Wild (LFW) [57] and Youtube Faces (YTF) [58].

The first row of the table shows the human performance on the LFW dataset which is a 97.53% [67]. This value is going to be used to have a first reference of how good an algorithm is. Only two algorithms of the table do not surpass the verification performance of human beings on the LFW dataset: DeepFace [68] achieving a close 97.35% and OpenFace [69] that is far with only a 92.92%. The rest of the algorithms surpass the human-beings verification performance.

The ones that perform the best in this dataset are CosFace [71] (99.73%), DeepID2 [72] (99.53%), ArcFace [73] (99.83%) and FaceNet512 [75] (99.60%), all of them achieving more than 99.5%. On the other hand, not all algorithms have been evaluated using the YTF dataset, therefore not all the values are on the table. ArcFace (98.02%), CosFace (97.60%) and VGG-Face [70] (97.30%) have the best verification performance on this dataset.

Both FaceNet algorithms have been trained with the biggest number of images (200 million). The difference is that FaceNet512 [75] is an extended version of FaceNet [74] that has a 512 vector as output instead of 128, increasing the verification performance as can be seen in the table.

For the purpose of this research, three algorithms of table A.1 have been selected to perform an analysis on UAV-based use cases: ArcFace [73], VGG-Face [70] and FaceNet512 [75]. They have been chosen due to the good verification performance they have on the LFW and the YTF dataset. Also, they have all surpassed the human-being verification performance on LFW.

Furthermore, many metrics can be used to calculate the similarity indexes between two faces, such as euclidean distance, Manhattan distance, and cosine distance. This paper is going to use the last one. It is one of the most used in the literature as it is able to show the similarity of two vectors more accurately. Cosine distance is calculated as follows:

$$CD(\vec{x}, \vec{y}) = 1 - \frac{\sum_1^n x_i y_i}{\sqrt{\sum_1^n x_i^2} \sqrt{\sum_1^n y_i^2}}$$

Where x and y are the features vector of two different faces. And the result of the calculation is the similarity index between them.

A.3 Experimental setup

A.3.1 Dataset

There is a lack of datasets that meet the requirements of our case (Drone Guard Angel), which focuses on verifying a person standing and looking at the UAV. In the literature, there is a limited number of datasets available for face verification with UAVs. However, these datasets are not suitable for our research for different factors such as lack of different ethnicities, videos not recorded using UAVs, or a limited number of faces. For instance, the DroneSurf dataset [30], while comprehensive and useful for face recognition in surveillance applications, does not meet the specific requirements of our use case. Moreover, our use case needs close images of each person to be verified as that picture needs to be compared with the ones from the UAV to perform the face verification. This dataset will not be released due to data protection constraints, as the authorisation of the volunteers was only given for this conference study.

Therefore, a new dataset of UAV-recorded humans has been created for this conference. It was created using a DJI Mini 2 drone and includes videos of 20 volunteer individuals of different ethnicities. The volunteers have been recorded at four different distances: 5, 7, 10, and 15 meters. These distances were selected first to be at a safe distance from the volunteer to record the videos. And also, to not be excessively far to not be able to detect the face using the RetinaFace [119] face detection algorithm. The recording angle is 30 degrees so that they did not have to raise their head excessively and maintain an optimal height for the UAV. Each video recorded lasts 30 seconds, during which the volunteer was asked to make different head movements to acquire a comprehensive range of data on different facial angles. The

videos have a resolution of 4K (3840x2160) and are captured at 30 Frames per second (FPS). Moreover, the dataset also contains a close image of each volunteer to be able to compare it with the faces from the videos to perform the face verification. Fig. A.1 shows one example of a cropped face from our dataset and each of the distances - 5, 7, 10 and 15 meters.

Figure A.1: Example of a cropped face at the four distances recorded in the dataset

A.3.2 Design of the pipeline

One of the main contributions is the design and implementation of a pipeline presented in Fig. A.2. As input, it has two images. The first one is a frame of a video recorded from a UAV obtained from our dataset videos. The second input is the face of the person we want to verify. This image has been obtained from a phone at a close distance. The output of our pipeline is the similarity index between the face of the person to verify and the faces in the video frame. It is divided into four stages as follows:

1. **Face Detection:** This is the first stage of our pipeline. The face detection algorithm used is RetinaFace as it has the best accuracy while detecting at long distances. On the other hand, it is not a fast algorithm compared to other face detection ones. But as the purpose of this study is to compare only the face verification algorithms this is not a problem. RetinaFace receives as input an image and provides the coordinates of every face in it and the accuracy of the detection.
2. **Preprocessing:** It is divided into two steps. The first one crops the face from the image using the coordinates provided by RetinaFace. Then the face is resized to the input

Figure A.2: Pipeline used to obtain the results from the experiments. It is divided into four stages: face detection, preprocessing, siamese network, and similarity index calculation.

size required by the face verification algorithm. The input size varies depending on the algorithm as shown in Table A.1. As the ratio of the input size is not going to be usually the same as the face, it is needed to apply padding to that image. Therefore, black pixels are included to reach the expected input size maintaining the image ratio. This ensures that the face is not distorted.

3. **Siamese Network [68] [160]:** They have been used by several authors in the literature to perform face verifications. A siamese network is composed of two Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) that have the same architecture and weights. If the input of both CNNs is the same, the output will also be the same. The input of each CNN is a face sized as the input size requested. The output will be the features of that face. These features are a vector of different dimensions depending on the algorithm used that represents the characteristics of that face.
4. **Similarity index calculation:** It is the last stage of the pipeline. It receives the features of both faces from the siamese network and calculates its similarity index. It is obtained by calculating the cosine distance between them as seen in the previous section. Thus, if we obtain a similarity index of 0 means that the faces are exactly alike while if the result is 2 means that the two faces are opposite.

A.3.3 Implementation

The results have been obtained using a common framework where all three face verification algorithms are implemented. The implemented framework is referred to as DeepFace [130] [131] and includes the three face verification algorithms, RetinaFace for face detection and cosine distance to calculate the similarity indexes. Evaluating all the algorithms on the same platform allows us to obtain reliable results to be compared as they have been obtained under the same conditions.

DeepFace has been run on Python version 3.8. It is powered mainly by Keras [161]. Also, the Python library OpenCV has been used for the preprocessing and postprocessing of the images. It has been executed on a computer with Focal Ubuntu version 20.04.3.

The pipeline has been implemented and executed using the three state-of-the-art face verification algorithms on the same testbed for evaluation and comparison purposes using the mentioned framework. The algorithms are going to be executed in a high-performance GPU for comparison. Thus, it can be simulated that the video is sent from the UAV to a high-performance GPU server for the execution of the pipeline.

A.4 Experiments and results

A.4.1 Testbed Description

The experiments have been carried out on a NVIDIA GeForce GTX TITAN X with 12GB of onboard memory. These experiments have been repeated 10 times to obtain the final results. The UAV used to record the dataset is a DJI Mini 2 that has a 4K camera (3840x2160 px) at 30 FPS.

A.4.2 Comparative

The three face verification algorithms will be compared using two metrics - inference time, and the similarity index distribution for positive and negative pairs - at four different fixed distances.

Inference time

It is defined as the time it takes for one frame to complete a full pipeline execution. The inference time can be divided into four stages, the same as the processing pipeline. This is useful to compare only the face verification algorithms' inference time and not the whole pipeline.

Table A.2: Pipeline inference time comparison of each face verification algorithm

Algorithm	ArcFace	FaceNet512	VGG-Face
Times	230 ms	240 ms	280 ms

1. **Face Detection:** Using the RetinaFace algorithm it takes around 165 ms to perform the face detection. Using another faster face detection algorithm, the inference time of the pipeline can be reduced greatly. This stage is the slowest in the pipeline.
2. **Preprocessing:** The time is independent of the face detection or verification algorithms used. This stage only takes 0.3 ms to run. It is the fastest of the four stages.
3. **Siamese Network:** Only the time it takes to obtain the features of the face from the video is taken into account. This is because the features of the image of the person to be verified are obtained at the beginning of the video and are not recalculated to accelerate the process. As the image is the same throughout the video, the same results are obtained as if they have been calculated for each frame. The time this stage takes depends on the algorithm used, as Table A.2 reflects.
4. **Distance calculation:** The last stage is also independent of the algorithms used. Using cosine distance as a metric it takes around 1.4 ms.

All stages have fixed times independent of the face verification algorithm used except for the Siamese network. The time differences that can be seen in Table A.2 are exclusively due to which face verification algorithm is used. VGG-Face is by far the slowest face verification algorithm and ArcFace the fastest. All stages excluding the Siamese network take approximately 166.7 milliseconds. Therefore, the inference times of only the siamese

Figure A.3: Similarity indexes of the ArcFace face verification algorithm for 5, 7, 10 and 15 meters of distance

Figure A.4: Similarity indexes of the VGG-Face face verification algorithm for 5, 7, 10 and 15 meters of distance

network for the three face verification algorithms are VGG-Face 113.3 ms, FaceNet512 73.3 ms, and ArcFace 63.3 ms.

Similarity indexes distribution

The pipeline in the previous section has been used to obtain the similarity indexes of our dataset. They have been divided into two types: positive and negative pairs. The first ones are obtained by calculating the similarity index of two faces that belongs to the same person. The negative ones have been obtained using two faces that belong to two different people,

Figure A.5: Similarity indexes of the FaceNet512 face verification algorithm for 5, 7, 10, and 15 meters of distance

so the verification will be negative. The plots of both similarity indexes are shown in each graphic. The further apart the two plots are, the better the algorithm is because it will be able to perform verifications with fewer false positives and negatives. If the plots are overlapped, it will be difficult to differentiate between the positive and negative pairs so there will be a lot of false positives and negatives.

The plots have been obtained for each of the three face verification algorithms: ArcFace (Figure A.3), VGG-Face (Figure A.4) and FaceNet512 (Figure A.5). Four different distances (5, 7, 10, and 15 meters) have been used to see how the plots evolve depending on the distance. By looking at all the graphs it can be appreciated that as the distance increases, the plots shift to the right. The similarity indexes are higher because at a greater distance, the face images have less resolution, so they become less similar.

Let us focus first on the ArcFace graphs (Figure A.3). The 5 meters graph (Figure A.3a) shows both plots - positive and negative pairs - well separated. The negative pairs curve starts approximately at 0.6 while most positive pair similarity indexes are below this point. So at this distance, users can be verified with high accuracy. At 7 meters (Figure A.3b) and 10 meters (Figure A.3c) the plots are similar but shifted to the right. The negative pairs curve continues starting at 0.6, but the positive pairs have higher similarity indexes. Most of the similarity indexes are above 0.6, so it will be more difficult to correctly verify a person without false positives. Furthermore, the 15 meters graph (Figure A.3d) shows how both curves are almost completely overlapped. Thus, it will be difficult to perform face verifications correctly. Only a small part of the curve is not overlapped below 0.7. So if the similarity index is below this value we will be able to perform face verifications without any false positives, therefore, it can be a good value to establish the verification threshold.

VGG-Face (Figure A.4) obtains good results in graphs at 5 (Figure A.4a) and 7 meters (Figure A.4b) as the negative and positive pairs can be difference easily. At 10 meters (Figure A.4c) the curves are more overlapped but a significant part of the positive pair curve is still below the minimum negative pair similarity index. Therefore, most of the face verifications will be performed without any false positives by choosing an appropriate threshold. At 15

meters (Figure A.4d) the curves overlap a lot, so there will be many false positives and negatives regardless of the chosen threshold.

FaceNet512 is the one that achieves the best results (Figure A.5). The graphs at all distances are well separated so it can be easier to verify a person than the other algorithms. At 5 meters (Figure A.5a) most of the positive pair curve is below 0.5, which is the minimum negative pair similarity index, so almost all of the verifications will be performed correctly without false positives. Furthermore, at 7 (Figure A.5b) and 10 meters (Figure A.5c) the peak of the positive pairs is still below the minimum negative pair similarity index. At 15 meters (Figure A.5d) the curves are more overlapped but they can still be differentiated easily. Thus, there will be false positives but not as many as using the other face verification algorithms.

A.5 Concluding remarks

This study has presented a comparison using a novel created dataset designed for this concrete purpose. Three state-of-the-art face verification algorithms have been compared at four different distances (5, 7, 10, and 15 meters). Two metrics have been compared: the inference time processing a frame in the whole pipeline, and the distribution of their similarity indexes for both positive and negative pairs.

Based on this comparison, it is possible to conclude if the state-of-the-art face verification algorithms are optimal to perform face verifications in real-time from UAVs. ArcFace is a fast algorithm but it only achieves good results up to 10 meters of distance. On the other hand, FaceNet512 can verify correctly at all analyzed distances but it is slower than the previous one. Finally, VGG-Face is a slow algorithm so it is only recommended to be used when the speed is not important in the use case. Further work would involve choosing one of the previously compared algorithms to perform face verification on UAVs. The results and video will be transmitted to the user via a wireless network such as 5G.

Acknowledgments

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Appendix B

Edge-Accelerated UAV Operations: A Case Study of Open Source Solutions

Please note that this chapter contains a copy of content present in a research paper, and that, therefore, it has already been peer-reviewed and accepted.

Abstract

This study explores the execution of AI algorithms on open Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) equipped with BeagleBone AI-64 (BBAI-64) boards, comparing their performance to high-performance computers equipped with Graphics processing unit (GPU). Key factors are evaluated, such as inference time, end-to-end processing time, Central Processing Unit (CPU) usage, or temperature on the board. Furthermore, this study presents the development of an open UAV platform based on an open-source flight controller (Durandal) executing an open-source autopilot (ArduPilot). This platform facilitates the integration of various sensors or cameras, regardless of brand or communication protocol. The study's key findings show that the BBAI-64 offers advantages for smaller Artificial Intelligence (AI) models, and achieving comparable performance for larger models with high-performance computers. This work contributes to optimising AI execution on UAVs and supporting the development of versatile, sensor-agnostic open-source UAVs.

B.1 Introduction

Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have revolutionised a variety of industries by allowing autonomous and remote-controlled operations, such as search and rescue [157], delivery services, etc. in remote areas at a low cost. By incorporating artificial intelligence algorithms into UAV platforms, their capabilities have been further improved, allowing for tasks such as object detection, path planning, and collision avoidance. However, the deployment of these algorithms on UAVs presents unique difficulties due to limited resources, the requirement for real-time processing, and low power consumption.

Furthermore, edge processing has become crucial in recent years for several reasons. One is the need for security. For instance, if everything is executed inside the UAV it will be more difficult for security issues to arise, such as video interception or attacks to the board in the UAV as the video will not be transmitted to the ground. The execution of algorithms on the UAV will increase its execution speed and enable real-time decision-making on the UAV. One main new use case using Edge Processing can be the Drone Guard Angel for public safety escort services, as being developed in the EU H2020 ARCADIAN-IoT project that aims to create an innovative, advanced and solid framework for trust, security and privacy management for IoT systems.[9]. In this use case, the UAV will go to the position of the user who requested the service and will accompany the person home, ensuring that it arrives safely. By having the capability of executing image processing algorithms onboard the drone, the tracking of the person will be faster and more secure as the video will only be transmitted inside the drone.

The main contribution of this research is to compare an object detection algorithm executed in two different scenarios, with the results visualised in a Ground Control Station (GCS). The video will be acquired from the UAV for both scenarios. In the first scenario, the algorithm will be executed on a BeagleBone AI-64 (BBAI-64) board [106] inside the UAV, and the results will be sent to the GCS. In the second scenario, the video will be transmitted from the Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) to a PC, and the algorithm will be executed on a high-performance GPU. Then, the results will be visualised in the GCS executed on the same PC. Several parameters will be compared in this study, such as the inference time

of the algorithm in both devices and the end-to-end time for both scenarios. Additionally, some metrics of the BBAI-64 will be compared in both scenarios, including CPU usage or temperature.

Another significant contribution is the design, and development of an Open-UAV. This entails basing the UAV on an open-source flight controller, aiming to achieve a sensor-agnostic drone capable of integrating any sensor in the market, regardless of the brand or communication protocol. This flexibility allows the implementation of any message broker to communicate with the flight controller or the BBAI-64. In summary, the main contributions of this study are as follows.

- Design and implementation of an architecture for an Open-source UAV platform.
- Empirical comparison of the inference time of state-of-the-art object detection algorithms in two scenarios: Edge on a board in the UAV and core on a high-performance computer.
- Empirical comparison of other board parameters, like the CPU usage or temperature for both scenarios.

The remainder of this paper is as follows: Section II reviews state-of-the-art UAV platforms and the execution of algorithms on them. Section III shows the designed and implemented Open UAV platform. Experiments and results are shown and discussed in Section IV. Concluding remarks are given in Section V.

B.2 Related Work

Table B.1 shows a comparison of several papers performing Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms using UAV camera footage. Most of them use commercial-based UAVs from the brand DJI. For example, [162] uses the footage of a DJI Inspire 1 to execute object detection algorithms in a Smartphone. The same author in [163] performs person detection using a thermal camera with the algorithm executed in a Jetson AGX Xavier using footage from a

Table B.1: Comparison of UAV platforms and Edge Processing solutions

Ref	UAV Platform	Execution Platform	Edge Execution (UAV)	Camera Type	Algorithm	Objective
[162]	DJI Inspire 1	Smartphone	No	Optical	Object Detection	Common Objects
[163]	DJI Matrice 210	Jetson AGX Xavier	No	Thermal	Object Detection	People
[164]	DJI Tello	Jetson Nano	No	Optical	Object detection	Faces and Face masks
[165]	DJI Matrice 600	Jetson TK1	Yes	Hyperspectral	Image processing	Crops inspection
[166]	DJI Matrice 100	Odroid-XU4	Yes	Optical	Object Detection	Vehicles
[167]	Custom Open-UAV	Raspberry Pi 2	Yes	Optical	Decision Making	UAV path
Ours	Custom Open-UAV	BeagleBone AI-64	Yes	Optical	Object Detection	Common Objects

DJI Matrice 210. Other authors use a Jetson Nano to perform object detection algorithms with video footage from a DJI Tello drone [164]. All these authors send video footage from the drone and the execution of the algorithms is in the core. The computer or smartphone is not integrated into the drone.

On the other hand, some authors execute the algorithms on a computer onboard the drone. For example, [165] uses a Jetson TK1 to perform crop inspection using a hyperspectral camera on the drone. Another study [166] uses an Odroid-XU4 board to execute object detection algorithms to detect vehicles. The board is onboard a DJI Matrice 100 drone with an optical camera.

[167] is the only study that uses a custom Open-UAV to perform the algorithms. Onboard the drone there is a Raspberry Pi 2 that executes decision-making algorithms to control and move the UAV for obstacle avoidance.

As can be seen, most studies use commercial-based UAVs and there is a lack of studies regarding custom Open-UAVs. On the other side, some studies compare the execution of models in the edge, onboard a UAV's computer, versus at the core, on a ground-based computer receiving footage from the UAV [168, 169]. In this study, we contribute to this body of knowledge by introducing our work, which involves a custom Open-UAV integrated with a BBAI-64 for optical-based object detection.

In summary, the referenced works collectively demonstrate the wide-ranging applications of UAVs in combination with different execution platforms, camera technologies, and objectives. These prior studies provide valuable insights into the adaptability of UAVs and lay the foundation for the present investigation, which aims to expand our understanding of open UAV platforms and their edge processing capabilities compared with the core ones.

Figure B.1: Schematic of the architecture of the designed open UAV platform. It is divided into two main parts: the components inside the UAV and the external connections on the ground.

B.3 Experimental Setup - Open UAV platform

For this research, an open-source UAV platform has been designed and implemented, offering key benefits in enhanced customisation flexibility and cost-effectiveness. The platform's openness allows for the creation of a sensor-agnostic drone, capable of integrating sensors regardless of brand or communication protocol. Moreover, it provides a low-cost alternative to state-of-the-art UAVs from major brands like DJI and Parrot, delivering comparable functionalities at a fraction of the cost. In this section, the architecture and its implementation will be explained.

B.3.1 Architecture Design

The designed architecture can be seen in Fig. B.1. The UAV is composed of six main sections explained as follows:

1. Video TX AI Processing: This section is responsible for receiving video input from a USB Camera, processing it using the designated AI algorithm and transmitting the processed video to the GCS using the board BBAI-64. It can also transmit the video

from the camera directly to the GCS without executing any AI algorithm. It can connect to the GCS via 4G, WIFI, or Ethernet for testing on the ground. If necessary, the video streaming could be encrypted for enhanced security transmission.

2. **Motors:** Comprising the Electronic Speed Controllers (ESC) and the motors, this section enables the UAV to lift off from the ground or land and enables its movement.
3. **Power:** The power section encompasses the battery/batteries and two power distributors: the Power Distribution Board (PDB) and the Power Distribution Drone (PDD). It ensures that all components inside the UAV are supplied with sufficient power for optimal functionality and with adequate voltage.
4. **UAV Control:** Serving as the central intelligence unit of the UAV, this section includes the Global Positioning System (GPS) module, which provides precise location information for the UAV. The flight controller receives and processes all relevant information, dispatching appropriate commands to each component. The X8R receiver receives input from the joystick, conveying the pilot's desired movements, while the telemetry module gathers essential data (such as battery status, location, speed, etc.) from the flight controller and transmits it to the GCS for real-time monitoring by the operator.
5. **First-Person View (FPV) Transmitter (FPV TX):** This section is responsible for acquiring and transmitting the FPV video feed to the pilot on the ground, enabling easier control and navigation of the UAV.

As can be seen in the schematic (Fig. B.1), three interfaces connect the ground devices with the UAV to receive and send information such as video, telemetry, etc:

1. **Ground Control Station (GCS):** The program QGroundControl [114] is used. UAVs can connect and send telemetry that can be seen on the display along with its position on a map. It can also receive video.
2. **Joystick:** It is controlled by the pilot who sends movement commands to the UAV, receiving telemetry information, like battery status, altitude, speed, etc.

3. First-Person Video Receiver (FPV RX): It receives FPV from the UAV and shows it on a display so the pilot can fly more easily visualising real-time video.

(a) Deployed open UAV platform indoors.

(b) Open UAV flying in an open field while performing the experiments.

Figure B.2: Pictures of the developed open UAV platform

B.3.2 Architecture Implementation

After the design of the architecture, the UAV has been implemented based on it. A commercial hexacopter frame has been used: Tarot X6. The flight controller used is Durandal from the brand Holybro as well as the GPS receiver and the telemetry radio. ArduPilot, an open-source autopilot system, is used to control the UAV. Fig. B.2 shows the built open-UAV platform in two scenarios: Fig. B.2a shows the open UAV completely deployed indoors and Fig. B.2b shows the UAV flying while performing the experiments.

B.4 Experiments and results

In this section, the results of the experiments performed are explained along with the description of the testbed used for them.

Figure B.3: Pipeline of the execution for both scenarios: Algorithms executed in the BBAI-64 and executed in the PC receiving the video from the UAV via the BBAI-64.

B.4.1 Testbed description

The testbed is composed of two different scenarios, as seen in Fig. B.3.

1. Scenario 1: In the first scenario, the models will be executed in the BBAI-64. It will obtain the video from the camera in the UAV and decode it. Then, the AI algorithms will be executed using its frames, and the video with the detections will be encoded again. It will be sent to the computer where it will be decoded and visualised in the GCS.
2. Scenario 2: In the second scenario, the BBAI-64 will get the video feed from the camera and send it to the computer. The video will be received, decoded and processed with the AI models. Then the video with the detections will be encoded again and visualised in the GCS.

The same three algorithms are going to be used. However, they require modifications in order to be onboarded on the BBAI-64 as will be explained.

Object Detection Algorithms

The algorithm selected is YOLOv5 [170] trained in the COCO dataset [171]. As shown in Table B.2, three different versions have been used. The differences between them are two hyperparameters: model depth multiple and layer channel multiple. The first one determines the overall depth in the YOLOv5 model, whereas the second one controls the width of the layer. Therefore, using lower values of these multiples, lighter models can be obtained. All models have an input size of 640 pixels. The term GFLOPs, which stands for Giga Floating-point Operations, quantifies the number of floating-point operations necessary to execute a single instance of the model. It is used to measure the computational complexity of models.

Table B.2: Comparison of the three models executed in the computer

Algorithm	Model depth	Layer channel	GFLOPs	mAP 50%
YOLOv5_s6	0.33	0.5	17.4	56.8
YOLOv5_m6	0.67	0.75	52.4	63.6
YOLOv5_l6	1	1	117.7	67.0

These models have been used in the computer. However, to onboard the models in the BBAI-64 some modifications are needed. The names of these models have been modified to differentiate them from the previous ones by adding *ti_lite*, as it is a lighter model created by Texas Instruments (TI). These lighter models have two main differences with the previous ones: [172]

1. The SiLU activation is replaced with ReLu as the first one is not suitable for embedded devices, as SiLu is less quantization-friendly than the ReLu activation function.
2. The first layer of YOLOv5 is a Focus layer, created specifically for this, however, the slice operations in this layer are not suitable for embedded models. Therefore, for the BBAI-64, this layer is replaced by a light-weight convolution layer. [173]

As it can be seen in Table B.3, the models lose less than 1.5% of accuracy with the changes, whereas the GFLOPs are almost equivalent. Therefore, the models will have a similar accuracy while executed on the computer or in the BBAI-64.

Table B.3: Comparison of the three models executed in the BeagleBone AI-64

Algorithm	Input Size	GFLOPs	mAP 50%
YOLOv5_s6_ti_lite	640x640	17.48	56.0
YOLOv5_m6_ti_lite	640x640	52.5	62.9
YOLOv5_l6_ti_lite	640x640	117.84	65.6

Devices

Depending on the scenario, the object detection algorithm will be executed on two different devices. One device is the BeagleBone AI-64 embedded in the Open UAV platform. It has several hardware accelerator devices allowing high-speed inference in this constraint device. For example, it has a C7x Digital Signal Processor (DSP) where the models are executed. Furthermore, other functions are executed in the R5F cores. Its current is also limited to 3A, which is important in a UAV where battery consumption is crucial. The average current consumption of the open UAV while flying is 55A, therefore, the use of the BBAI-64 will only increase the consumption by 5%.

In the PC, the algorithm has been executed in an NVIDIA GeForce GTX TITAN X with 12GB of onboard memory. Both devices were connected via WIFI using a HUAWEI E8372 4G single plugged into the BBAI-64.

B.4.2 Results

Four different metrics are going to be evaluated to compare both scenarios: the temperature and CPU usage of the BBAI-64, the inference time of the models and the end-to-end time.

Board temperature

The temperature of the BBAI-64 is going to be analysed in two different areas: the R5F cores and the C7x DSP. The analysis of board temperature is crucial because elevated temperatures can negatively impact the speed performance of the models. Higher temperatures may lead to a slowdown in the CPU, resulting in increased algorithm inference times. Conversely, lower temperatures facilitate the execution of the processes at a faster rate. The temperature will be

Figure B.4: Temperature in the Arm Cortex-R5F MCUs for the two different scenarios.

obtained for the two scenarios. In the first one, the values for the three algorithms executed are obtained. However, for the second scenario, only one plot is shown as the BBAI-64 only sends video to the computer, independently of the algorithm executed there.

Fig. B.4 shows the temperature for the R5F cores. The four plots have different starting values as they depend on the initial state of the board. Therefore, the important value is the last one as it is where the value tends towards. As can be seen in the second scenario, the temperature stays constant at a low value of around 62 degrees. However, in scenario 1 for the three algorithms, the temperature increases significantly. As expected, the YOLOv5_l6 algorithm has the highest temperature, as it is the largest model, achieving almost 78 degrees. YOLOv5_m6 achieves a temperature of around 75 degrees and YOLOv5_s6 71 degrees.

Fig B.5 shows the same graph but for the temperature in the C7x DSP, where the AI algorithms are executed. The shape of the plots is the same as before, but the values are higher. YOLOv5_l6 algorithm rises to 81 degrees, YOLOv5_m6 to 79 degrees and YOLOv5_s6 to 73 degrees. The temperature in scenario 2 remains constant again at the value of 62 degrees.

Figure B.5: Temperature in the C7x DSP for the two different scenarios.

CPU usage

The analysis of CPU usage is crucial as it shows how possible is to run other processes in parallel with the AI algorithm. These additional processes may encompass a navigation system, obstacle avoidance, or telemetry router. Fig. B.6 presents the CPU usage of the BBAI-64 while executing the three algorithms for scenario 1 and while transmitting video for scenario 2. As can be seen, the CPU usage for scenario 2 is really low because no decoding/encoding is needed for transmitting video. Therefore, in scenario 2, other algorithms or programs can be executed on the board while transmitting the video.

In scenario 1, the algorithms YOLOv5_s6 and YOLOv5_m6 have similar CPU usage as shown in the figure, whilst YOLOv5_l6 appears to have a lower one.

Table B.4 shows the average CPU usage for the four cases. As seen in the figure, scenario 2 has a low CPU usage of 4.36%. YOLOv5_s6 and YOLOv5_m6 have similar values of CPU usage of 139% and 137% respectively. YOLOv5_l6 has a lower CPU usage of 117%. This lower CPU usage for a heavier model can be due to its optimisation. As the other models are a scaled version of YOLOv5_l6, they are not as optimised as this one. The elevated

Figure B.6: CPU usage in the BeagleBone AI-64 for the two different scenarios.

Table B.4: Comparison of the CPU usage in the BeagleBone AI-64 on both scenarios for the three algorithms

Scenario	Average CPU usage
Scenario 1 - YOLOv5_s6_ti_lite	139.16%
Scenario 1 - YOLOv5_m6_ti_lite	137.35%
Scenario 1 - YOLOv5_l6_ti_lite	117.21%
Scenario 2	4.36%

CPU usage values might impede the execution of additional high-requiring commands on the BBAI-64. However, additional tasks requiring low CPU usage, such as a MAVLink router redirecting drone status messages to the GCS, can be executed.

Inference time

The inference time for the three algorithms in both scenarios is analysed. It is important to note that in the BBAI-64, the executed algorithms slightly differ from those on the computer, as they require modifications for embedding, as discussed in previous sections.

Fig. B.7 shows the cumulative average of the inference time for the three algorithms in both scenarios. Additionally, Table B.5 presents the average inference times. As can be

Figure B.7: Cumulative average inference time of the models in both scenarios.

seen, the algorithms executed in the computer are faster than in the BBAI-64. The difference diminishes as the model becomes lighter. For example, for YOLOv5_s6 the gap between execution in the computer and the BBAI-64 is only 1 ms. However, for YOLOv5_m6 the difference increases to 10 ms and with a heavy model like YOLOv5_l6, the difference reaches 30 ms. Furthermore, there is a noticeable rise in inference time on the BBAI-64, likely attributed to the progressive increase in board temperature over time. Implementing cooling measures could potentially enhance model speed.

Table B.5: Comparison of the average inference time for the three algorithms executed in both platforms: PC and the BeagleBone AI-64

Algorithm	Scenario 1 - BBAI-64	Scenario 2 - Computer
YOLOv5_s6	13.30 ms	12.03 ms
YOLOv5_m6	26.48 ms	16.27 ms
YOLOv5_l6	58.08 ms	27.10 ms

This shows that larger models are going to be more suitable for computers with high-spec GPUs due to the requirements. However, for lighter models, an embedded board can execute it as fast as a computer.

End-to-end time

The end-to-end time, as defined in our scenarios, represents the duration from the moment a frame is captured by the camera until it is displayed in the GCS. It is the total system delay. Table B.6 presents the end-to-end time for the three algorithms in both scenarios. As can be seen, the time is lower for the three algorithms when executed in the BBAI-64. The difference is more pronounced with heavier models. For example, for YOLOv5_s6 the difference is nearly 500 ms, while for YOLOv5_m6, the gap narrows to around 50 ms.

Table B.6: Comparison of the end-to-end time for the three algorithms executed in both platforms: PC and the BeagleBone AI-64

Algorithm	Scenario 1	Scenario 2
YOLOv5_s6	0.571 s	1.091 s
YOLOv5_m6	0.684 s	1.145 s
YOLOv5_l6	1.102 s	1.154 s

The main difference in the times is attributed to the decoding and encoding of the video. The BBAI-64 is equipped with dedicated hardware for these tasks, resulting in faster performance compared to the execution on the computer.

B.5 Concluding remarks

This research has presented a novel architecture of an open-UAV platform. Subsequently, this platform was built to conduct a comparative analysis between the execution of the AI algorithms in the UAV and on a computer. The models in the UAV are executed on a BeagleBone AI-64 board, which is the same board used for transmitting video to the computer.

The study concludes that for lightweight models, executing them on the BBAI-64 offers a significant advantage. However, when running larger models, the speed and accuracy are similar for both systems. It is important to note that when referring to 'large models', we are specifically talking about models that are large in the context of the BeagleBone AI-64, as

the computer can handle even more substantial models that cannot be accommodated on our board. For our comparison, almost identical algorithms were used on both devices.

Furthermore, this research has underscored the significance of having an open-source UAV platform and the myriad possibilities it opens for future experiments. It enables the integration of any sensor or camera available in the market, creating a brand-agnostic platform.

In scenarios with limited bandwidth, transmitting video to the GCS may not be feasible. Hence, for future work, it would be preferable to transmit only the GPS location of the detections and display on the GCS map. To achieve this, a novel algorithm to calculate the GPS coordinates using the detections on a frame is required.

Acknowledgment

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Appendix C

Efficient CNN-based Low-Resolution Facial Detection from UAVs

Please note that this chapter contains a copy of content present in the research paper [3], and that, therefore, it has already been peer-reviewed and accepted.

Abstract

Face detection in UAV imagery requires high accuracy and low execution time for real-time mission-critical operations in public safety, emergency management, disaster relief and other applications. This study presents UWS-YOLO, a new Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) based machine learning algorithm designed to address these demanding requirements. UWS-YOLO's key strengths lie in its exceptional speed, remarkable accuracy, and ability to handle complex UAV operations. This algorithm presents a balanced and portable solution for real-time face detection in UAV applications. Evaluation and comparison with the state-of-the-art algorithms using standard and UAV-specific datasets demonstrate UWS-YOLO's superiority. It achieves 59.29% of accuracy compared with 27.43% in a state-of-the-art solution RetinaFace and 46.59% with YOLOv7. Additionally, UWS-YOLO operates at 11 milliseconds, which is 345% faster than RetinaFace and 373% than YOLOv7.

C.1 Introduction

Detecting and tracking down people on the ground from a drone or Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) is critical for a myriad of applications such as remote monitoring and surveillance, search and rescue to find missing people [157, 158], people counting in dense crowds, emergency and vigilance (e.g., the Drone Guard Angel in the EU H2020 project ARCADIAN-IoT) and public safety (e.g., surveillance application in the EU H2020 project 5G-INDUCE) [174]. Face detection is an active research area in the field of computer vision to identify specific individuals. It is the first step to develop a robust facial recognition system by detecting and locating the human face from the obtained image. Automatic face detection system plays a vital role in face identification, facial expression recognition, head-pose estimation and human–computer interaction among others [33]. Although there has been a lot of research conducted on facial detection, there are still several issues to be addressed owing to various challenging operational conditions being involved in facial detection from drones including a high degree of variability, distance from the camera, face orientation, illumination, face occlusion, complex backgrounds, low resolution to name a few. These challenges have a detrimental effect on the detection rate and accuracy of the detection [33].

In addition, most of the research work is just focused on accomplishing the task of detecting faces in the scene with high accuracy. Nevertheless, the complete use case when follow-up tasks are executed is not generally considered in the research community. Fig. C.1 presents a typical example of a flowchart in order to perform some of the mentioned follow-up tasks, such as face identification, expression recognition and head pose estimation. These tasks are computationally expensive and thus, their inference time is high. Therefore, the face detection task should be fast and light, in order to allow other tasks to provide results close to real-time. This research is focused on improving the inference time in the face detection stage.

Although having a low execution time is mandatory for the success of different use cases, developing and executing a low computationally expensive algorithm is key to reduce the required amount of memory needed from the GPU (Graphics Processing Unit). Current

Figure C.1: Flowchart with examples of the use of face detection with follow-up tasks with their average inference time.

research work should focus on lowering the rate of operations per second to allow other algorithms to perform in parallel in the same GPU.

The aim of this study is to create a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) specifically designed for deployment with Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS). The CNN targets for a trade-off among accuracy, speed and portability. The solution should achieve high accuracy able to detect small faces within large images even if the faces consist of only a few pixels. In addition, in order to overcome the highlighted challenges, the CNN is optimised in terms of speed to achieve an execution time beyond real-time (faster than 30 frames per second). Finally, this algorithm is power-efficient with low computational demands. As a result, our contributions are summarised as follows:

- Up-to-date literature review on face detection techniques and their limitations.
- Design and implementation of a novel CNN-based algorithm (UWS-YOLO) to perform facial detection from a UAV.
- Creation, processing and labelling of a new dataset with people's faces recorded from a UAV at different distances.

- Performing qualitative and quantitative evaluation, and comparison with state-of-the-art algorithms (RetinaFace and YOLOv7) in terms of performance.

The organisation of the paper is as follows: Section 2 reviews the related work. Section 3 describes the design of the proposed solution to perform facial detection, followed by the implementation setup in Section 4. Section 5 presents the results of the proposed solution. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

C.2 Related work

The aim of this section is to explain the techniques used in this paper. In addition, it reviews state-of-the-art work related to facial detection.

C.2.1 Machine learning techniques

The methods commonly used to detect faces from images or videos are divided into two main categories: feature-based and image-based approaches. The feature-based approaches such as Viola-Jones[31] and Gabor features-based methods [32] focus on extracting main facial features which result in sub-optical facial detection [33]. These methods are fast but fail when the detections are from different angles and lighting conditions [34]. Image-based approaches including deep convolutional neural networks have inspired face detection in recent years. There are two categories for CNN-based face detectors, region-based (two-stage) and single-stage methods. Fast RCNN [35], Faster RCNN [36], and R-FCN [37] are common region-based methods. They have achieved high accuracy at the cost of speed. The single-stage methods including YOLO series [38–40], and SSD (Single-Shot Detector) [41] have achieved high inference time but lower accuracy compared to two-stage approaches. RetinaFace [42] using Resnet-152 as backbone achieves great accuracy but has a high inference time while processing HD (1920×1080) or 4k (4096×2160) images.

C.2.2 Advanced network configurations

The aforementioned single-stage CNNs may be configured in order to achieve higher accuracy for low-pixel size object detection. Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP) and Path Aggregation Network (PAN) are two advanced techniques that keep the small features extracted in the preliminary CNN's layers to increase the accuracy at almost no cost in execution speed.

Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP)

The SPP [123] uses large max poolings to improve the receptive field and consequently increases the accuracy of the architecture. It is robust to object deformation and carries out information cumulation at a deeper stage of the neural network. To increase the receptive field and get better accuracy, the strides in the SPP module were changed to 7x7, 10x10 and 13x13 in the backbone of the proposed architecture.

Path Aggregation Network (PAN)

PAN is a method for the improvement of the detection of small objects. To achieve this, the features of the top layers with more information are combined with the deeper layers with more shallow features [124]. In this study, the PAN architecture was modified using an additional up-sampling to keep more meaningful information which is essential for the detection of small objects.

C.2.3 Facial detection

This subsection compares state-of-the-art facial detection results with the proposed approach in this article. The results have been obtained from the papers of each algorithm. Table C.1 shows the comparative analysis.

In one study, [43] proposed a face detection technique implemented on a Raspberry Pi. Haar cascade classifier algorithm was implemented using OpenCV [54]. The Droneface dataset [55] was used as the facial image dataset. Although high accuracy was obtained (98%, 93%, 86% and 80%) for distances of 1.5, 3, 4 and 5 meters respectively, the detections

were not tested from an altitude of more than 5m. In addition, the speed of the model has not been reported. In another study, [44] proposed an enhanced YOLOv3 algorithm for face detection being comparable with YOLOv3 and YOLOv4. The Mean average precision (mAP) of 51.9% was achieved using WIDER FACE dataset [23] which is less than our model with mAP of 72.26%. The speed of the model has not also been reported.

In [34], a fast customised CNN was implemented suitable for UAV use cases. In [45] and [46], although high performance has been achieved for face detection and identification, they are not fast enough for our use case and they have been tested up to a distance of 10 m. In [48], a Mobilenet-SSD was implemented in TensorFlow for facial detection, Although very high accuracy was obtained (91.92%), the algorithm was not tested on the drone. In another study [47], YOLOv3 was implemented on Raspberry Pi for facial detection. This study is slow for our use case (6.7 frames per second) and has been tested at a distance of 3.8m. In [49], LBP Histogram (LBPH) was used as a face recogniser for anti-theft and surveillance applications. Although it has obtained a high accuracy of 89.1%, the speed and the distance have not been reported.

In [50] a high accuracy is achieved in the WIDER FACE dataset but without specifying what input size was used to obtain this accuracy. Moreover, it achieves almost real-time inference speed being close to 30 Frames per second (FPS) which is slower than our model (91 FPS). In [51] and [53] a high accuracy is achieved in the WIDER FACE dataset but the inference time has not been reported. In [52] a modification of RetinaNet to improve accuracy and speed is presented. However, our model achieves better results in terms of accuracy and inference time in the WIDER FACE dataset.

In summary, current literature does not consider deeply the challenges involved in facial detection from UAVs including altitude, illumination, and face orientation among others and the models used in these studies are computationally expensive. However, our proposed solution reduces the computational power to make it more suitable for portable, resource-constrained devices.

Table C.1: Comparison of Facial detection solutions

Ref.	Algorithm	Exec Env.	Platform	Accuracy	Speed (FPS)	Model size	Distance
[43]	Haar cascade	RPi	OpenCV	98.00%	NG	NG	Up to 5 m
[44]	Enhanced YOLOv3	PC	Darknet	51.90%	NG	NG	WF distance
[34]	Customised CNN	PC	Caffe	77.40%*	31.0	NG	WF distance
[45]	LSTM	PC	NG	99.20%	00.7	NG	3 m - 6 m
[46]	SVM	PC	OpenCV	97.50%	13.0	NG	2 m - 10 m
[47]	YOLOv3	RPi	NG	NG	06.7	NG	3.8 m
[48]	Mobilenet-SSD	PC	Tensorflow	91.92%	39.0	NG	NG
[49]	LBPH	RPi	NG	89.10%	NG	NG	NG
[50]	IRNet	PC	PyTorch	76.60%	31.3	1.68MB	WF distance
[51]	Enhanced YOLOX	PC	PyTorch	87.38%	NG	NG	WF distance
[52]	Enhanced RetinaNet	PC	PyTorch	41.00%	11.8	NG	WF distance
[53]	EfficientFace	PC	PyTorch	90.10%	NG	NG	WF distance
TP	UWS-YOLO	PC	Darknet	59.29%	91.0	49MB	2 m - 30 m

TP = This Paper; NG = Not Given; RPi = Raspberry Pi; WF = WIDER FACE; *=Recall

C.3 Design of the proposed algorithm

The proposed algorithm is designed to strike a balance between accuracy, speed and portability. The UWS-YOLO integrates three key components to create an effective solution for face detection. First, a robust Backbone architecture to achieve high accuracy, followed up by an SPP module with modified strides of 7, 10 and 13 in the max-poolings. Finally, an enhanced PAN to increase the accuracy for small object detection. Fig. C.2 presents the architecture of the proposed solution combining all the techniques implemented.

C.3.1 The backbone

The baseline of the proposed solution is the Tiny-YOLOv4 [121] backbone whose main strength is the low execution speed (4ms). This backbone serves as the foundation of the UWS-YOLO algorithm, nevertheless, its main flaw is the low accuracy that it presents. Our solution includes Cross-Stage Partial Networks (CSPBlock) modules which replace the ResBlock module in the residual network (marked as a). CSPBlocks [122] were chosen in order to improve the correlation difference of gradient information and enhance the learning

Figure C.2: The architecture of UWS-YOLO face detector.

ability of the convolution network. The feature maps are divided into two branches to apply different transformations and then concatenated back together. UWS-YOLO includes three CSPBlock modules with 64, 128 and 256 filters. The parameters of the CSPBlocks are adopted according to [175]. Experiments with various filter numbers have been carried out in order to choose the best.

To implement this architecture, firstly similar to YOLOv4, the CSPBlock modules were used in the backbone of the proposed architecture. Cross-stage residual edge is used in the CSPBlock module to combine the two divided feature maps (groupid=1/2 in the figure). This enhances the learning ability of convolution networks compared with the ResBlock module.

The filter number of 64 in the first CSPBlock module is divided into two convolutions of 32 filters and then combined with 3x3 convolution at the beginning of the backbone with 32 filters. The results are then passed to a 3x3 convolution with a filter number of 64 and combined with the shortcut from the first convolution with the filter number of 64.

The filter number of the second CSPBlock module is 128 and divides into two convolutions of 64 filters and then combined with a 3x3 convolution of the backbone with 64 filters. The results are then passed to a 3x3 convolution with a filter number of 128 and combined with the shortcut from the first convolution with the filter number of 128.

The last module starts with a convolution of 256 filters and divides into two convolutions with filters of 128 and then combined with a shortcut from the convolution with 128 filters. The results are then passed to a 3x3 convolution with filter number of 64. The result is combined with the shortcut from the first convolution with filter 256.

Secondly to improve the receptive field of the backbone, an SSP module was modified concatenating the max-pooling outputs with kernel sizes of 7, 10 and 13 respectively. The concatenation of these max pooling outputs improved the accuracy of the architecture.

Thirdly, to be able to detect small faces from long distances, a modified PAN module was included to the backbone of the architecture with an additional bottom-up path augmentation added to the FPN architecture to aggregate features from low-level layers with more detailed information and the higher level layers with more semantic information. An extra upsampling (3 downsampling with factors of 16, 8, and 4) was added to the PAN architecture

in comparison with YOLOV4 to keep shallower features. The concatenation of the features from the bottom-up path goes through a 1×1 convolution.

C.3.2 Enhanced Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP)

The second component, an enhanced Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP) [123] is included at the end of the backup (Marked as b) at the end of the backbone. This technique provides the capability to handle different sizes of the image input sizes and this capture multi-scale information from different spatial resolutions being this a key factor when detecting object at low resolutions from large images. By deploying this technique, the CNN become more robust when the UAV is flying at different altitudes because the algorithm is less affected by variations in the size of the faces.

C.3.3 Enhanced Path Aggregation Network (PAN)

A modified Path Aggregation Network (PAN) [124] module was also added (Marked as c) in the algorithm with three up-samplings (compared to YOLOv4). This technique enhances the capability of keeping the fine-grained features from the first layers along the computation of the following ones. This becomes an important matter when the details extracted from low-pixel size faces may be lost along the CNN.

The number of filters selected was 64, 128, 256, 128, and 64 respectively. The extra bottom-up path augmentation was down-sampled (3 down-samplings compared to two down-samplings in YOLOv4) with factors of 16, 8, and 4 respectively. The number of filters selected was 64. The features from the bottom-up path were then concatenated and 1×1 convolution was run on the result. The coordinates, probability and confidence were obtained using YOLOv3 headers. The YOLOv3 headers were used to output the coordinates, probability and level of confidence. 19×19 , 38×38 and 76×76 are the feature maps of the YOLOv3 header.

C.4 Implementation and deployment

This section presents the implementation and deployment of the UWS-YOLO in order to detect faces from UAV images and videos. It describes how the proposed solution is trained and tested in addition to the datasets used to evaluate results. Besides, further explanation is given regarding standards algorithms commonly employed to perform face detection in order to be compared against our algorithm.

C.4.1 Face detection datasets

Several algorithms are compared in terms of accuracy and speed. Every algorithm presented should be trained and evaluated over the same dataset in order to perform a fair comparison. In this manuscript, two datasets are presented. First, a publicly available dataset named WIDER FACE which is mainly composed of images taken at ground level. Secondly, the authors of the manuscript created a face detection dataset recorded from a UAV: UAV-UWS dataset.

WIDER FACE

One of the largest datasets for face recognition is WIDER FACE dataset. It contains 32,203 images and 393,703 faces which is an average of 12 faces per image. The different illumination, scales, poses, and occlusions included in this dataset make it a challenging task to achieve very high accuracy. WIDER FACE [23] is divided into three levels of difficulties namely easy, medium and difficult. The accuracies in this research have been obtained by joining all three subsets together.

In order to allow other researchers to compare their algorithms against UWS-YOLO, this manuscript uses this dataset as the benchmark to compare our proposed solution with the state-of-the-art architectures; however, UWS-YOLO is optimised for low-pixel face recognition and not for close range images.

UAV-UWS dataset

In the scope of this research work, the authors have also created a dataset to test the algorithms in videos captured from a drone. This dataset was recorded using a DJI Mini 2 UAV. The frames obtained have a 4K resolution (3840×2160 pixels) and a frame rate of 30 FPS.

20 people from different ethnicities were recorded for the dataset. For each person, a video of 30 seconds was recorded at 8 different distances from the drone to the face (2, 5, 7, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 meters). Therefore, the dataset is composed of 144,000 different frames. The UAV was positioned at 30° above the face at each distance. Furthermore, the people recorded were asked to do different head movements to get a complete view of the whole face. Fig. C.3 shows an example of the head movements asked to every volunteer. Initially, participants were asked to execute a lateral head movement, looking first to the left and then to the right. Following this, a full circular movement with the head was made to cover the rest of the positions, including upward and downward positions. Finally, the volunteers were asked to stare directly at the drone, looking forward.

Due to the similarity of the faces in consecutive frames. The test dataset has been created extracting only one frame per second. Therefore, the dataset used for testing is composed of 4,800 images with a ratio of one face per image.

It is worth noting that General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance is a critical consideration in our data-gathering process, as we are committed to respecting individuals' privacy and adhering to the regulations. While the dataset may be relatively small in comparison to some other studies, it has been meticulously curated to cater specifically to the objectives of our research. We emphasise that the dataset's size is appropriate for the testing and validation of our proposed model and offers a representative sample for the intended use case.

Table C.2 shows the average face size, face at each distance of our dataset with two image sizes: the original 4K resolution and after being resized to 608×608 . As can be seen, at higher than 15 meters, the size of the faces in the resized image is less than 10 pixels. The smallest face is at 30 meters where the average size is only 2×5 pixels in the resized image.

Figure C.3: Examples of the different face positions recorded in the UAV-UWS dataset.

C.4.2 Face detection algorithms

UWS-YOLO is compared against RetinaFace [42] and YOLOv7 [133] in terms of accuracy, inference time, loading time of the model and model size. To compare all algorithms, these were trained in the same conditions over the same dataset. First, every algorithm was trained with the general dataset WIDER FACE. Then, each algorithm is evaluated over the testing dataset of WIDER FACE. Finally, to compare the accuracy of the algorithms when detecting faces from UAV images at high altitudes, the UAV-UWS dataset is used as a testing dataset, therefore, this dataset is only used for verification of the algorithms. This process is useful for comparing how each algorithm with the same training behaves at different distances.

C.4.3 Hyperparameters

Table C.3 shows the execution hyperparameters used to train UWS-YOLO, RetinaFace and YOLOv7.

Table C.2: Distance from the camera to the face versus the size of the detected face in pixels (px) for the original resolution and the resized image

Distance	Size Face	
	3840 × 2160 px	608 × 608 px
2 m	125 × 170 px	20 × 28 px
5 m	80 × 98 px	13 × 28 px
7 m	50 × 59 px	8 × 17 px
10 m	38 × 44 px	6 × 12 px
15 m	25 × 31 px	4 × 9 px
20 m	20 × 24 px	3 × 7 px
25 m	17 × 19 px	3 × 5 px
30 m	14 × 19 px	2 × 5 px

RetinaFace - ResNet50

A momentum coefficient of 0.9 was used for training. The input size of the training images was 640×640 px and the batch size used was 8. Moreover, the Machine Learning execution platform for RetinaFace was TensorFlow 2.5.3 [176].

UWS-YOLO

We utilise a momentum coefficient of 0.9 as the learning policy. An image input size of 608×608 px was used in our training with a batch size of 64. The machine learning execution platform used was Darknet [177].

YOLOv7

YOLOv7 was trained with a momentum coefficient of 0.9. 608×608 px is the size as the images are fed in YOLOv7. The batch size chosen is 8. The machine learning execution platform is Darknet [177].

C.4.4 Intersection over Union (IoU)

The Intersection over Union (IoU) is a fundamental metric used in object detection. The IoU measures the overlap between the predicted bounding box and the ground truth bounding

Table C.3: Execution Hyperparameters

Hyperparameters	RF-ResNet50	UWS-YOLO	YoloV7
Image size in pixel	640×640	608×608	608×608
Number of iteration	161000	40000	120000
Batch size	8	64	8
Momentum coefficient	0.9	0.9	0.9

box, providing a quantitative assessment of the accuracy of the detection. As shown in Fig. C.4, the IoU is defined as the area of overlap (intersection) between the bounding boxes divided by the area of union.

Figure C.4: IoU formula with example figures.

Face detection is only one stage in the pipeline of our use case. Therefore, subsequent stages rely heavily on obtaining accurate face images to achieve high accuracy. For instance, in face verification tasks, having precise face images is crucial for obtaining successful results. Hence, an accurate bounding box around the face is of utmost importance, and this is where the IoU threshold becomes crucial.

Fig. C.5 illustrates three different face detections varying the IoU threshold. The green bounding box represents the ground truth, while the red one corresponds to the face detected by the model. With an IoU of 90% (Fig. C.5a) the detected face closely matches the ground truth. When using an IoU of 75% (Fig. C.5b) a small portion of the face is lost, but the results are still satisfactory for subsequent stages. However, with an IoU of 50% (Fig. C.5c) a significant part of the face is lost, possibly even an eye from the bounding box. This makes

it challenging for the next stages to achieve excellent results; however, the impact is not significant. In cases with an IoU below 50%, it becomes impossible to achieve good results in the next stages as more than half of the face may be lost.

Figure C.5: Examples of face detections using three different IoU thresholds: 90%, 75% and 50%.

Therefore, in this study, the accuracy of the models will be compared using these three IoU values: 90%, 75% and 50%.

C.4.5 Pipeline

The pipeline is divided into three stages as depicted in Fig. C.6. First, the image is preprocessed, and then it is fed into the neural network. Finally, the results are post-processed to obtain the bounding boxes with confidence scores for each detection. The input to the pipeline is a single frame.

Figure C.6: IoU formula with example figures.

Preprocessing

The preprocessing stage consists of three steps aimed at preparing the captured frame for the neural network.

1. **Resize:** The image is resized to match the input size required by the neural network. In this process, the OpenCV resize function is utilised.
2. **Scaling:** The pixel values in each channel are scaled to fit within the range expected by the neural network.
3. **Channel conversion:** The image is converted from the Blue-Green-Red (BGR) colour space to Red-Green-Blue (RGB). Moreover, the channel dimensions are transposed from (N, H, W, C) to (N, C, H, W) , where N represents the number of images in a batch, C is the number of channels in the image, H is the height of the image, and W is the width.

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)

The preprocessed image is then passed through a CNN. For this research, three different CNN models were employed: RetinaFace, YOLO-UWS and YOLOv7. Each model produces detection candidates along with their corresponding confidence scores.

Detections

A detection threshold is defined to determine the acceptance of a detection. If the confidence score of a detection is higher than the threshold, it is considered a valid detection; otherwise, it is discarded. Lowering the threshold will increase the number of true detections but also lead to an increase in false detections, therefore, it may reduce the accuracy. The choice of an appropriate threshold is crucial to achieve high accuracy with each model. Once the detections are confirmed, the bounding boxes are resized to match the dimensions of the original size.

The output of the pipeline consists of the bounding boxes for each detection, defined by the coordinates of the top-left corner of the bounding box, as well as its width and height. Furthermore, the pipeline provides the confidence score for each detection.

C.5 Empirical Results and Discussions

This section presents both quantitative and qualitative results from various experiments conducted to facilitate a comprehensive comparison of the algorithms. The quantitative results subsection shows the comparison of RetinaFace (with three different input sizes), YOLOv7 and UWS-YOLO on different metrics such as the inference time, the build time, the weights size and the accuracy of the algorithms. The last one has been analysed on two different datasets - WIDER FACE and UAV-UWS. The qualitative results show what can our algorithm (UWS-YOLO) achieve on images at different distances.

C.5.1 Experimentation environment

The experiments have been carried out on a computer with an Intel(R) Xeon(R) E5-2630 v4 at 2.20 GHz with 20 cores and 32 GB of RAM. In addition, an NVIDIA GeForce GTX TITAN X with 12 GB of onboard memory with CUDA compatibility [129] was used. The Operative System (OS) used is Focal Ubuntu 20.04.3 with a Kernel version of 5.11.00.

C.5.2 Quantitative results

Accuracy

The accuracy of the models has been evaluated using three different approaches. Firstly, the WIDER FACE dataset was utilised, employing three IoUs: 0.5, 0.75 and 0.9. Subsequently, the models were tested on the UAV-UWS dataset employing the same IoUs. Finally, they were tested on the UAV-UWS dataset but at every distance with a fixed IoU of 0.5. All the results have been obtained from experiments conducted specifically for this study.

Table C.4 shows the results for the WIDER FACE dataset. Among the models, YOLOv7 exhibits the lowest accuracy. UWS-YOLO demonstrates modest performance and matches the accuracy of RetinaFace only when using an input size of 416 px and the most permissive IoU (50%). RetinaFace achieves the highest accuracy across all IoU, particularly with an input size of 1600 px.

Table C.4: Accuracy of UWS-YOLO and RetinaFace for WIDER FACE dataset varying IoU percentage.

Models	IoU		
	90%	75%	50%
RetinaFace - 416 px	2.35%	43.61%	72.40%
RetinaFace - 608 px	3.80%	53.60%	81.96%
RetinaFace - 1600 px	4.76%	63.60%	93.05%
YOLOv7 - 608 px	0.69%	29.62%	65.43%
UWS-YOLO - 608 px	1.66%	32.98%	72.26%

Table C.5 presents the accuracy of the models on the UAV-UWS dataset. Our model (UWS-YOLO) demonstrates exceptional accuracy, second only to RetinaFace with an input size of 1600 px. Compared with models with the same input size, UWS-YOLO achieves +12.7% better accuracy than YOLOv7 and +31.86% improvement over RetinaFace with an IoU of 50%. Even with a stricter IoU of 90%, UWS-YOLO outperforms YOLOv7 by +3.96% and RetinaFace by +2,33%.

Table C.5: Accuracy of UWS-YOLO and RetinaFace for UAV-UWS dataset varying IoU percentage.

Models	IoU		
	90%	75%	50%
RetinaFace - 416 px	1.34%	9.52%	14.85%
RetinaFace - 608 px	4.81%	19.17%	27.43%
RetinaFace - 1600 px	24.14%	51.24%	64.74%
YOLOv7 - 608 px	3.18%	32.91%	46.59%
UWS-YOLO - 608 px	7.14%	37.86%	59.29%

Table C.6 shows the accuracy of the models on the UAV-UWS dataset for each of the eight distances recorded: 2, 5, 7, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 meters. At a distance of 2 meters, all models achieve similar results, but both YOLO variants (YOLOv7 and UWS-YOLO)

achieve the highest accuracy, exceeding 87% of accuracy. At 5 meters, better results are observed, except for RetinaFace with an input size of 416 px, which fails to detect faces beyond 5 meters. Moreover, RetinaFace with an input size of 608 px can only detect faces up to 10 meters, where it achieves an accuracy of merely 0.35%. This indicates that RetinaFace with a small input size is only able to detect faces accurately at short distances.

Table C.6: Accuracy at different flying distances = IoU 50%

Models	Metric Type	Distance							
		2m	5m	7m	10m	15m	20m	25m	30m
RetinaFace - 416 px	mAP	82.64%	29.71%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
RetinaFace - 608 px	mAP	83.29%	84.75%	45.04%	0.35%	0%	0%	0%	0%
RetinaFace - 1600 px	mAP	83.60%	92.18%	98.63%	90.81%	82.44%	55.54%	10.62%	0.39%
YOLOv7 - 608 px	mAP	87.67%	92.05%	84.65%	60.42%	36.23%	4.95%	0.15%	0.01%
UWS-YOLO - 608px	mAP	87.58%	93.52%	92.90%	75.62%	60.15%	37.35%	8.54%	2.22%

RetinaFace with an input size of 1600 px, YOLOv7 and UWS-YOLO are the only models that achieve good results at longer distances (more than 10 meters) as indicated in the table. At 25 and 30 meters, YOLOv7 struggles to detect any face, resulting in significantly low accuracy (0.15% and 0.01% respectively). In contrast, UWS-YOLO achieves an accuracy of more than 8% at 25 meters and 2.22% at 30 meters, surpassing even RetinaFace with an input size of 1600 px by +1.83%.

These results demonstrate that our model UWS-YOLO performs well at both short and long distances, surpassing, at some distances, models with nearly three times larger input sizes. Furthermore, when compared to models with the same input size, UWS-YOLO consistently accomplishes superior results across all distances.

Built time, weights size and inference time

Table C.7 provides a comparison of the built time, the weights size and the inference time for the three models under consideration. The values shown are with the same input size of 608 px for all three models. YoloV7 exhibits the longest building time, taking approximately 4 seconds, and it has also the biggest weights size of 140 MB. In contrast, RetinaFace has a build time of around 2.5 seconds with a weights size close to 130 MB. Notably, our proposed

model, UWS-YOLO demonstrates the fastest build time of only 1.5 seconds, showcasing its speed and stands out as the most lightweight model with only a weights size of 49 MB.

Table C.7: Build time, weights size and inference time for the three compared models with input size of 608 px

Model	Build time	Weights Size	Inference Time
RetinaFace	2426 ms	128 MB	26 FPS (38 ms)
YoloV7	4040 ms	140 MB	24 FPS (41 ms)
UWS-YOLO	1552ms	49 MB	91 FPS (11 ms)

Regarding inference time, a correlation can be observed with the weights size. Our proposed model achieves the fastest inference time, merely 11 ms, equivalent to 91 FPS. In contrast, RetinaFace has an inference time of 38 ms (26 FPS) while YoloV7 is the slowest with 41 ms (24 FPS). Therefore, our model stands as the only one capable of achieving real-time processing, defined at a frame rate of 30 FPS.

Our proposed model is +345% faster than RetinaFace achieving better accuracy when evaluated on the UAV-UWS dataset. Furthermore, in comparison to YoloV7, our model outperforms it significantly, being +373% faster and showcasing better accuracy across all tested datasets, including WIDERFACE.

Inference time and mAP comparison over different input sizes

Fig. C.7 shows the relation between the accuracy and the inference time in our UAV-UWS dataset. It has been compared using the three models - RetinaFace, YOLOv7 and UWS-YOLO - with three different input sizes - 416, 608 and 1600 px. In the figure, the leftmost area indicates the fastest models whilst the area at the top indicates models with higher accuracy. The figure also shows where is the real-time processing defined as 33 ms (30 FPS). Any model on the left of this vertical line will execute real-time detections.

YOLOv7 and RetinaFace models only achieve real-time processing with their smallest input size (416), while our model achieves it even with an input size of 608. Furthermore, not only our model is faster than the others at these input sizes (416 and 608) but also it achieves a higher accuracy. Using an input size of 416, our model is +371% faster than RetinaFace

and has an accuracy improvement of +18.31%. Moreover, it is +314% faster than YOLOv7 and better accuracy by +3.54%.

Our model was trained with an input size of 608 px, therefore, the best results will be when this input size is used. Fig. C.7 reflects this. Our model is the upper leftmost compared to the other models. As mentioned in previous sections, our model with this input size is +345% faster than RetinaFace and +373% than YOLOv7. It also has +31.86% and +12.7% higher accuracy than RetinaFace and YOLOv7 respectively.

On the other side, with an input size of 1600 px, our model is faster than the other models (+330% than RetinaFace and +365% than YOLOv7), but it has lower accuracy (−3.68% than RetinaFace and −8.07% than YOLOv7).

Although RetinaFace-1600px achieves the highest accuracy (69.16%), its inference time is also really high (208 ms). Moreover, UWS-YOLO does not show a great accuracy difference when increasing the input size to 1600 px (1.8% more) but the inference time increased significantly (46 ms more), being slower than real-time. This can be seen in Fig. C.7. Therefore, based on the trade-off between high speed and high accuracy and that real-time processing is needed, our algorithm UWS-YOLO-608px will achieve the best results.

Figure C.7: mAP accuracy with IoU 0.5 in the UAV-UWS dataset versus its inference time in milliseconds using three different input sizes: 416, 608 and 1600.

C.5.3 Qualitative results

Fig. C.8 shows frames from our UAV-UWS dataset at four different distances and head positions. Each frame contains only one person and therefore one face. Fig. C.8a shows a volunteer at 2 meters with the head facing right down. The face was detected by our model with a confidence score of 58%. The low confidence score can be attributed to the person's face facing down, resulting in an obscured facial appearance. This demonstrates the capability of our algorithm to detect faces under conditions where not all facial features are readily visible. Fig. C.8b shows the same volunteer in the same position but at a distance of 7 meters. Our model is able to detect the face with a confidence score of 61%. Again, this confidence score can be attributed to the downward-facing orientation of the face.

In Fig. C.8c the person is at 20 meters and is looking directly at the drone. The face is detected with a confidence score of 81%. The model achieves a high confidence score even at far distances as the person is facing the drone and all the face features can be appreciated. Finally, Fig. C.8d shows the same person staring at the drone but at 30 meters, the maximum distance of our dataset. Our model is capable of detecting the face, but only with a confidence score of 13%. It is worth reminding that at 30 meters, the size of the face in the resized image (608×608) is 2×5 px. Therefore, the confidence score is low as the resolution of the face is small and most of the face features have been lost.

C.6 Conclusions

Face detection is a widely studied task in research, primarily focusing on achieving high accuracy. However, most existing solutions neglect the crucial aspect of low execution times, which are essential for real-time performance and subsequent face identification processes. Moreover, face detection from UAV imagery poses additional challenges due to factors such as face posing, angle variations, camera inclination, and drone vibrations.

This manuscript introduces a novel CNN-based algorithm, UWS-YOLO, specifically designed to address these limitations. Our algorithm demonstrates high-accuracy face detections with minimal inference times from UAV videos. To evaluate the performance of

(a) Detection at 2 m with the face looking right down. (b) Detection at 7 m with the face looking right down.

(c) Detection at 20 m with the face looking forward directly to the drone. (d) Detection at 30 m with the face looking forward directly to the drone.

Figure C.8: UWS-YOLO detections at 4 four distances in frames from our UAV-UWS dataset.

UWS-YOLO, we conducted comprehensive training and evaluation experiments, comparing it against SOTA algorithms, including RetinaFace. The evaluations were performed on both a standard dataset (WIDER FACE) and a dataset collected by the authors using a UAV. Empirical evaluation has been conducted, and UWS-YOLO outperforms RetinaFace by a significant margin, achieving an accuracy rate of 59.29% compared to RetinaFace's 27.43%. Notably, UWS-YOLO surpasses RetinaFace's capabilities by successfully detecting faces even beyond a distance of 10m. Furthermore, in terms of speed, UWS-YOLO exhibits exceptional efficiency, performing 345% faster than RetinaFace.

The key advantages of UWS-YOLO can be summarised as follows: superior speed, remarkable accuracy, and the ability to handle the complexities of face detection in UAV operations. These findings position UWS-YOLO as a balanced and highly suitable algorithm for face detection in UAV applications. In summary, the presented research has created a

cutting-edge solution that surpasses previous algorithms in terms of speed and accuracy, while also addressing the unique challenges associated with face detection from UAV imagery.

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Appendix D

Dynamic-Distance-Based Thresholding for UAV-Based Face Verification Algorithms

Please note that this chapter contains a copy of content present in the research paper [4], and that, therefore, it has already been peer-reviewed and accepted.

Abstract

Face verification, crucial for identity authentication and access control in our digital society, faces significant challenges when comparing images taken in diverse environments, which vary in terms of distance, angle, and lighting conditions. These disparities often lead to decreased accuracy due to significant resolution changes. This paper introduces an adaptive face verification solution tailored for diverse conditions, particularly focusing on Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)-based public safety applications. Our approach features an innovative adaptive verification threshold algorithm and an optimised operation pipeline, specifically designed to accommodate varying distances between the UAV and the human subject. The proposed solution is implemented based on a UAV platform and empirically compared with

several state-of-the-art solutions. Empirical results have shown that an improvement of 15% in accuracy can be achieved.

D.1 Introduction

Nowadays, face recognition and face verification are widely deployed in many areas of our lives, for instance, at border control points between countries, for building access management in universities and companies, unlocking smartphones, service authentication/authorisation for individuals, and so on. Face recognition aims to identify all the concerned persons, and thus a database is usually needed to store all the people to be identified. In contrast, face verification seeks to identify only one person, so a database would not be needed as only one person would be being searched. The reasons for recognising or verifying a face are many, including customised services, targeted advertisement, health measures, or even security.

Moreover, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) are increasingly deployed in multiple areas for Search and Rescue (SAR) operations [157], delivering goods [178], and many other purposes, as a cost-effective mobile platform. When UAVs meet face verification, the possibilities of potential use cases are immense in light of joining the capabilities of both technologies together in one platform. It is therefore promising to combine the two technologies and be able to recognise people from UAVs. Nevertheless, it is important to secure the UAV, as it will process sensitive privacy data, like the faces images for verification purposes [179].

Such a face verification-enabled UAV system allows for the recognition of a person from distances, without being intrusive to the user by removing the need for a camera close to the face, and opens up opportunities for new location or mobility-based services. Combining both technologies, face verification and UAVs could be highly useful for many use cases, lowering costs and extending the range. One main new use case for face verification from UAVs is the Drone Guard Angel for public safety escort services in the Arcadian-IoT European Project [9]. In this use case, a UAV comes to the customer's position on demand, recognises the person, verifies his/her face to authorise the services as subscribed, and accompanies the

person home in a safe way, acting as an invigilator that can help in case of any malicious activity.

Currently, most face verification techniques are performed at close distances. For instance, when a phone is unlocked using face verification, it is usually positioned 30 cm from the face. At this distance, all the features of the face can be captured with a high resolution; therefore, face verification can be performed without significant difficulties using state-of-the-art technologies. However, if face verification is performed from a UAV, it is not possible to position it at 30 cm from the face due to safety reasons. Thus, the UAV has to be at long distances, which vary depending on its size. It is noted that most face verification algorithms are optimised for close distances. Moreover, face verification is usually effective at a fixed distance or within a small range, whereas, for a UAV-based use case, the distance between a face and the UAV is significantly higher; thus, the size of the face in pixels varies and the low pixel resolution of a face introduces significant difficulties in face verification, imposing the challenge of developing new techniques to improve the accuracy of these algorithms when face verification is carried out from longer distances.

In addition, for services like the Drone Guard Angel, the operational environments pose further challenges in terms of poor lighting conditions due to outdoor and late evening operations as well as the fast-changing positions and angles of the target face due to the movement of the UAV. For this reason, a new technique that is lighting- and position-adaptive is proposed in this manuscript to enable the successful deployment of the new services such as Drone Guard Angel.

Consequently, the main contribution of this work is a novel dynamic size-adaptive threshold technique for face verification from UAVs, where the face has to be verified from long distances and in a highly adaptive manner in response to the challenging operational environments where lighting conditions and the positioning of the face change rapidly. To this end, a smart pipeline has been developed for introducing dynamic thresholds.

Furthermore, in order to compare the proposed technique with the existing solution, an empirical analysis of different algorithms is performed, including four state-of-the-art face verification algorithms (ArcFace [73], VGG-Face [180], SFace [128], and Dlib [181]). To

conduct a more complete analysis, two different similarity metrics for distance calculation are explored: cosine and Euclidean distances. A study of the suitability of each metric for the different face verification algorithms is conducted too.

The main contributions herein can then be summarised as follows:

- A novel adaptive threshold algorithm for enhancing different state-of-the-art face verification and recognition algorithms to suit UAV-based applications.
- A new pipeline with novel capabilities to integrate the proposed dynamic threshold algorithm.
- An empirical evaluation of the effectiveness of the proposed adaptive threshold technique when dealing with UAV-based face verification use cases using two different similarity metrics.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: in Section D.2, the literature in this research area is reviewed, especially the representative state-of-the-art face verification algorithms and metrics focused for enhancement in this paper. Section D.3 describes the proposed design of the face verification pipeline. In Section D.4, the algorithm to calculate the proposed thresholds, together with the dataset used, is explained. In Section D.5, the implementation of the experiments is presented. In Section D.6, the accuracy of the algorithms of the proposed dynamic-distance-based thresholds is compared with the state-of-the-art algorithms and the suitability of each metric for the algorithms is analysed. Finally, in Section D.7 conclusions are drawn.

D.2 Related Work

Most of the state-of-the-art studies focus on face recognition rather than on face verification, whilst the latter is what this paper will emphasise. The primary distinction between them lies in the outcome: a face recognition algorithm provides the identity of the recognised person, whereas a face verification algorithm determines whether the person being assessed matches the intended individual or not.

Furthermore, the inference time of face recognition algorithms is always greater than that of face verification ones. This is due to the need to compare one face with all the present faces in the database to achieve face recognition. On the contrary, in face verification it is only necessary to compare one face to another to decide if they are or are not the same person.

Additionally, the decision could be made differently between face recognition and face verification. For the former, the decision can be performed through a K Nearest Neighbour (KNN) algorithm. It stores all the available classes and classifies the data based on similarity. The decision it makes relates to which person in the database is most similar to the one being compared to. On the other hand, face verification is based on a global threshold to decide if it is the same person or not [74]. For this reason, choosing an optimal threshold is critical. If it is not defined properly, many false positives or negatives are possible, leading to erroneous verification. Other thresholding techniques are based on having client-specific thresholds. This paper is based on applying different thresholds depending on the person to be identified [182].

Figure D.1 shows the most common approach used by other research works to verify a person: a Siamese neural network [183]. In other words, two identical neural networks with the same network model/structure and the same weights. Two images are also needed. The first one is a picture of the face of the person already verified. The second one is a picture of the person to be verified. These pictures go through the Siamese neural network, obtaining as output two different vectors that can be compared as they are the result of the same neural network. Then, the distance between them is calculated. If the distance is above the threshold, the decision is that they are not the same person. If it is below the threshold, it is concluded that they are the same person.

Currently, there is a lack of literature on face verification from UAVs. A few studies can be found about detecting and finding people from UAVs [158], for instance, to conduct SAR operations [157]. There are studies in which face verification from UAVs is performed, although only from very short distances. Moreover, they focused on traditional face verification algorithms with low accuracy but high speed, such as Local Binary Pattern (LBP) [184].

Figure D.1: Simplified diagram of the face verification process.

Other papers develop algorithms for face verification; however, they do not use real images from UAVs.

For example, [185] uses a Haar Cascade for detecting faces, and an LBP Histogram (LBPH) Face Recognizer. A complete system for the acquisition of images from a UAV and their subsequent physical recognition is proposed. The results do not provide any real images from the UAV, so it has not been possible to test it in a real system. While the LBPH algorithm is easy to implement, it is not as accurate as more current face verification algorithms such as those selected in our contribution.

Another similar work is [64], which also employed an LBPH algorithm along with OpenCV to perform face recognition from a UAV. It used a Raspberry Pi and a Raspberry Pi Camera. The results present some images of face recognition while controlling the UAV. Although all the images are from very close distances, we are trying to perform face recognition from long distances, up to 30 m.

Several studies have explored both the influence of the distance from the UAV to the person and the angle between them. Certain findings suggest that the distance and the depressing angles are crucial constraints in face verification systems, particularly when the UAV is positioned at high altitudes [186]. Another study analysed the effects of the horizontal and vertical angles between the face and the camera, utilising a face recognition pipeline based on OpenCV and Dlib libraries [187]. Further research has developed an innovative

deep learning-based face detection and recognition system for drones. The system was analysed by varying the distance and height of the drone to the person, demonstrating good accuracy at lower heights and close distances [65]. These existing studies did not address the adaptive dynamic thresholding technique proposed in this paper.

D.2.1 Empirical Comparison of Face Verification Algorithms

Table D.1 shows an in-depth comparison among different face verification and recognition algorithms available in the literature. The verification performance and the different parameters of each algorithm have been obtained from its official paper. The table compares the input and output size of the network used by each algorithm, and the verification performance using two different datasets: Labeled Faces in the Wild (LFW) [57] and Youtube Faces (YTF) [58], as well as comparing the size of the pre-trained weights of the neural networks, and the number of images it has been trained with.

The human-level performance in face verification on LFW is 97.53% [67]. Four algorithms shown in the table do not surpass this value: Open-Face [127], Deep-Face [68], Fisher-Vector Faces [188], and TL Joint Bayesian [189].

VGG-Face [180], Deep-Face [68], and CosFace [71] are the algorithms with the heaviest weights, leading to slow performance when executed. On the other hand, DeepID2 [72] and Open-Face [127] have the lightest weights. Therefore, they will be fast but not as accurate as others. Furthermore, TL Joint Bayesian [189] and GaussianFace [190] algorithms do not have pre-trained weights available, and they have not been evaluated on the YTF dataset [58].

AdaFace [78], CurricularFace [80] and SFace [128] are new algorithms that achieve good accuracy in the LFW dataset (more than 99%). However, there is no information about the output size or the accuracy on the YTF dataset for the first two.

Four representative algorithms have then been selected to perform deeper, empirical analysis in this paper, including VGG-Face [180], ArcFace [73], SFace [128], and Dlib [181].

These four algorithms have been selected for several reasons. Firstly, they all achieve more than 98% accuracy in the LFW dataset; therefore, all four surpass the human-level performance of LFW (97.53%). Moreover, they have pre-trained weights available that can per-

form tests without training. ArcFace was selected because it provides the loss function with the best verification performance of the three algorithms compared (SphereFace [77], CosFace [71], and ArcFace [73]), whilst Face-Net [74] has been discarded because SFace [72], Dlib [181], and VGG-Face [180] have better verification performance. Furthermore, SFace explores a new method by training the model with synthetically generated data.

These four selected algorithms have the greatest potential to improve through training as they all have open-source code that can be modified according to our needs, and the datasets used are public so the results of these four algorithms can be replicated and used conveniently.

These face verification models are Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)s. They obtain an image as an input and have a vector as an output. They represent images of faces as vectors. The images captured with the UAV have to be resized in order to have the same size as the inputs for each algorithm. Then as output shapes, there is a vector with different sizes for each algorithm. These vectors will be the ones used to measure the distance between them to decide if the person is verified or not. The bigger the output shape, the greater the computational usage and processing time but the higher the accuracy.

Table D.1: Comparative between different face verification State-of-the-Art algorithms

Algorithm	Input Size	Output Size	Verification Performance		Pre-trained Weights Size	Training Images	Other information
			on LFW dataset	on YTF dataset			
<i>Human-beings</i> [67]	N/A	N/A	97.53	NG	N/A	N/A	Humans performance
Open-Face [127]	96x96x3	128	92.92	NG	14 MB	1M	Open source framework
Deep-Face [68]	152x152x3	4096	97.35	91.40	551 MB	4.4M	Deep Convolutional Network
Fisher-Vector Faces [188]	160x125x3	128	93.03	NG	NG	NG	Fisher Vectors
TL Joint Bayesian [189]	Variable	NG	96.33	NG	NG	NG	Bayesian model
VGG-Face [180]	224x224x3	2622	98.95	97.30	554 MB	2.6M	Convolutional Neural Network
CosFace [71]	112x96x3	NG	99.73	97.60	214.3 MB	5M	Loss function
DeepID2 [72]	55x47x3	160	99.53	93.20	1.6 MB	0.2M	Deep Neural Network
GaussianFace [190]	150x120x3	NG	98.52	NG	NG	NG	Gaussian Model
ArcFace [73]	112x112x3	512	99.83	98.02	131 MB	5.8M	Loss function
Dlib [181]	150x150x3	128	99.38	NG	22 MB	3M	Machine Learning Toolkit
SphereFace [77]	112x96x3	512	99.42	95.00	68.6MB	0.5M	Loss function
Face-Net [74]	160x160x3	128	98.87	95.12	88 MB	200M	Deep Convolutional Network
AdaFace [78]	112x112x3	NG	99.82	NG	668MB	15.1M	Loss function
SFace [128]	112x112x3	128	99.13	NG	36.9MB	1.1M	Synthetic dataset training
CurricularFace [80]	112x112x3	NG	99.80	NG	249MB	6.3M	Loss function

NG = Not Given; N/A = Not applicable

VGG-Face

This algorithm has been developed by the University of Oxford. Its architecture has 22 layers and 37 deep units. Also, the input is a face image of 224×224 pixels, which is the biggest input of the four algorithms analysed. Moreover, it also has the biggest output, a 2622 dimension vector. That is why, as will be seen below, this algorithm achieves the best accuracy but it is also the slowest [180].

SFace

It has been trained using a synthetically generated face dataset to train the face verification model. To generate the data, a class-conditional generative adversarial network has been used. The generated dataset is composed of 634k synthetic images distributed on 10,575 classes. The face verification model uses ResNet-50 as the backbone and the loss function used is CosFace. The input size of the face is 112×112 pixels [128].

ArcFace

It is an algorithm developed by the Imperial College London. It is based on MXNet [191] and Python, but in the framework used it is based on a re-implementation in Keras [161]. The model is based on ResNet34 Architecture. The algorithm has as input an image of 112×112 pixels and has as output a vector of 512 dimensions [73].

Dlib

It is not an algorithm but a library written in C++ that also has a Python interface. This library contains machine learning algorithms like the one used for face recognition. It is based on a Resnet34 model but with some modifications consisting of 29 convolutional layers. Its input is a 150×150 face image and its output is a 128 dimensions vector [181].

D.2.2 Distance Calculation Methods

For the calculation of the distance between the two images (the one of the person to compare and the image to be compared), two different metrics will be used: Euclidean distance and cosine distance. For each one of them, a different dynamic threshold will be calculated.

D.3 Proposed Pipeline Architecture of Face Verification Algorithm

This research develops a new system with a size-adaptive dynamic threshold for enhancing face verification capabilities and then compares four state-of-the-art face verification algorithms. Figure D.2 shows the proposed face verification system. The proposed system needs two inputs to perform face verification. The first one is a video received from a UAV, and the second one is the face of the person to verify. Each input will go through the same steps in parallel up to the distance calculation. The system could be divided into five different stages as shown in the figure:

1. **Face Detection:** This is the first stage in our pipeline. The images are processed with RetinaFace [42], which is a face detection algorithm with high performance for both high- and low-resolution faces. Notice that face detection has nothing to do with face identification or face verification. Face detection is the process of determining that there is a face in a set of pixels. Thus, the output of this algorithm is the number of faces in the image and the coordinates of each of them in the image. For research purposes, there will be only one face in each frame. This stage is the slowest of the pipeline as the detection lasts on average 170 ms, causing the maximum processing speed to be less than 6 Frames per second (FPS). This face-detection algorithm has been selected for our pipeline because of its considerable accuracy in detecting low-resolution faces.
2. **Preprocessing:** It is divided into two different components. First, the detected face is cropped from the frame using the coordinates provided by RetinaFace and the OpenCV library. Then, the cropped face is resized to the input size of the algorithm that is going

to be used according to Table D.1 using OpenCV. This step is really fast as it only takes 0.3 ms to complete. In most cases, the image ratio of the cropped face will not be the same as the expected size of the algorithms. Therefore, in order not to distort the image, black pixels are included to reach the expected size while maintaining the same image ratio. Further preprocessing is not executed in order to compare the performance of the face verification algorithms at different distances without any image enhancement methods.

3. **Siamese network:** This stage leverages a Siamese network, which contains two CNNs. They have the same architecture and the same weights. Therefore, for example, if the same two images are introduced in the Siamese network the same outputs would be obtained in both. It can be used with any face verification algorithm. In this research, the four selected ones are explored. The inputs are the two cropped faces that are going to be compared with each other. The size of both images is the same as the input required for the CNNs. The outputs are the features of each face converted into a vector. The length of each vector is different according to the definition of the algorithm, as can be seen in Table D.1.
4. **Distance calculation:** In this stage of the pipeline, the distance between the features of the faces is calculated. Two different metrics are used for the distance calculation: Euclidean distance and cosine distance, as described in the previous section. Meanwhile, more metrics can be explored, for instance, Manhattan distance. The metric used depends on the face verification algorithm in the Siamese network. Depending on how it obtains the features, one metric can perform better than others in determining if the faces are the same or not. Therefore, each algorithm has a better performance with one of the metrics.
5. **Decision making:** This is the most critical stage where a decision is made based on a threshold. If the distance is above the threshold, the faces are from different people; otherwise, they are the same person. Thus, it is crucial to define an appropriate threshold to be able to have the true positives while minimizing the false negatives.

Our main contribution at this stage is a size-adaptive dynamic threshold; depending on the size of the cropped face from the video, different thresholds are used. Just as the size of the image varies, so do the features obtained from the Siamese network. Thus, the distances between the faces will vary too. That is why a dynamic-distance-based threshold will improve the accuracy of the face verification algorithm, leading to more true positives and fewer false negatives. A different threshold will be used depending on the selection of the algorithm, the metric, and the distance between the face and the UAV (calculated in the last stage). Finally, the pipeline ends by showing the decision that is made: whether it is the same person or not. More details of the proposed threshold algorithm are presented in the next section.

Figure D.2: Block diagram of the proposed face verification pipeline composed of five stages: face detection, preprocessing, Siamese network, distance calculation, and decision making. There are two inputs: a video from a UAV and the face of the person to identify, and an output that is the decision.

D.4 Proposed Dynamic-Distance-Based Thresholding

The problems of the existing face verification algorithms and the distances at which they are least efficient have been identified and can be improved by defining appropriate thresholds for each distance.

In this section, a scale of sizes is defined and then the proposed distance-based thresholds are calculated for each range using a new algorithm. The calculations are data-driven as the thresholds are calculated based on the data obtained from a dataset.

D.4.1 Dataset Description

A new dataset of UAV-recorded human subjects has been created. This is due to the need for a dataset with a list of specific characteristics for our research and use case, and the fact of the lack of public availability of such an existing dataset.

This new dataset is composed of videos recorded from a UAV at different distances. The UAV used for the recording is a DJI Mini 2. The videos obtained have a resolution of 4K (3840×2160 pixels) and a frame rate of 30 FPS.

For the purpose of this research, 20 volunteers were recorded individually in an open field with no one else in the video—one face per video. Each video lasted 30 s, during which a human subject was asked to make head movements to obtain different angles of the face and to stare at the camera for a few seconds. Per subject, eight videos were recorded with each subject from different distances (2, 5, 7, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 m). Figure D.3 shows the distances arranged for the recordings. The distances are measured from the face of the subject to the UAV camera, and in all cases the UAV has 30 degrees of elevation above the face of the person. The dataset contains 60 images of each person per distance; as there are eight distances, the total number of images per person is 480 plus the identity image. Therefore, the total number of images in the dataset is 9620. The identity face is a close image taken from a smartphone with the volunteer facing the camera. The height of the identity face in pixels is approximately 800 px.

The dataset has been divided arbitrarily into two subsets of the same size. One is going to be used for the calculation of the proposed thresholds in Section D.4 and the other for the comparison between the accuracy using the proposed and the original thresholds in Section D.6. A summary of the dataset can be seen in Table D.2.

It is worth noting that General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance is a critical consideration in our data-gathering process, as we are committed to respecting individuals'

Figure D.3: Schematic of the dataset recording distances.

privacy and adhering to the regulations. All the volunteers were asked to give informed consent to allow us to record their faces and to use them for the purpose of this research only.

The minimum distance of our videos is 2 m. This is a safe distance for the user with a small drone like the one used to record. At further distances, the volunteers felt more comfortable as they did not have a drone close to them. Therefore, to enhance the user experience, it is important to increase the accuracy of the face verification algorithms at long distances.

Moreover, Table D.3 shows the relation between the distance of the face from the UAV and the average size in pixels of the face recorded. The large difference in size depending on the distance can be observed. These face sizes have been acquired using a 4k camera. If a lower resolution camera is used, the size of the face will be smaller too at each distance as the size of the whole image is also smaller.

Furthermore, Figure D.4 shows the cropped faces from the eight different distances of the dataset. In Figure D.4a, all features of the face can be seen without any problem. The person can easily be verified. On the other hand, in Figure D.4h it is challenging to verify the person of the image due to the low resolution and its small size.

Table D.2: Specifications of the novel created dataset

Number of people	20 volunteers
Distances recorded	2, 5, 7, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 metres
Videos resolution	4K (3840x2160 px)
Videos frame rate	30 FPS
Recording device	DJI Mini 2 Drone
Duration of each video	30 seconds
Total number of images	9620
Age range	18 - 60 years
Other characteristics	Different ethnicities Different genders Different lighting conditions
Dataset division	50% Thresholds Calculation 50% Testing

Table D.3: Distance from the camera to the face versus the size of the detected face in pixels

Distance	Size Face
2 m	125x170 px
5 m	80x98 px
7 m	50x59 px
10 m	38x44 px
15 m	25x31 px
20 m	20x24 px
25 m	17x19 px
30 m	14x19 px

D.4.2 Empirical Definition of Face Scale Based on Distance

To be able to calculate the new dynamic thresholds, a new scale for them has to be established. Two different approaches can be adopted to define the new scale. The first one uses the distances from the face to the UAV's onboard camera. Depending on the distance of the person, one threshold or another is applied. This approach has several problems. For example, it is hard to know exactly the distance from the face. The UAV should have a rangefinder mounted to be able to find the distance. However, not all UAVs have one mounted, thereby being unable to take this approach. Moreover, if the resolution of the camera varies, the size of the detected face in pixels will vary too. Therefore, we can have different face sizes for

Figure D.4: Cropped faces at the eight distances recorded.

one distance, depending on the resolution of the camera. That is why using the distance as a scale is not efficient or useful.

The alternative and more advantageous approach is to directly utilise the size of the face for the scale. One threshold would be applied depending on the pixels of the face. Moreover, by taking this approach and knowing the resolution of the camera, the distance to the face could be calculated approximately if needed.

Once the approach is determined, the scale has to be created. As Table D.3 shows, there are major changes in the width rather than the height of the image. Hence, the thresholds will be decided depending on the width of the face. Then, the scale is defined using four different ranges, as Figure D.5 shows. It also shows which distances of our dataset each of the ranges cover. The principle of the proposed scale scheme is simple and intuitive, whilst the performance is effective. If the detected face width is less than 20 px, it will be considered that the face is very far and the corresponding threshold will be used. If the face width is between 20 and 32 px, the person is considered to be far and a second threshold will

be selected instead. If it is between 32 and 75 px, it is a medium distance, and if the face is larger than 75 px, the person is very close and then a corresponding threshold will be applied. The regions have been defined based on empirical experimentation and because those pixel values correspond to the different distances shown in Figure D.5.

Figure D.5: Scale of defined distances depending on the width of the cropped face.

By using this scale and changing the thresholds depending on the detected face width, it is expected to achieve an improvement in the accuracy of the face verification algorithms at all distances. Moreover, by adopting this approach we have made the system independent of the camera resolution because it only depends on the size in pixels of the face, not the distance to the person.

D.4.3 Methodology for Empirical Threshold Calculation

Algorithm 1 shows the proposed algorithm to calculate the dynamic-distance-based thresholds for each distance, metric, and face verification algorithm.

The verification set is composed of a close image of the face of each person appearing in the dataset named as ‘face identity’. Then, the positive pairs are the frames from the dataset associated with a specific identity and the same ‘face identity’ of that person. In contrast, the negative pairs include the same ‘face identity’, along with all the remaining frames that are not associated. The similarity index is defined as the distance between two faces. Therefore, each negative or positive pair will have an associated similarity index. A hyperparameter is used to iterate along the threshold candidates in the loop. Its value depends on the metric or the face verification algorithm used.

Algorithm 1 Proposed optimal threshold calculation algorithm.

Let us define the verification set (V) as one sample (V_i) of each one of the y face identities to be verified (V_i) and a dataset (D), composed of x samples (S_j) of the same face identities (F_i).

$$V = \sum_{i=0}^y V(i), D = \sum_{i=0}^y \sum_{j=0}^x F_i(S_j)$$

Let us create now the **Positive Pairs of identity I** , defined as:

$$P_I^+ = (V_i, \sum_{j=0}^x F_I(S_j))$$

And the **Negative Pairs of identity I** , defined as:

$$P_I^- = (V_i, \sum_{i=0}^y \sum_{j=0}^x \text{if}(i \neq I)[F_I(S_j)], \text{otherwise } 0)$$

Let us define the **similarity index of a pair** as: $E(x, y)$. And let us define the **minimum similarity index of all the positive pairs** as :

$$E_{min}^+ = \min(\sum_{i=0}^y E(P_i^+))$$

Analogously, let us define the **maximum similarity index of all the positive pairs** as:

$$E_{max}^+ = \max(\sum_{i=0}^y E(P_i^+))$$

Let us define the **hyperparameter** as the step used to iterate the threshold candidates in the *for* loop. The value depends on the algorithm and the metric (the cosine or Euclidean distance) used. And let us apply the proposed dynamic threshold calculation as follows:

Input: $P_I^+, P_I^-, E_{min}^+, E_{max}^+, \text{hyperparameter}$

Output: *Threshold, MaxAccuracy*

Initialise *threshold* = 0, *MaxAccuracy* = 0

Calculate Ratio of all Positive Pairs:

$$R(P^+) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^y \text{Size}(P_i^+)}{\sum_{i=0}^y \text{Size}(P_i^+) + \sum_{i=0}^y \text{Size}(P_i^-)}$$

Calculate Ratio of all Negative Pairs:

$$R(P^-) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^y \text{Size}(P_i^-)}{\sum_{i=0}^y \text{Size}(P_i^+) + \sum_{i=0}^y \text{Size}(P_i^-)}$$

for *candidate* = E_{min}^+ ; *candidate* < E_{max}^+ ; *candidate* = *candidate* + *hyperparameter* **do**

$$TP = \text{count}(\sum_{i=0}^y \text{if}(E(P_i^+) < \text{candidate})) 1, \text{otherwise } 0$$

$$TN = \text{count}(\sum_{i=0}^y \text{if}(E(P_i^-) < \text{candidate})) 1, \text{otherwise } 0$$

$$A = 100 * \frac{TP * R(P^+) + TN * R(P^-)}{\sum_{i=0}^y \text{Size}(P_i^+) * R(P^+) + \sum_{i=0}^y \text{Size}(P_i^-) * R(P^-)}$$

if $A > \text{MaxAccuracy}$ **then**

$$\text{MaxAccuracy} = A$$

$$\text{Threshold} = \text{candidate}$$

end if

end for

In the algorithm, first, two ratios are calculated, one for positive pairs and another for negative ones. As the number of samples in both pairs are different, this study establishes this ratio to provide the same importance to both pairs. Otherwise, the pairs with more samples (in this case the negative pairs) will have more importance when calculating the thresholds. Afterwards, a for loop is defined from the minimum (E_{min}^+) to the maximum similarity index (E_{max}^+) of all positive pairs using as step the hyperparameter.

The threshold candidate value is the one to be iterated. In the loop, the numbers of True Positives (TP) and True Negatives (TN) are calculated first. TP is calculated as the number of positive pairs whose similarity index is less than the threshold candidate. TN are the result of the number of negative pairs whose similarity index is less than the threshold candidate. Then, the accuracy is calculated using TP, TN, and the ratios previously calculated. The formula for the accuracy is as follows:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

where False Positives (FP) are the negative pairs similarity indexes that are higher than the threshold candidate and False Negatives (FN) are the positive pairs similarity indexes that are higher than the threshold candidate). The sum of TP and FN corresponds to all the positive pairs, and the sum of TN and FP corresponds to all the negative pairs. Therefore, the accuracy is calculated by dividing the sum of TP and TN by the sum of all positive and negative pairs, applying the ratios calculated.

Finally, if the accuracy is the maximum value calculated so far, the threshold candidate is the chosen threshold for this moment. When the loop finishes, the threshold candidate that achieves the highest accuracy will be the chosen one.

D.4.4 Application of the Proposed Methodology for Close (5 m) and Far (15 m) Distances

The thresholds will be calculated in order to maximise the accuracy in each range of the scale, as seen in the proposed algorithm (Algorithm 1). This section further explains how the algorithm works to maximise the accuracy.

Figure D.6 shows the graphics for the four face verification algorithms while using a cosine distance at 5 m. Figure D.7 is an analogous figure for 15 m. In each of these figures, two graphs are shown per the algorithms analysed. The first graph shows the distribution of the similarity indexes. It is composed of two plots: one for the positive pairs and another one for the negative pairs. The second graph shows the value of the accuracy as a function of the threshold. Additionally, this second graph shows the two plots depicting the original threshold and the proposed one.

Regarding the distributions of the similarity indexes, they have been obtained by executing the face verification pipeline on the created dataset using the four state-of-the-art algorithms analysed: ArcFace, SFace, Dlib, and VGG-Face. By using our own dataset, we have obtained well-distributed distances both for positive and negative pairs. The positive pair distances have been obtained by executing the pipeline using the videos of one person and comparing them with their photo. The negative pairs have been obtained in the opposite way, using the videos of one person and comparing them with the photos of the other people from the dataset, as explained in the proposed algorithm. The further apart the two different plots are, the greater the accuracy that will be achieved by returning more true positives whilst minimising the false ones. If they are too overlapped, it will be difficult to verify a person and many mistakes will occur. Nevertheless, by choosing an adequate threshold the accuracy can be maximised.

Let us focus, for instance, on ArcFace at 5 m using cosine distance Figure D.6a,e. In Figure D.6a, it can be seen that both plots are well separated, and thus high accuracy should be achieved. The positive pairs have lower values than the negative pairs. This is because the positive pairs are more similar than the negative ones, as they should be. In Figure D.6e,

Figure D.6: Distribution of the similarity indexes and accuracy by threshold at **5 m** of the four algorithms using **cosine distance** as metric. **(a)** Distribution of Similarity indexes of ArcFace. **(b)** Distribution of Similarity indexes of SFace. **(c)** Distribution of Similarity indexes of Dlib. **(d)** Distribution of Similarity indexes of VGG-Face. **(e)** Accuracy by threshold of ArcFace. **(f)** Accuracy by threshold of SFace. **(g)** Accuracy by threshold of Dlib. **(h)** Accuracy by threshold of VGG-Face.

the accuracy across the thresholds can be seen. Below 0.2, the accuracy is 50% because all the pairs would be identified as false due to none of the similarity indexes being below the threshold. Then, we have our proposed threshold in green and the original one in orange. As shown, there is an improvement in the accuracy of choosing the proposed one.

It is worth noting that the thresholds chosen do not match the maximum of the accuracy plots. This is because what has been maximised is a range of our scale and not every distance of the UAV from the face. Therefore, what is optimised is a range of distances rather than every fixed distance.

Notice how at 15 m, for instance, Figure D.7a, the plots of the distribution of the positive and negative pairs are more overlapped. This is due to the fact that the faces are increasingly different as their resolution is lowered. Therefore, it is more difficult to choose an optimal threshold. However, it can be seen in the distribution of positive pairs that there is a tail to the left, which facilitates the presence of a substantial number of true positives, even in cases of plot overlap.

All of the algorithms approximately maintain their distribution, but the positive pairs have moved to the right. This supports the necessity of varying the thresholds depending on the distance to the face.

Figures D.8 and D.9 show analogous results but using Euclidean distance as metric. As can be seen, the plots are further apart and do not overlap much. By using Euclidean distance, the value of the thresholds is greater than in cosine because the similarity indexes also have greater values. The cosine distance range is limited between 0 and 2, while the Euclidean distance range is unlimited.

In all figures at 15 m (Figure D.9a–d), it can be seen that the positive pairs plots are shifted to the right: the two pairs of faces are less alike. This is due to the fact that the resolution is lower as the face is further from the drone, so the two faces are going to be more different.

The use of our dynamic thresholds will not significantly increase the computational requirements of a face verification system. Instead of having one fixed threshold for all the distances, in the proposed scheme a threshold will be dynamically selected based on

Figure D.7: Distribution of similarity indexes and accuracy by threshold at **15 m** of the four algorithms using **cosine distance** as metric. (a) Distribution of Similarity indexes of ArcFace. (b) Distribution of Similarity indexes of SFace. (c) Distribution of Similarity indexes of Dlib. (d) Distribution of Similarity indexes of VGG-Face. (e) Accuracy by threshold of ArcFace. (f) Accuracy by threshold of SFace. (g) Accuracy by threshold of Dlib. (h) Accuracy by threshold of VGG-Face.

Figure D.8: Distribution of similarity indexes and accuracy by threshold at **5 m** of the four algorithms using **Euclidean distance** as metric. **(a)** Distribution of Similarity indexes of ArcFace. **(b)** Distribution of Similarity indexes of SFace. **(c)** Distribution of Similarity indexes of Dlib. **(d)** Distribution of Similarity indexes of VGG-Face. **(e)** Accuracy by threshold of ArcFace. **(f)** Accuracy by threshold of SFace. **(g)** Accuracy by threshold of Dlib. **(h)** Accuracy by threshold of VGG-Face.

Figure D.9: Distribution of the similarity indexes and accuracy by threshold at **15 m** of the four algorithms using **Euclidean distance** as metric. **(a)** Distribution of Similarity indexes of ArcFace. **(b)** Distribution of Similarity indexes of SFace. **(c)** Distribution of Similarity indexes of Dlib. **(d)** Distribution of Similarity indexes of VGG-Face. **(e)** Accuracy by threshold of ArcFace. **(f)** Accuracy by threshold of SFace. **(g)** Accuracy by threshold of Dlib. **(h)** Accuracy by threshold of VGG-Face.

the distance to the person. Our technique will only add 1 us to the execution time of the pipeline. As the selection is not complex, the computational requirements or the power consumption will not vary greatly. Furthermore, our system will still work in different operational conditions. For instance, in crowded environments, the threshold will be adjusted for the size of each of the faces detected. Moreover, in adverse weather conditions, our proposed technique will also work as far as the face detection algorithm is able to detect faces correctly under such circumstances. Finally, it is worth highlighting that the empirical work of this paper is based on real implementation of the proposed system.

D.4.5 Recommended Thresholds for the Selected Face Verification Algorithms

Tables D.4 and D.5 show the proposed dynamic-distance-based thresholds calculated for each range of the scale for both cosine and Euclidean distance, respectively. They are the result of applying the proposed algorithm (Algorithm 1) to every range, face verification algorithm, and metric selected.

Table D.4: Calculated dynamic thresholds for cosine distance as metric

Algorithm	Very Far	Far	Medium	Close
ArcFace	0.9522	0.9433	0.7958	0.7476
SFace	0.9	0.826	0.772	0.722
Dlib	0.1245	0.1084	0.0882	0.0829
VGGFace	0.5241	0.4623	0.3924	0.3788

Table D.5: Calculated dynamic thresholds for Euclidean distance as metric

Algorithm	Very Far	Far	Medium	Close
ArcFace	9.65	5.29	4.91	4.65
SFace	10.916	11.124	10.659	10.743
Dlib	0.721	0.662	0.603	0.59
VGGFace	0.62	0.581	0.528	0.5

D.5 Implementation

As mentioned before, four different face verification algorithms are explored: ArcFace, SFace, Dlib, and VGG-Face. For the empirical calculation of the threshold, a common framework where all of them are integrated is created in the same machine in this research. The implemented framework is referred to as DeepFace and includes four different face verification algorithms with their pre-trained weights and two different distance calculation metrics [130, 131].

It also implements several face detection algorithms such as RetinaFace [42], MTCNN [120], Dlib [181], or Face-SSD [192]. As mentioned, RetinaFace is the face detection algorithm used in this research. It has been chosen due to its great accuracy at all distances in our dataset. It was able to detect faces even at 30 m with a small reduced number of false positives. As this paper is focused on the face verification algorithms, there is no analysis of the face detection algorithms, and, therefore, the one with the best performance on our dataset was the one chosen.

Deepface is run on Python version 3.8. The library is mainly powered by TensorFlow [176] and Keras [161]. For the preprocessing and postprocessing of the videos, OpenCV is used. The framework has been executed on the same machine using a Focal Ubuntu version 20.04.3. Pycharm is the IDE (Integrated Development Environment) used to write and execute the code. The threshold calculations were performed using GNU Octave.

The proposed pipeline has been implemented using the mentioned framework. The proposed algorithm and associated techniques have been integrated to the four state-of-the-art face verification algorithms on the same testbed for evaluation and comparison purposes.

D.6 Experimental Results

D.6.1 Testbed Description

All experiments were carried out on a single NVIDIA GeForce GTX TITAN X (Nvidia Corporation, Santa Clara, California) with 12 GB of onboard memory. The experiments

were repeated five times, and the average of the results of the five runs was then calculated to obtain the final results. The UAV used to obtain the videos is a Mini 2 model created by DJI. The videos were recorded with 4K resolution (3840×2160 px) at 30 FPS.

D.6.2 Empirical Validation of the Improvement Achieved by the Dynamic Thresholding Technique Proposed for UAV-Based Face Verification

The accuracy is compared between the original thresholds and the proposed ones. Table D.6 shows the accuracy using the proposed thresholds and with the cosine distance as metric, and Table D.7 shows the accuracy using Euclidean distance.

Figure D.10 illustrates the accuracy of the four face verification algorithms depending on the distance using the cosine distance as the metric. It shows the accuracy both using the proposed thresholds and the original ones. It is important to mention that our proposed technique improves all the analyzed face verification algorithms, and thus it is not tailored for a concrete algorithm. For instance, in VGG-Face (Figure D.10d) the best improvement is achieved at long distances, whilst at close distances, the accuracy is not greatly increased as it already had good results. Both ArcFace and Dlib have a greater improvement at medium and far distances. SFace (Figure D.10b) has improved the accuracy in all instances, with more than a 25% of improvement at some distances.

Table D.6: Accuracy of the algorithms at different distances using our dynamic thresholds - Cosine Distance

Algorithm	2m	5m	7m	10m	15m	20m	25m	30m
ArcFace	91.91	91.55	88.19	81.41	71.96	65.59	58.82	56.39
SFace	83.74	81.41	81.48	79.13	75.04	73.76	71.81	65.70
Dlib	83.26	81.97	79.58	75.68	68.67	61.95	57.21	54.22
VGG-Face	93.39	91.69	90.09	85.87	76.42	71.49	65.43	64.10

Then, Figure D.11 shows the accuracy of each algorithm for both thresholds using Euclidean distance as a metric. In contrast to cosine, if using the VGG-Face algorithm, a better improvement is achieved at close distances (Figure D.11d), but still, the accuracy is

Figure D.10: Accuracy of the algorithms at fixed distances using the original and the proposed thresholds and cosine distance as metric.

lower than that of using cosine. In the ArcFace algorithm, similar results are obtained, and there are greater improvements at close and medium distances (Figure D.11a), whilst at long distances, the accuracy does not improve much. One conclusion that can be drawn from this is that Euclidean distance is not optimal for these algorithms as the accuracy does not improve at long distances, which is where it is needed most for a UAV use case. Dlib (Figure D.11c) improves at far distances, while at close distances the same results are obtained.

SFace (Figure D.11b) has minimum improvement while using Euclidean distance as a metric. It can be seen that SFace does not have good accuracy while using this metric. The proposed thresholds are all very close to the original one; therefore, the improvement is minimal. This algorithm could not be improved using our method of Euclidean distance.

On the other hand, as seen previously, while using cosine distance (Figure D.10b) there is a high improvement in accuracy. Therefore, it can be concluded that SFace performs far better while using cosine distance than while using Euclidean distance.

Table D.7: Accuracy of the algorithms at different distances using our dynamic thresholds - Euclidean distance

Algorithm	2m	5m	7m	10m	15m	20m	25m	30m
ArcFace	91.69	89.57	85.91	77.17	61.52	52.28	50.58	50.41
SFace	76.70	72.81	73.51	70.41	67.27	62.23	60.64	56.80
Dlib	84.19	83.18	81.07	77.55	69.70	62.47	58.07	56.42
VGG-Face	82.47	81.19	77.36	75.28	64.45	62.83	58.84	57.17

As can be seen, there is a huge improvement in accuracy when the new thresholds are used. This improvement is more significant at long distances where the accuracy was very low with the original thresholds as they were optimised for close distances. For instance, at 20 m with ArcFace and cosine distance, an improvement of 15% in accuracy has been achieved.

To the best of our knowledge, existing face verification studies simply apply a static fixed threshold to the distance between the embeddings as their thresholding technique. In these results, we have shown that when executing face verification algorithms from drones, the accuracy can be significantly improved by applying a dynamic threshold depending on the distance instead of using a fixed threshold.

Our system has some limitations that are the same as the ones of the face verification algorithms being used. If the algorithm cannot perform correctly at a specific distance, our dynamic thresholds will not be able to increase its accuracy significantly.

D.6.3 Empirical Validation of the Best Similarity Index Based on the Selected Algorithm

Table D.8 shows, with each metric, at which distances the greatest improvements are achieved. Also, the final column shows which metric is better to use with each algorithm. Dlib is the only one that achieves a greater performance using Euclidean distance at all distances.

It is worth mentioning that the proposed technique is able to enhance the accuracy of all the proposed face verification algorithms using any of the similarity metrics analysed. Thus,

Figure D.11: Accuracy of the algorithms at fixed distances using the original and the proposed thresholds and Euclidean distance as metrics.

it has been proven that the methodology and approach provided in this contribution is robust enough to be considered in this kind of AI pipeline.

D.6.4 Analysis of Inference Times

The speed of the pipeline is assessed by measuring the inference time. It is defined as the time spent since the frame enters the processing pipeline until the decision is received, and it is measured empirically to compare the speed of the algorithms. Figure D.12 shows the cumulative average inference time per frame. A great difference between the face verification algorithms can be appreciated.

VGG-Face is by far the slowest algorithm. When used, the inference time takes approximately 275 ms, and we can only achieve a maximum processing speed of 4 FPS. On the

Table D.8: Distances at which the greatest improvements are achieved with each metric and what is the recommended metric to use with each algorithm.

Algorithm	Improvement with Cosine Distance	Improvement with Euclidean Distance	Metric Recommended
ArcFace	All distances	Close Distances	Cosine Distance
SFace	All distances	None distance	Cosine Distance
Dlib	All distances	Far distances	Euclidean Distance
VGG-Face	Far distances	Close distances	Cosine distance - Close distances Euclidean distance - Far distances

other hand, Dlib is the fastest algorithm. The pipeline processes each frame in approximately 180 ms. Furthermore, it is noted that RetinaFace takes approximately 165 ms, which means that Dlib can obtain the features in less than 15 ms.

The second fastest algorithm is SFace, with approximately 220 ms per frame. Finally, ArcFace is the second slowest algorithm, taking approximately 230 ms per frame to obtain the result of the pipeline.

Our distance-based thresholds do not add any significant delay to the system as one threshold or another will be selected based on the size of the face. Our technique will only add 1 us to the execution time of the pipeline. The calculation of the thresholds using the proposed algorithm will be made before the system is deployed. Therefore, the threshold selection will be almost instant, and real-time processing could be achieved by improving the face detection and verification algorithms.

D.7 Concluding remarks

This paper presents a novel technique to perform face verification by modifying the thresholds depending on the distance of the UAV from the face. Moreover, an empirical study of four state-of-the-art face verification algorithms has been performed including a comparison with the proposed technique.

By adding the dynamic size-adaptive thresholds to the face verification pipeline, we have significantly improved the accuracy of these face verification algorithms. Furthermore, two metrics have been employed to conduct the comparison (cosine and Euclidean distance).

Figure D.12: Cumulative average of the inference time in milliseconds per frame for each algorithm.

Another analysis has been performed to conclude which of the metrics better suits each algorithm in order to achieve higher accuracy for face verification.

Empirical results have shown that a high improvement in the accuracy of the face verification algorithms at different distances has been achieved. Using the ArcFace algorithm at 20 m with cosine distance as a metric, there is an improvement of 15% in the accuracy. The SFace algorithm has been improved by more than 20% at some distances. At 30 m and using cosine distance, the VGG-Face algorithm has improved its accuracy by 10%.

Our proposed thresholding algorithm has improved all four face verification algorithms used. This proves that by using a dynamic threshold, the accuracy of the face verification algorithms can be improved, leading to fewer false positives and maximising the true ones. Furthermore, our technique is not limited to UAV-based public safety use cases and can be applied to any application domain where face verification is required, such as intruder detection in industrial premises.

For future work, an enhanced dataset can be created using more people at more distances and angles from the UAV to the face. The lighting is important too because in the dataset for this research, the data were obtained in various light conditions. For future research, more lighting conditions can be considered to have a more complex and complete dataset, for example, at night or low visibility.

Moreover, the thresholds have been calculated to maximise the accuracy, but other metrics can be maximised. For example, the same calculations can be made but maximising the F1-Score or defining a maximum acceptable value of false positives. The maximised metric would vary depending on the use case.

Some potential future research directions involve integrating other techniques to improve the accuracy of the algorithms depending on the environment. For instance, light or image enhancement methods can be added to increase the brightness or resolution of the images. Furthermore, the backbones of the algorithms can also be modified to increase the accuracy by adding or modifying layers while trying not to reduce their speed.

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Appendix E

Face Verification Algorithms for UAV Applications: An Empirical Comparative Analysis

Please note that this chapter contains a copy of content present in the research paper [5], and that, therefore, it has already been peer-reviewed and accepted.

Abstract

Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) are revolutionising diverse computer vision use case domains, from public safety surveillance to Search and Rescue (SAR), and other emergency management and disaster relief operations. The growing need for accurate face verification algorithms has prompted an exploration of synergies between UAVs and face verification. This promises cost-effective, wide-area, non-intrusive person verification. Real-world human-centric use cases such as a "Drone Guard Angel" for vulnerable people can contribute to public safety management and offload significant police resources. These scenarios demand efficient face verification to distinguish correctly the end users for authentication, authorisation and customised services.

This paper investigates the suitability of existing solutions, and analyses five state-of-the-art candidate face verification algorithms. Informed by the advantages and disadvantages of existing solutions, the paper proposes an extended dataset and a refined face verification pipeline. Subsequently, it conducts empirical evaluation of these algorithms using the proposed pipeline and dataset in terms of inference times and the distribution of the similarity indexes. Furthermore, this paper provides essential guidance for algorithm selection and deployment in UAV-based applications. Two candidate algorithms, ArcFace and FaceNet512, have emerged as the top performers. The choice between them will depend on the specific use case requirements.

E.1 Introduction

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) have gained momentum in recent years as a novel and transformative technology, finding applications across diverse domains, from surveillance and security applications [193][194] to SAR operations [157]. Moreover, the demand for effective and accurate face verification algorithms has become increasingly pronounced. These algorithms have become widely used in different applications but they have several limitations like restricted coverage or the inability to track individuals, as it is mostly performed from fixed camera systems [195].

The combination of both technologies - UAVs and face verification - can achieve a breakthrough in the capacity to verify people at a low cost, covering large areas fast and from a high distance, thereby preserving the safety of the individual without being an intrusive method.

A number of use cases have explored this combination. For example, the Drone Guard Angel in the EU Horizon 2020 project ARCADIAN-IoT [9]. It is a public safety management service: an UAV will go to the position of a user who has requested the service, the user's face will be verified, and then the UAV will accompany the user ensuring that the user arrives at the destination safely. Furthermore, yet another use case can be surveillance network

applications in the EU Horizon 2020 project 5G-INDUCE [152], where the UAV pilot identity will be verified before the start of the operation.

The emergence of these applications has underscored the need for highly accurate and fast face verification algorithms capable of functioning effectively with UAV video feeds. Some challenges arise while dealing with images from UAVs. For instance, the long distances from UAVs to human faces result in low-pixel resolution, making it more difficult to verify the users [196]. Moreover, UAVs must deal with adverse environmental factors such as low lighting conditions during night-time operations. Moreover, there can be rapid changes in the pose and positioning of a person or sudden movement of the UAV. Notably, there is a lack of practical solutions in the literature regarding face verification from UAVs. This research work is based on [1], which has provided a preliminary study regarding face verification algorithms. This paper expands that research by conducting a more comprehensive analysis of state-of-the-art algorithms.

In this research paper, five state-of-the-art face verification algorithms are compared, in terms of accuracy, inference and building time and the size of the weights. The analysis is performed using an extended dataset with videos at six fixed distances: 2, 5, 7, 10, 15 and 20 metres. In order to perform the experiments, an enhanced face verification pipeline has been designed and implemented to support different similarity index calculations. Furthermore, an up-to-date literature review on face verification algorithms is conducted. In summary, this study's principal contributions are as follows:

- Design and implementation of an enhanced face verification pipeline to conduct the experiments using different similarity index calculations.
- Expansion of the UAV recorded dataset (UAV-UWS) to add two additional distances to have a more comprehensive dataset.
- An empirical analysis of the inference time in a face verification pipeline using five state-of-the-art algorithms.
- An empirical evaluation of five state-of-the-art face verification algorithms, yielding practical insights into their suitability for application in UAV-based scenarios.

The structure of this paper is outlined as follows. Section II provides an overview of state-of-the-art face verification algorithms. Section III presents the dataset expansion, the design of the pipeline, and the implementation. The testbed, experimental results and findings are presented and discussed in Section IV. Finally, Section V concludes the paper.

E.2 Related Work

In recent years, the utilisation of UAVs has experienced a remarkable surge across numerous applications. One of the most important advancements attributed to drones is their ability to perform operations that were before extremely expensive at a considerably reduced cost. One of the use cases is border surveillance, where UAVs can cover extensive territories easily at a low cost [197]. Another notable application is SAR operations, which used to require the deployment of helicopters at a high economic cost. By using UAVs the operations can be performed easier and explore larger areas in less time by employing multiple UAVs. Furthermore, the incorporation of object detection algorithms using optical or thermal cameras in the UAVs has significantly increased the effectiveness of these operations, resulting in a higher number of successful rescues.[198][163]

Several research papers have explored the utilisation of drones in face verification applications, often employing simple yet fast algorithms, like LBP Histogram (LBPH) [64]. These algorithms are usually lightweight models that are suitable for embedded systems like a UAV companion computer. However, the situation transforms when a high-speed connection can be established between a Ground Control Station (GCS) like QGroundControl [114] and the UAV. In this context, high-performance algorithms with large models can be executed in a high-spec computer where the GCS or other software is running and the UAV will only have to send video. [187]

Furthermore, prior research papers have analysed the influence of factors such as distance and height on the accuracy of face recognition algorithms using UAVs [65]. In [46] face recognition and distance estimation are performed from UAV-captured data using a Siamese

Table E.1: Comparative between state-of-the-art face verification algorithms

Ref	Algorithm	Input Size	Output Size	Verification Accuracy		Weights size	Training Images
				on LFW dataset [57]	on YTF dataset [58]		
[67]	Human-beings	N/A	N/A	97.53%	NG	N/A	N/A
[68]	Deep-Face	152x152x3	4096	97.35%	91.40%	551 MB	4.4M
[69]	OpenFace	96x96x3	128	92.92%	NG	14 MB	0.5M
[70]	VGG-Face	224x224x3	2622	98.95%	97.30%	554 MB	2.6M
[71]	CosFace	112x96x3	NG	99.73%	97.60%	214 MB	5M
[72]	DeepID2	55x47x3	160	99.53%	93.20%	1.6 MB	0.2M
[73]	ArcFace	112x112x3	512	99.83%	98.02%	131 MB	5.8M
[74]	FaceNet	160x160x3	128	98.87%	95.12%	88 MB	200M
[75]	FaceNet512	160x160x3	512	99.60%	NG	91 MB	200M
[76]	Dlib	150x150x3	128	99.38%	NG	22 MB	3M
[77]	SphereFace	112x96x3	512	99.42%	95.00%	69 MB	0.5M
[78]	AdaFace	112x112x3	NG	99.82%	NG	668 MB	15.1M
[79]	DAM-R	112x112x3	NG	99.03%	95.23%	NG	1.5M
[80]	CurricularFace	112x112x3	NG	99.80%	NG	249 MB	6.3M

NG = Not Given; N/A = Not applicable

network. Different architectures can be used for face recognition on UAVs as analysed in [66], that compares ResNet-50 and SENet.

It is important to clarify the distinction between two key terms: face recognition and face verification [8]. The fundamental difference is that face recognition needs a database because it aims to tell which person a face belongs to. On the other hand, face verification just compares two faces and decides whether the face belongs to the same person or to a different one. In this research paper, only face verification is going to be analysed as two faces will be compared: one is the reference or identity face, and the other is the face of an unidentified person.

Table E.1 shows an in-depth comparison among different face verification algorithms available in the literature. It has been expanded from our previous preliminary work [1] to add more parameters and up-to-date algorithms. The verification performance and the different parameters of each algorithm have been obtained from its official paper. In the table, different parameters are compared, such as the input and output size of the neural network, the number of images used for training and the size of the weights file. This last parameter is useful in case the algorithm wants to be embedded in a companion computer in the UAV, as large models are not going to be able to be embedded. Moreover, the verification accuracy is compared using the most common verification datasets for face recognition and verification:

Labeled Faces in the Wild (LFW) [57] and Youtube Faces (YTF) [58]. The evaluation in the LFW is conducted using 6000 face pairs while in the YTF 5000 face pairs are used.

The first row of the table shows the performance that human beings have on the LFW dataset. The accuracy obtained is 97.53% [67] and it will be our reference for the comparison of the accuracy of the face verification algorithms. Two algorithms do not surpass this accuracy: Deep-Face [68] with 97.35% and OpenFace [69] with 92.92%.

The algorithms that achieve the highest accuracy in the LFW dataset are ArcFace [73], AdaFace [78] and CurricularFace [80] with 99.83%, 99.82% and 99.8% respectively. Regarding the YTF dataset, ArcFace is the one which achieves the highest accuracy. It is important to mention that not all algorithms have been evaluated on the YTF dataset. For instance, we have no information for AdaFace, CurricularFace or FaceNet512 [75] algorithms.

Moreover, not all the algorithms report the output size of the neural network, which will be the size of the obtained feature vector. The algorithm with the biggest length is Deep-Face with 4096 while the smallest are FaceNet [74] and OpenFace with 128. Regarding the size of the weights file, the biggest ones are AdaFace, VGG-Face [70] and Deep-Face making them large models. The smallest are DeepID2 [72], OpenFace and Dlib [76], making them light models, and easily embedded.

SphereFace [77] is an algorithm that has not been trained with many images (only 0.5 million) but achieves high accuracy on the LFW dataset (99.42%). CosFace [71] achieves high accuracy on the LFW and YTF datasets. However, it has not been selected due to the lack of information in the available literature. DAM-R [79] is a novel algorithm that achieves high accuracy on the LFW dataset but underperforms in the YTF dataset compared with the other algorithms.

Finally, FaceNet and FaceNet512 algorithms were trained with the highest number of images (200 million), followed by AdaFace with 15.1 million. The difference between both FaceNet algorithms is that FaceNet512 [75] is an extended version of FaceNet [74] that has a 512 vector as output instead of 128, increasing the verification performance as can be seen in the table.

In our previous work [1], three algorithms were chosen to perform an analysis on UAV-based use cases: ArcFace [73], VGG-Face [70] and FaceNet512 [75]. In this paper, our research has been expanded by incorporating two additional algorithms present in Table E.1: OpenFace [69] and Dlib [76].

The inclusion of these two algorithms was driven by various considerations. OpenFace, while not delivering the highest accuracy, distinguishes itself as a lightweight and fast algorithm. Moreover, Dlib has a high accuracy, surpassing human performance, while also being a lightweight model. By introducing these two lightweight algorithms, we aim to facilitate a comprehensive comparative analysis, allowing us to contrast them with algorithms known for their higher accuracy but slower inference speeds.

Furthermore, many metrics can be used to calculate the similarity indexes between two faces, such as Euclidean distance [199], Manhattan distance [200], and cosine distance [201]. This paper, as opposed to the previous work [1], is going to use two different metrics: cosine distance and Euclidean distance. These are two of the most used metrics for distance calculation in the literature.

Cosine distance [201] has two vectors as inputs and the result will be a number that signifies the similarity index between the vectors. It is calculated as shown in Equation E.1:

$$CD(\vec{x}, \vec{y}) = 1 - \frac{\sum_1^n x_i y_i}{\sqrt{\sum_1^n x_i^2} \sqrt{\sum_1^n y_i^2}} \quad (\text{E.1})$$

Here, \vec{x} and \vec{y} are the feature vectors of two different faces. The result of the calculation is the similarity index between them, which will be within the range of 0 and 2. A similarity index of 0 indicates that the faces are exactly alike while if the result is 2 means that the two faces are opposite.

Moreover, we have Euclidean distance [199]. This metric also takes two feature vectors as inputs. The results will be the similarity index between them. The Euclidean distance can be calculated as shown in Equation E.2:

$$ED(\vec{x}, \vec{y}) = \sqrt{\sum_1^n (x_i - y_i)^2} \quad (\text{E.2})$$

Once again, \vec{x} and \vec{y} represent the feature vectors of two different faces. Greater similarity indexes mean that the faces are less similar whereas small values signify that the faces are more alike.

E.3 Design and Implementation of the Proposed System

E.3.1 UAV-UWS dataset

In our previous preliminary work [1], a dataset was introduced, known as the UAV-UWS dataset. It was a UAV-recorded dataset at four fixed distances from the volunteers: 5, 7, 10 and 15 metres. This research extends this dataset by incorporating two additional distances: 2 and 20 metres, thereby significantly enlarging the face verification range from 5 to 15 meters to 2 to 20 meters. This addition improves the dataset's overall comprehensiveness.

The 2-metre distance helps evaluate how well the algorithms perform at very close ranges, which is the closest safe distance of operating a UAV in front of volunteers. Furthermore, the addition of the 20-metre distance allows us to assess the performance of the face verification algorithms at a greater distance and identify where their accuracy decreases significantly, making them ineffective. The extension of the UAV-UWS dataset enables a more thorough evaluation of the algorithms to the greatest extent for the UAV platform used.

Therefore, this UAV-UWS dataset has been created and expanded by recordings at six different distances: 2, 5, 7, 10, 15 and 20 metres. These videos were recorded using a DJI Mini 2 UAV with 4K resolution (3840x2160 px) at a frame rate of 30 Frames per second (FPS). The dataset includes videos of 20 volunteers representing diverse age groups, genders and ethnicities, resulting in a more inclusive and diverse dataset.

The recording angle was set at 30 degrees to ensure that the volunteers did not need to strain their necks to face the UAV directly. Table E.2 shows the vertical and horizontal distance from the face to the UAV for each of the recording distances in our dataset. Each video has a duration of 30 seconds, during which volunteers were asked to perform a range of head movements, including facing down, up, left and right, making head circles, and staring directly at the UAV. This allows us to have a comprehensive range of the features of

Table E.2: Vertical, horizontal and direct distance from the UAV to the face of the volunteers with a recording angle of 30 degrees.

Direct distance	Horizontal distance	Vertical distance
2 m	1.7 m	1.0 m
5 m	4.3 m	2.5 m
7 m	6.0 m	3.5 m
10 m	8.7 m	5.0 m
15 m	13 m	7.5 m
20 m	17 m	10 m

each face and analyse how the algorithms perform when volunteers are not facing the UAV directly.

Figure E.1: Example of a cropped face at the six distances recorded in the dataset

Furthermore, the dataset also contains a close image of each volunteer taken with a smartphone. This will be the identity face that will be compared with the ones from the UAV videos. Fig E.1 shows one example of a cropped face from the UAV-UWS dataset at each distance: 2, 5, 7, 10, 15 and 20 metres. Moreover, Table E.3 shows the relation between the average face size in pixels versus the distance from the camera of the UAV. These values have been obtained using our dataset and therefore images with 4K resolution (3840x2160 px).

The UAV-UWS dataset will not be publicly released due to GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) considerations as it contains personal information for the volunteers.

E.3.2 Design of the face verification pipeline

One of the primary contributions of this study lies in the conceptualisation and realisation of a pipeline for executing face verification and obtaining empirical results, as depicted in

Table E.3: Average face size in pixels at different distances from the camera of the UAV.

Distance	Size Face
2 m	125x170 px
5 m	80x100 px
7 m	50x60 px
10 m	40x45 px
15 m	25x30 px
20 m	20x25 px

Figure E.2: Enhanced pipeline used to obtain the results from the experiments. It is divided into four stages: face detection, preprocessing, Siamese network, and similarity index calculation.

Figure E.2. The pipeline operates on a pair of input images. The first image is extracted from a video frame captured by a UAV within our proprietary dataset. The second input image corresponds to the facial image of the individual undergoing verification, captured at close proximity using a mobile device. The ultimate outcome of this pipeline is a similarity index quantifying the likeness between the target individual’s face and the face within the video frame. The pipeline comprises four distinct stages:

1. Face Detection: This initial stage of our pipeline employs the RetinaFace algorithm, chosen for its superior accuracy in long-distance face detection. Although RetinaFace might not be the fastest face detection algorithm available, its speed is not a significant concern for our research’s objectives, which focus solely on face verification algorithms.

RetinaFace takes an image as input and yields the coordinates of all detected faces within the image, along with the associated detection accuracy.

2. **Preprocessing:** This stage is divided into two additional steps. The first one involves cropping the face from the image using the coordinates provided by RetinaFace. Then, the face is resized to match the input dimensions required by the specific face verification algorithm employed. These input dimensions vary depending on the chosen algorithm as shown in Table E.1. Since the aspect ratio of the original face may differ from the input size, padding is applied to the image. Black pixels are added to the sides of the image to achieve the expected input dimensions. This approach ensures that the face is not distorted during the resizing process.
3. **Siamese network [68] [160]:** In the third stage of the pipeline a Siamese network is used. It is a frequently adopted configuration in the literature for face verification tasks. It comprises two identical Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with identical backbones and weights. When presented with the same input, these CNNs produce identical outputs. Each CNN takes as input a face resized to the required input dimensions. The output of these networks is a feature vector, whose dimensions vary based on the chosen algorithm. This vector represents the distinctive characteristics of the processed face.
4. **Similarity index calculation:** The final stage of the pipeline involves calculating the similarity index between the two feature vectors obtained from the Siamese network. It is important to note that this stage diverges from our prior conference paper's approach as outlined in [1]. In that research, the sole metric employed for index calculation was the cosine distance. However, in this paper, the flexibility of our approach has been expanded to allow the utilisation of various distance calculation metrics, such as Euclidean distance, Manhattan distance and cosine distance. The optimal distance calculation method varies depending on the face verification algorithm used.

Other authors have created similar approaches for a face verification pipeline but without further explanation about the preprocessing stage or having a fixed similarity index metric

[202]. Our pipeline allows swift changes in the similarity index metrics depending on the algorithm used. For example, we can switch between cosine distance, Euclidean distance, Manhattan distance, etc. Furthermore, our pipeline allows us to introduce other stages in the preprocessing in case further improvements to the images are needed, such as face alignment. Finally, the Siamese network allows faster execution of the pipeline as the identity features only need to be extracted in the first execution, as it will not change.

E.3.3 Implementation

The results presented in this study were obtained using a unified framework, where all five verification algorithms are implemented. The framework is denoted as DeepFace [130] [131] and includes the five face verification algorithms used. It also includes the face detection algorithm: RetinaFace and the two metrics used in this paper: cosine distance and Euclidean distance. Evaluating all the algorithms on a uniform platform ensures reliable and easily comparable results given that they were acquired under identical conditions.

DeepFace uses the Keras library [161] in a Python 3.8 environment. Additionally, the OpenCV Python library was employed for the image preprocessing. The computational environment for the implementation was a computer running Focal Ubuntu version 20.04.3.

The pipeline was meticulously executed employing all the five verification algorithms and evaluated with a common testbed. For the purposes of this comparative analysis, the algorithms were executed on a high-performance GPU. This setup simulates a scenario where the video feed from the UAV is transmitted to a computer for the execution of the pipeline.

E.4 Empirical Results and Discussion

E.4.1 Testbed description

The experiments were conducted on an NVIDIA GeForce GTX TITAN X with 12GB of onboard memory. These experiments were executed 10 times to obtain the final results. The

UAV used to record the dataset is a DJI Mini 2 with a 4K (3840x2160 px) camera and the videos have been recorded at 30 FPS.

It is noted that substantially more experiments have been conducted to produce a significantly larger number of comparative results, in contrast to the results reported in our preliminary work [1].

E.4.2 Comparison of different face verification algorithms

Build time and weights size

Table E.4 shows the model's build time and the size of the weights for each algorithm. As can be seen, FaceNet512 is the one with the highest building time, while VGG-Face has the lowest. Moreover, VGG-Face is the one with the largest weights file. The size of the weights file is important, for example, if the algorithm is going to be embedded in a system without a lot of memory onboard. In that case, the smaller the size of the file, the better. In addition, the build time is also significant as it shows us how long it is going to take the algorithm to initiate the verification process.

Table E.4: Comparative between build time and weights of each model

Algorithm	Build Time	Weights
ArcFace	1001 ms	131 MB
OpenFace	828 ms	15 MB
FaceNet512	2130 ms	91 MB
Dlib	144 ms	22 MB
VGGFace	758 ms	554 MB

Inference time

It is defined as the time it takes for one frame to complete a full pipeline execution. The inference time can be divided into four stages, the same as the processing pipeline. This allows for a comparison of the inference time of only the face verification algorithms, rather than the entire pipeline.

1. **Face Detection:** Using the RetinaFace algorithm in the pipeline, the face detection process takes approximately 165 ms. However, by employing a faster face detection algorithm, the pipeline's inference time can be reduced significantly. It is worth noting that this stage is the slowest of the pipeline.
2. **Preprocessing:** This time is independent of the algorithms used. This stage of the pipeline only takes around 0.3 ms, making it the fastest of the four stages.
3. **Siamese Network:** Only the time required for extracting the facial features from a face from the video is considered. This has been done because the features of the identity face are initially extracted at the beginning of the process and remain constant throughout. This eliminates the need for recalculations to speed up the process. The time taken for this stage varies depending on the face verification algorithm used, as shown in Figure E.3.
4. **Similarity index calculation:** The last stage is also independent of the algorithms used. The inference time is approximately the same for both metrics: cosine and Euclidean distance. It takes around 1 ms.

All the stages have fixed times for the five face verification algorithms used, except for the Siamese network stage. The cumulative average inference time for the five face verification algorithms is shown in Figure E.3, with improved visualisation compared with our preliminary work [1]. As a result, it is possible to see the evolution of the average inference time during a whole video, frame by frame.

The variations in the inference time depicted in Figure E.3 are exclusively due to which face verification algorithm is used. VGG-Face is clearly the slowest algorithm, while Dlib is the fastest. FaceNet512, ArcFace and OpenFace have similar inference times, with OpenFace being the fastest of the three.

It is worth noting that all the stages excluding the Siamese network have approximately a constant inference time of 167 ms. Therefore, the inference times of only the Siamese network for the face verification algorithms are VGG-Face 114 ms, FaceNet512 74 ms, ArcFace 64 ms, OpenFace 58 ms and Dlib 25 ms, respectively.

Figure E.3: Cumulative average of the inference time (milliseconds) per frame for each algorithm

Similarity indexes distribution

The similarity indexes were obtained for each of the five face verification algorithms at the six distances of our UAV-UWS dataset. They were obtained using the proposed pipeline designed and explained in Section III. They are divided into two different types: Positive pairs and negative pairs. The first ones were obtained by having the one that contains the same persons of the identity faces as the video input, i.e., we compare the image of the face of one person with a different image containing the face of the same person. On the other hand, the negative pairs were obtained using a video input that contains different people from the identity face, i.e., we compare the image of the face of one person with the image of another person. The negative pairs similarity indexes should be high, as two different people are compared and their similarity should be low. On the other hand, the positive pair similarity indexes should be low as two faces from the same person are compared.

In the graphs, the most important aspect to compare is the overlapping between the two plots. If the positive and negative pairs plots are highly overlapped, it is going to be

Figure E.4: Similarity indexes of the ArcFace face verification algorithm for 2, 5, 7, 10, 15 and 20 metres of distance

extremely difficult to define an optimal threshold, therefore the accuracy will be low, with a high number of false positives and negatives. On the other hand, if both plots are further apart, a threshold will be easy to define and the algorithm will have high accuracy.

As can be seen in all the graphs, the further the distance, the positive pairs plots shift more to the right. This occurs because as the UAV moves further from the person, the face is going to have lower resolution, so it is more difficult to appreciate the features of the face and therefore the similarity index is higher.

Firstly, let us focus on the ArcFace graphs (Figure E.4). At 2 (Figure E.4a) and 5 metres (Figure E.4b), it can be seen that both plots are well separated; therefore, it can be easy to define an optimal threshold. The specific position of the threshold can vary depending on the use case. If it is a high-security one with no false positives allowed, 0.6 will be an optimal value. If it is a more permissive use case, the threshold could be defined at around 0.75. At 7 metres (Figure E.4c), the positive pairs plot starts shifting to the right and starts to overlap with the negative pairs one, yet still, a high accuracy can be obtained. At 10 metres (Figure

Figure E.5: Similarity indexes of the VGG-Face face verification algorithm for 2, 5, 7, 10, 15 and 20 metres of distance

E.4d), a high quantity of positive pairs similarity indexes are completely overlapped with the negative pairs having a peak at around 0.9. The accuracy is not going to be very high, yet still, some good identifications can be obtained. At 15 metres (Figure E.4e), both plots are almost completely overlapped except for some values between 0.4 and 0.7, and the accuracy will be very low. Finally, at 20 metres (Figure E.4f), both plots are completely overlapped and it will not be possible to differentiate between two faces. Therefore, ArcFace will not be able to verify at distances higher than 15 metres.

Secondly, VGG-Face (Figure E.5) has good results at the first three distances: 2 (Figure E.5a), 5 (Figure E.5b) and 7 metres (Figure E.5c). Both plots are well separated in the three graphs. The peak of the negative pairs is around 0.5, while the positive pairs is at 0.2. At 10 metres (Figure E.5d), the plots start to become more overlapped but the peak of positive pairs is still not overlapped, so a high accuracy can still be obtained. At 15 metres (Figure E.5e), both plots are overlapped; however, still a considerable number of positive pairs similarity indexes are out of the overlapping, and thus reasonable accuracy can still be obtained. Finally,

Figure E.6: Similarity indexes of the FaceNet-512 face verification algorithm for 2, 5, 7, 10, 15 and 20 metres of distance

although the plots are highly overlapped at 20 metres (Figure E.5f), VGG-Face will verify the face at this distance with low accuracy, as some similarity indexes are still not overlapped.

Thirdly, FaceNet512 is the algorithm that has the best performance as seen in Figure E.6. All the graphs are well separated so it will be easy to define an optimal threshold and verify correctly most users. At 2 metres (Figure E.6a), both plots are almost completely separated so the accuracy will be very high with almost no false negatives or positives. At 5 (Figure E.6b), 7 (Figure E.6c) and 10 metres (Figure E.6d), the peak of the positive pairs similarity index is not overlapped so the accuracy will still be very high. At 15 (Figure E.6e) and 20 metres (Figure E.6f), the plots are more overlapped, although it is still possible to differentiate them; thus a decent threshold can be defined in order to maintain a good accuracy. FaceNet512 achieves very good results being able to verify at all distances using cosine distance as the metric.

Fourthly, let us scrutinise OpenFace (Figure E.7). Even at 2 metres (Figure E.7a), both plots are overlapped, although the main peak of the positive pairs is not, and thus it will

Figure E.7: Similarity indexes of the OpenFace face verification algorithm for 2, 5, 7, 10, 15 and 20 metres of distance

have reasonable accuracy. At 5 metres (Figure E.7b), the curves are highly overlapped, and thus it will be difficult to verify correctly unless the conditions are optimal. At 7 (Figure E.7c), 10 (Figure E.7d) and 15 metres (Figure E.7e), the same occurs respectively. The curves are almost completely overlapped, and hence there is a high probability of having false positives while verifying a person. Moreover, the choice of a threshold will be difficult and false positives will have to be assumed. At 20 metres (Figure E.7f), both plots are totally overlapped and it will not be possible to verify anybody correctly. It can be seen that OpenFace, as it is a lightweight model, will only have good accuracy at really close distances, and thus it will not be suitable for UAVs.

Fifthly and finally, Dlib is a fast algorithm as can be seen in Figure E.8 although it does not have a good performance. At 2 metres (Figure E.8a), most of the positive pairs plot is overlapped. Meanwhile, the main peak is below 0.05 (beginning of negative pairs plot), and thus some good results may be achievable. At 5 (Figure E.8b), 7 (Figure E.8c) and 10 metres (Figure E.8), the positive pairs plot starts to shift to the right, becoming highly overlapped

Figure E.8: Similarity indexes of the Dlib face verification algorithm for 2, 5, 7, 10, 15 and 20 metres of distance

with the negative pairs plot. In this situation, a high number of false positives and negatives will be obtained; therefore, the accuracy is going to be low. At 15 metres (Figure E.8e), both graphs are almost completely overlapped and as both start at around 0.05, it is not possible to have true positives without obtaining also false positives. The accuracy at this distance will be very low. At 20 metres (Figure E.8f), both plots are completely overlapped; therefore, the accuracy is going to be extremely low. The algorithm at this distance is not useful. Hence, despite Dlib being the fastest algorithm, the accuracy is low; consequently, it will not be useful for UAV use cases.

For further comparison, we have obtained the graphs for OpenFace at three different distances but using Euclidean distance as the metric to obtain the similarity indexes. As it can be seen in Figure E.9, the graphs are mostly similar to the ones obtained using the cosine distance (Figure E.7). OpenFace will perform similarly using cosine distance or Euclidean distance. Therefore, the use of one distance or the other will only vary the accuracy slightly. Hence, the recommendation of one distance calculator will depend on the algorithm and the

Figure E.9: Similarity indexes of the Dlib face verification algorithm for 2, 7 and 15 metres of distance using Euclidean distance as metric

specific use case. Further analysis will be needed when an algorithm has been selected to choose the optimal distance calculator. This can be obtained using the enhanced pipeline that admits any distance calculator, such as the previously mentioned cosine or Euclidean distance, but also Manhattan or Minkowski distance [203].

E.4.3 Discussion

Based on the results obtained, ArcFace achieves good results only up to 10 metres. VGG-Face is going to be a useful algorithm for UAV use cases up to 15 metres, whilst as the distance increases, the accuracy will be reduced significantly. FaceNet512 is the best algorithm of all. It is going to have good accuracy at every distance concerned in this study, making it a highly useful algorithm for face verification from UAVs. Finally, although OpenFace and Dlib are fast algorithms, the accuracy they achieve is very low, and they will only be useful at close distances (less than 2 metres). Therefore, they are not suitable for face verification at long distances. Table E.5 shows a summary of the results obtained for each algorithm. The first column shows how fast each of the algorithms is. The second column shows which is the highest distance where the algorithms can verify correctly with reasonable accuracy. Finally, the last column shows the overall recommendation for the use of the algorithms in UAV-based use cases.

Table E.5: Results comparison for each face verification algorithm

Algorithm	Inference time	Maximum verification distance	Overall recommendation for UAVs
ArcFace	Medium	10 metres	Recommended
OpenFace	Fast	2 metres	Not recommended
FaceNet512	Slow	20 metres	Highly recommended
Dlib	Very fast	2 metres	Not recommended
VGGFace	Very Slow	10 metres	Not recommended

E.5 Concluding remarks

In this paper, we have conducted a comprehensive comparison among five state-of-the-art face verification algorithms with a proposed pipeline for executing these algorithms and obtaining empirical results. In order to conduct a more inclusive analysis, the UAV-UWS dataset has been expanded to add two new distances (2 and 20 metres) to have six in total, compared with the previous preliminary study where four distances (5, 7, 10 and 15 metres) were investigated. The algorithms have been compared based on different metrics such as their inference time, similarity indexes distribution, building time and the size of the weights file.

Our findings indicate that FaceNet512 emerges as the algorithm that will have the best accuracy in UAV use cases, as demonstrated by the results obtained from the experiments. While VGG-Face and ArcFace will also have good accuracy, they perform less optimally at long distances (more than 10 meters). Notably, VGG-Face is the slowest algorithm among the concerned algorithms. OpenFace and Dlib are the fastest algorithms but exhibit reduced accuracy when used with UAVs, and will only have good performance at really close distances (less than 2 meters). As a result, our recommendation for UAV face verification applications leans towards FaceNet512 and ArcFace. FaceNet512 will have better accuracy than ArcFace at long distances although it is a slower algorithm. Therefore, the choice of one algorithm or the other will depend on the requirements of the specific use case.

For future work, one of the previously recommended algorithms will be chosen to perform face verification from UAVs. The pipeline will be enhanced for that specific algorithm, and an appropriate threshold will be defined. The video feed from the UAV will be transmitted

via a wireless network, such as 4G or 5G, and visualised alongside the face verification results in a Ground Control Station.

Moreover, in follow-up publications, the accuracy of each of the algorithms can be obtained using different calculations to define the optimal thresholds, such as maximising the accuracy, the F1-score or defining a FAR limit.

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Appendix F

UWS-YOLO extended architecture visualisation

Appendix G

Ethical Compliance

There are two different ethical considerations that have been diligently addressed all along the execution of this doctoral journey. This section will provide a detailed description for each of them together with the procedures carried out to ensure the maximum level of ethical compliance with respect to the current legislation available in both the UK and EU.

G.1 Usage of Datasets

Four out of the five publications that are contained in this portfolio-based PhD thesis are making use of the following already available datasets: WiderFace [23] and Arcadian-IoT Faces [9]. These datasets consist of a set of images in which people appear. Thus, it is worth explaining them in detail.

WiderFace: This is a publicly available dataset, accessible by everyone that is composed of 32,00 images and nearly 394,000 labelled faces and that has been released to the community under the “Creative Common License”. This dataset is licensed by the following authors: Shuo Yang, Ping Luo, Chen Change Loy and Xiaoou Tang. The license allows unrestricted usage of the dataset providing a protective legal framework for the safe usage of such dataset.

ARCADIAN-IoT Dataset: The non-publicly available ARCADIAN-IoT dataset, containing images of 20 volunteers’ faces. It was collected by the University of West of Scotland as part of a European research project, *Arcadian-IoT*, for the exclusive purpose of research

and dissemination. The project underwent comprehensive ethical and data protection review, conducted by a dedicated Ethical Board with support from the law firm E-Lex and oversight by the European Commission. This process established Full GDPR and ethical compliance, documented in several project deliverables, including **D5.5 - ARCADIAN-IoT Use Cases Validation and Legal Compliance** and **D4.3 - Vertical Plane of ARCADIAN-IoT**.

The ARCADIAN-IoT project was subject to rigorous ethical review, as evidenced by several deliverables focused on the ethical and data protection framework:

- **D7.1: H - Requirement n°1:** This deliverable outlined the procedures for recruiting participants and obtaining informed consent, including templates of consent forms and participant information sheets. Special attention was given to the involvement of vulnerable individuals, ensuring GDPR compliance and participant understanding.
- **D7.3: POPD - Requirement n°3:** This deliverable confirmed the appointment of a Data Protection Officer (DPO), ensuring that data subjects were informed of their rights and provided the DPO's contact information. It also established the legal basis for processing sensitive data and described the data minimization principle. Security and confidentiality measures were outlined, including anonymization and pseudonymization techniques, to safeguard participants' data.
- **D7.5: GEN – Requirement n°6:** The Ethics Board was established to address ethics issues identified in the Ethics Summary Report, particularly those related to human research. This Board's mandate included overseeing participant protection and data handling, ensuring that GDPR and ethical guidelines were followed across all aspects of the project.
- **D7.6: GEN – Requirement n°7 and D7.7: GEN – Requirement n°8:** These deliverables documented the Ethics Board's ongoing assessment of ethics issues, including the protection of personal data, security, and general research ethics. These reports confirmed the project's commitment to complying with EU standards in all aspects of data use and participant rights.

- **D1.7: Arcadian-IoT Ethics Guide:** This document served as a comprehensive ethics guide for project partners, detailing the EU legal framework for data protection and providing guidelines to ensure responsible research. Recommendations included specific technical and organizational measures to uphold privacy and data protection, aligning with the project's ethical commitments.

The complete executive summary of these deliverables is provided in Appendix G.3.

Throughout the project, these deliverables confirmed that data processing and security standards were thoroughly evaluated and met EU data privacy and ethics regulations. The dataset used in my thesis-related publications was handled according to the Arcadian-IoT project's guidelines and GDPR principles:

- **Data Minimisation:** Only essential data was collected, namely, the images of volunteers' faces. No identifying information, such as names, was linked to the images, ensuring anonymity.
- **Purpose Limitation:** The dataset was collected strictly for the research project's scope, with explicit volunteer consent covering the research, analysis, and dissemination of results, including academic outputs such as my thesis.
- **Storage Limitation:** The data will be retained only for the duration necessary to complete the project and its dissemination phase, after which it will be securely deleted.
- **Integrity and Confidentiality:** To safeguard confidentiality, the dataset is stored in an encrypted database, accessible only to authorized project team members, ensuring compliance with data security requirements.

All the 20 volunteers involved in the creation of the dataset provided written informed consent (Appendix G.4), with the GDPR and ethical requirements of the project approved by the European Commission, the Ethical Board and the law firm E-LEX overseeing the project. Additionally,

Since it was not publicly available, University of the West of Scotland was requested to confirm their dataset was GDPR compliance. (Appendix G.5).

G.2 Usage of Artificial Intelligence for Face Verification

The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for face verification and detection in this PhD research raised some ethical and legal considerations. To address these comprehensively, several measures were implemented to ensure compliance with UK and EU legislation, including the EU AI Act and the UK and EU GDPR, safeguarding individual rights during the development and application of face verification technology.

The EU AI Act introduces a risk-based framework for AI systems, categorizing real-time biometric identification in public spaces as high-risk and subject to stringent requirements. However, as outlined in Article 2(6), the AI Act exempts AI systems developed exclusively for research, such as the one created for this thesis.

Nevertheless, to ensure compliance with applicable regulations, this research incorporated the following measures:

- **Data minimisation:** Only the data strictly necessary to train and execute the models was used. The data was limited to the specific purposes of the thesis and its defined use cases.
- **Purpose limitation:** It was ensured that the AI models in this thesis were developed and used solely for research purposes. Moreover, the use cases where are used are limited to the ones defined in the thesis, not including any defence or law enforcement use cases.
- **Storage limitation:** All data and models were stored only for the duration of the thesis. After completion, the data will be deleted, ensuring storage is limited to the project's scope.
- **Integrity and confidentiality (Security):** The computer where the models, and the data were stored was secured with password limiting external access. Moreover, the

database where the datasets were stored was encrypted and secured avoiding any external unwanted access that would create a security breach.

Furthermore, this research avoided practices prohibited by the EU AI Act, such as untargeted scraping of facial images from the internet or CCTV footage to create face verification databases, and the use of biometric identification systems in public spaces for law enforcement purposes.

In conclusion, the face verification system developed in this thesis complies with the regulations of both the UK and the EU. A combination of technical and procedural safeguards addressed legal and ethical concerns, ensuring alignment with the EU AI Act and UK/EU GDPR.

G.3 ARCADIAN-IoT Deliverables Related to Ethical Procedures and GDPR

- **D7.1: H - Requirement n°1:**

- The procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants.
- The informed consent procedures including personal data processing that will be implemented for the participation of humans
- Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) including personal data processing.
- Clarifications regarding the involvement of vulnerable individuals (including children) or groups.

- **D7.3: POPD - Requirement n°3:**

- Confirmation that the host institution has appointed a Data Protection Officer (“DPO”) and that the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research.
- Identification of the legal basis for the processing of sensitive personal data.
- Explanation of how all of the data the hosts intend to process is relevant and limited to the purposes of the research project (in accordance with the data minimisation principle).
- A description of the technical and organisational measures that will be implemented to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subjects/research participants.
- A description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing.

- Description of the anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques that will be implemented.
- Evaluation of the ethics risks related to the data processing activities of the project.
- **D7.5: GEN – Requirement n°6:**
 - Considering the potential ethics issues raised by the research to be pursued within Arcadian-IoT project, as identified within the Ethics Summary Report, an Ethics Board (EB) must be established. This document presents the members of this EB.
- **D7.6: GEN – Requirement n°7:**
 - This deliverable addresses GEN – Requirement n°7, presenting Arcadian-IoT's Ethics Board report focusing the project's status with respect to relevant ethics issues, in particular associated to research with humans.
- **D7.7: GEN – Requirement n°8:**
 - This deliverable addresses GEN – Requirement n°8, presenting Arcadian-IoT's second and final Ethics Board report focusing on the project's status with respect to relevant ethics issues, in particular associated to research with humans, protection of personal data, security, safety and general ethics issues.
- **D1.7: Arcadian-IoT Ethics guide:**
 - The objective of this document is to support project partners in conducting the research and innovation process as well as the implementation of the ARCADIAN-IoT system in compliance with ethics principles, as well as EU legal and otherwise regulatory framework, with particular emphasis on privacy and data protection.
 - This document should be read in conjunction with section 5.1 of the project DoA and take in account the analysis conducted in the Deliverables 7.1 and 7.3.

- First of all, in order to make all partners aware about the framework, section 1 illustrates a general introduction to the ethics principles and EU legal context on data protection, to which the consortium has to be compliant in any project activity.
- Based on that, section 2 provides a set of recommendations that ARCADIAN-IoT should concretely apply to ensure its compliance to EU data privacy regulations and laws and responsible research, adopting organisational and technical measures. Such a set of recommendations is not meant to be exhaustive, but they pave the way for a common understanding of the ethics matters within ARCADIAN-IoT.

G.4 Arcadian-IoT Faces Dataset Informed Consent Form

This subsection of the appendix presents the Informed Consent Form provided to volunteers for the collection of the ARCADIAN-IoT Faces dataset.

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Integration of authentication service for Arcadian-IoT project and its dissemination

Part I: Information Sheet

This Informed consent has two parts: the first one, in which we share with you some information about ARCADIAN-IoT and your participation in the activities; the second one is where we collect your signature, if you decide to participate.

About the project

The following is being conducted as part of the ARCADIAN-IoT project, funded by the European Commission (GA n. 101020259) with the coordination and under the responsibility of University of the West of Scotland as Partner of ARCADIAN-IoT Consortium. ARCADIAN-IoT has the goal of developing and making available an innovative, advanced framework for trust, security and privacy management in IoT systems to promote trustworthy IoT systems. ARCADIAN-IoT aims to fill a gap in the IoT threat intelligence landscape by providing a novel IoT- specific Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) approach, which supports integrated, automated and privacy- preserved IoT threat information sharing.

For further information about the ARCADIAN-IoT project, please visit our website at: <https://www.arcadian-iot.eu/>.

About the Activity

This activity aims to integrate the authentication service between the different partners of the project. For that purpose some images will be requested and stored in a database. The images can also be used for dissemination and research purposes of the project.

You may ask for any other information about the activity to the researcher who has provided this form to you.

About your participation

Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary and you may change your mind at any moment, without any consequence or prejudice for you.

You will not receive any personal benefit for your participation in this activity. Your participation may help us to integrate our component with the authentication process and with the dissemination of the project. No risk is foreseen.

Some information about your data.

Within this Activity we collect the following data:

- Face images from different angles.

Confidentially

Your personal data will not be transferable to any other entity external to the Consortium, except in the case of respecting the legal framework on data protection.

Besides, we have a specific procedure to collect, store, protect and destroy your information collected today and are responsible to ensure the accomplishment of regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regards to the processing of personal data.

Who to contact

If you have any questions about processing your data, you can ask our researchers or later, contact us at the address below and we will answer you within a time period not exceeding one month.

You can also contact our data protection officer (DPO) at this email address dataprotection@uws.ac.uk to withdraw your consent at any time or to request access rectification or restriction of processing notwithstanding the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority.

You can ask me any more questions about any part of the research study if you wish to. However, we want to inform you that:

All the information collected will be anonymized or, if anonymizing corrupts the project purpose, de-identified and treated as confidential by the researchers. If we collect your demographic information, it will be used only to contextualize the statistical analysis of the aggregate results and not be published or used in any form, rather than the above mentioned statistical analysis;

All the data will be securely stored and used only for the purpose of the present research, in accordance with ethical requirements;

The overall results generated from this activity may be published, in an anonymized manner, in journal articles, conference presentations, via any other mode of scientific exchange, and dissemination that will be seen as appropriate by the researchers. However, participants' anonymity will always be protected, and all data will be de-identified.

Who to contact

If you have any questions or concerns about the Activity or in the future, please feel free to contact:

Partner contact data

Jose M. Alcaraz Calero
jose.alcaraz-calero@uws.ac.uk

Researcher contact data

Julio Diez Tomillo
julio.diez-tomillo@uws.ac.uk

Project coordinator contact data

Sergio Figueiredo
sfigueiredo@ipn.pt

Project's DPO contact

Carmela Occhipinti
carmela.occhipinti@gmail.com

Part II: Informed Consent

Participant's statement of Informed Consent

I have been invited to participate in the integration process of the authentication service and the dissemination of the project. I have read and understood the foregoing information. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and I've received a proper answer to my questions. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in these integration process of the authentication service, the dissemination and research within the project, and with the processing of my personal data in line with GDPR. I also give my consent for my facial images to be stored in the database for research and project purposes.

By signing below, I confirm that I have read and understood the terms of this consent form, and I freely and voluntarily consent to the use of my facial image as described above.

Full name and surname

Signature

ID Number

Date

Thank you for your collaboration!

G.5 Statement of Implementation and Compliance with GDPR

Statement of implementation and compliance with the GDPR

University of the West of Scotland, with registered office at High Street, Paisley and registered with charity number SC002520 represented by its legal representative Emma Cuckow, Data Protection Officer hereby

Declares and guarantees

- to know and to have fully implemented the provisions of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (the "GDPR") and further applicable laws on the protection of personal data (the "**Applicable Law**"); and therefore
- the processes carried out as part of its activities as data processor pursuant to the GDPR and in the ARCADIAN-IoT project are compliant with the provisions of the Applicable Law; and specifically
- with reference to each processing activity, a suitable legal basis under Article 6 of the GDPR has been identified and applies;
- to have a proper organisation to process the data in full compliance with Applicable Law, including the security aspect.

Paisley, 6th December 2021

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